

Transformative Biodiversity Innovations

Deliverable 2.2

November 2025

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Introduction

How this deliverable was created

The Deliverable D2.2 – “Transformative Biodiversity Innovations” is the outcome of a process that unfolded throughout the entire duration of WP2 within the BIOTraCes project, through a sequence of progressive stages that gradually led to the construction of a shared analytical framework. D2.2 represents the synthesis of a trajectory in which moments of methodological reflection, successive monitoring activities, partner exchange workshops, and field-based activities mutually informed and reinforced the evolution of the research questions and interpretive categories. Within this broader framework, the research team of the University of Catania, as responsible of Task 2.2, coordinated a cumulative process in which the diverse contributions of all partners were gathered, discussed, and translated into a common analytical architecture, articulated across the various sections of D2.2.

From the earliest phases of the project, this deliverable was conceived as a long-term outcome, to be constructed progressively and in close dialogue with the development of the case studies. The focus was directed not solely at the collection of empirical findings, but also at the definition of a conceptual and methodological framework capable of valuing the heterogeneity of local contexts while ensuring a strong degree of comparability across the nine case studies. This approach required theoretical–methodological elaboration and fieldwork to advance in parallel, sustained by a continuous movement back and forth between the project’s core questions, the materials generated through empirical investigation, and the collective reflections developed within the research consortium. The sections that follow trace the successive phases that shaped this deliverable. Beginning by briefly reflecting on the contribution of Deliverable D1.5, whose methodological and theoretical foundations informed several dimensions of the process, and then move through the shared reflections initiated with D2.1, the progressive insights emerging from the monitoring cycles and bilateral meetings, the comparative dialogues fostered during consortium workshops, and the consolidation of these elements into the final analytical structure presented in the subsequent paragraphs.

A moment of collective reflection

An essential contribution to the collective orientation of WP2 was provided by Deliverable D1.5 – *Theories Transformative Innovations Analysis* (submitted at M12). D1.5 offered the consortium a comprehensive methodological and conceptual foundation from which subsequent tasks could draw. Through its systematic review of transition literature, scenario analysis and back-casting methods, and its guidance on stakeholder and right-holder mapping, D1.5 equipped partners with shared tools for analysing the conditions under which biodiversity innovations emerge, succeed, or encounter barriers. Equally important were its contributions on narrative and discourse analysis, interpretative policy analysis, and science–policy interface studies, which informed the consortium’s attention to diverse value systems, positionalities, institutional lock-ins, and knowledge-use patterns. In this way, D1.5 served as a methodological compass that shaped the interpretive sensitivities and analytical orientations that would later be refined within WP2, preparing the ground for the structured reflection that characterised the development of D2.1.

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An important early milestone in the process leading to the creation of D2.2 is represented by Deliverable 2.1 – Case Study Plan, which provided partners with a structured space for joint reflection on the objectives, conceptual focus, and operational modalities of WP2. D2.1 allowed the consortium to clarify the key issues that would subsequently orient the development of the work: the need to understand the diverse configurations of human–nature relations across the case studies; the importance of identifying the mechanisms through which inequalities and marginalisations are produced and reproduced; the role played by locally grounded actors in driving biodiversity-related innovations; and the broader significance of institutional and socio-political transformation processes.

At this stage, the six thematic areas of Task 2.2 concerning mechanisms of inclusion and exclusion, power lock-ins, inclusive measures, the role of niche innovators, bottom-up innovations, and emerging forms of intervention were discussed collectively and acknowledged as a shared analytical framework for the forthcoming phases of WP2. D2.1 thus functioned as a moment of conceptual clarification and alignment, enabling partners to confront their expectations, refine their research assumptions, and compare methodological orientations. This dialogue contributed to the construction of a shared vocabulary and interpretive horizon, which reappears in D2.2 in the form of structured questions and recurring analytical categories.

In parallel, D2.1 supported a collective reflection on methodological triangulation and on the application of participatory action research across different contexts. The exchange on methodological configurations guided partners in identifying coherent combinations of field-based methods, participatory tools, and documentary or historical analyses, thereby laying the groundwork for the subsequent integration between methodological choices and the analysis of transformative change. In this sense, the case study plan fostered a first substantive connection between the objectives of Task 2.2 and the concrete research practices that would unfold within the case studies.

Monitoring Forms as spaces of progressive analytical convergence

The core of the process that led to the creation of the *Transformative Biodiversity Innovations* deliverable is located in the five monitoring cycles conducted throughout WP2 and in the corresponding bilateral meetings coordinated by UNICT. Each monitoring cycle followed a two-step structure: first, partners completed a written monitoring form; second, in the following weeks, UNICT held a bilateral meeting with each team to discuss, refine, and further interpret the material submitted. This clarifies why each cycle covers a time span (e.g., M8–10): the labelled interval reflects the combined duration of the written phase and the subsequent bilateral discussion. Together, these paired phases created a continuous sequence of analytical checkpoints through which the evolution of the research became visible and collectively assessable.

Far from serving merely administrative functions, monitoring forms and bilateral meetings acted as regular arenas of joint reflection, enabling partners to articulate ongoing methodological choices, contextual developments, and analytical insights. The iterative nature of these cycles allowed trends to be identified early, facilitated comparability across case studies, and progressively shaped the questions that now structure Deliverable 2.2.

- ✓ The first full monitoring cycle (M8–10) gathered essential information regarding the initial configuration of each case study, the early role played by societal partners, and the networks of actors already engaged or to be involved. The responses described emergent forms of collaboration, evolving levels of trust, strategies for engaging underrepresented groups, and initial interactions with communities, associations, institutions, and other stakeholders. Several themes surfaced here that would accompany the entire trajectory of WP2: the coexistence of heterogeneous views on nature, the varying accessibility of social groups, and the need to understand how values, narratives, and practices shape relationships

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between people, territories, and biodiversity. The bilateral meetings that followed enabled deeper examination of these elements, clarification of critical points, and their first operational alignment with the thematic areas defined in Task 2.2.

- ✓ A second moment of structured reflection occurred with the monitoring form embedded within D2.1, corresponding to (M11-14). This form accompanied the Single Case Study Plan and asked partners to outline research team composition, preliminary engagement strategies with societal partners, early selections of methodological configurations, expectations regarding triangulation, and initial hypotheses related to human–nature relations in each context. The form also invited partners to assess potential challenges, reflect on their timeline for fieldwork, and specify the types of support they expected from WP2 coordination. This monitoring, fully integrated into the D2.1 process, constitutes an important transitional moment: it enabled the consolidation of the methodological foundations of each case study and established a baseline for the subsequent monitoring cycles, thereby becoming the second step in the overall sequence of five rounds initiating the translation of D2.1's conceptual reflections into the analytical architecture of D2.2.
- ✓ During the third monitoring cycle (M16–18), partners provided a more advanced picture of field activities and emerging participatory dynamics. They were invited to describe how relationships with societal partners had evolved, what joint activities had been carried out, how spaces of co-research were beginning to take shape, and which local initiatives could be interpreted as emerging biodiversity innovations. The responses demonstrated that categories discussed during the initial phase, such as bottom-up innovations, key actors, and mechanisms of inclusion and exclusion, were now actively informing the interpretation of case-study phenomena. In the bilateral meetings, UNICT deepened this dialogue by facilitating analytical connections between individual case trajectories and the conceptual framework of Task 2.2. At this stage, the core paragraphs of D2.2 began to crystallise themes linked to inclusion/exclusion and the role of key actors were gradually systematised into identifiable components that would later form the backbone of the deliverable.
- ✓ The fourth monitoring cycle (M24–26) further strengthened this progressive dynamic by introducing a more systematic reflection on the relationship between methods, PAR, and the analysis of socio-ecological transformations. Partners were asked to explain how methodological triangulation was being implemented and adapted, what role societal partners played in the co-production of knowledge, and how participatory activities contributed to the emergence of transformative dynamics. Their responses provided more detailed accounts of mechanisms of inclusion and exclusion, the figures acting as catalysts for change, the forms of conflict and negotiation between actors, and local experiments oriented toward biodiversity regeneration. Much of what constitutes the core of deliverable 2.2 finds its first structured expression here: the questions of the fourth monitoring cycle closely anticipate the analytical architecture of the deliverable, particularly the sections that examine mechanisms of inclusion/exclusion, niche innovators, and bottom-up innovations.
- ✓ The last monitoring cycle (M32–34) took place at a more advanced stage of WP2, close to the drafting of D2.2. This round focused predominantly on processes of knowledge co-production and on activities accompanying the testing and assessment of transformative interventions planned under subsequent tasks. Although this cycle is less central to the original formulation of D2.2's structure, themes raised here – especially the role of participatory workshops, focus groups, and the principles of the Theory of Transformative Change – contributed to consolidating the transformative perspective adopted in the deliverable. In this sense, the last monitoring cycle also forms an integral part of the progressive

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construction of deliverable 2.2, by providing a final layer of reflexive insight into how innovations were being enacted and interpreted across the case studies.

Across all five monitoring cycles, the alternation between written forms and bilateral meetings produced a progressive, multi-layered interpretive trajectory, through which empirical observations, methodological reflections and conceptual elaborations converged. This iterative process allowed the consortium to refine, cycle after cycle, the analytical questions that now organise the deliverable Transformative Biodiversity Innovations, and to root them firmly in the lived research experience of each case study.

The Mértola Workshop and collective dialogues across the consortium

Another significant stage in the genesis of deliverable 2.2 was the workshop held in Mértola during the consortium's second live meeting. This occasion offered partners the opportunity to share field materials, preliminary analyses, and emerging interpretations of the dynamics observed in their respective case studies, with a particular focus on the mechanisms that foster or hinder biodiversity-related innovations. The case presentations highlighted how, despite the diversity of contexts, several recurrent issues surfaced: tensions between local practices and institutional policies; conflicts between economic interests and conservation concerns; challenges in recognising situated knowledge and community-based experiences; and the presence of creative forms of experimentation involving heterogeneous constellations of actors.

The collective discussions brought several shared patterns into sharper focus. In many cases, innovations favouring biodiversity were in marginal or interstitial spaces vis-à-vis dominant institutional configurations, drawing strength from social and affective networks that were not always formally acknowledged within decision-making arenas. In other cases, transformative dynamics appeared to be rooted in shifting values and meanings attached to nature and territory, where cultural practices, historical memories, and moral sensibilities played a central role in shaping perceptions and motivating action. These exchanges reinforced the need for an analytically nuanced reading of inclusive and exclusive mechanisms, of the positionalities and strategies of "niche innovators" and of the ways in which bottom-up innovations interact with and potentially reshape governance arrangements.

Alongside the Mértola workshop, the development of this deliverable was supported by additional moments of structured dialogue among partners, during which UNICT presented and discussed intermediate versions of the analytical questions and the emerging structure of the deliverable. These encounters enabled a collective examination of possible paragraph articulations, the refinement of conceptual clarity and terminological precision, and the verification of coherence between the Task 2.2 framework and the empirical trajectories unfolding across the case studies. Partner feedback guided a sequence of increasingly targeted revisions, through which the structure of deliverable was stabilised and consolidated, ensuring both internal comparability and sensitivity to the specificities of each local context.

The Internal Structure of D2.2

The outcome of this progressive trajectory of exchange, monitoring, and collective reflection is embodied in the internal structure of this deliverable, conceived as a single chapter dedicated to biodiversity-related transformations and articulated into a series of coherently interconnected sections. The chapter opens with this introductory component (1.1), which reconstructs the sequence of milestones that shaped the deliverable and clarifies the role of the various methodological devices, D2.1, the monitoring cycles, workshops, and internal discussions, in the formulation of its analytical questions. The

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subsequent sections develop, in a systematic manner, the core thematic areas of Task 2.2 as they emerged through this cumulative process.

- ✓ Section 1.2 focuses on mechanisms of inclusion and exclusion, examining how values, social attitudes, knowledge practices, and economic arrangements contribute to structuring hierarchies, access, recognition, and silences within the case study contexts. The analyses presented here draw directly from the first three monitoring cycles and from collective dialogues, where issues related to marginalised groups, value conflicts, and power relations progressively gained centrality. This section highlights how such mechanisms shape the capacity of biodiversity innovations to emerge, consolidate, and become embedded in socio-ecological systems.
- ✓ Section 1.3 addresses niche innovators and key players, emphasising the individuals and collectives who animate innovation processes across the project's diverse contexts. The profiles of these figures, their public biographies, the networks they inhabit, the repertoires of action they mobilise, and the relationships they maintain with institutional and non-institutional actors, are grounded in the analyses developed during the second and third monitoring cycles. This section shows that these innovators often operate from hybrid positionalities at the intersection of formal and informal spheres, and that their actions contribute to reshaping imaginaries, practices, and institutional arrangements.
- ✓ Section 1.4 turns to bottom-up innovations with transformative potential. It examines the practices, initiatives, and projects that emerge from local contexts and that, across the case studies, demonstrate the capacity to affect human–nature relations in substantive and enduring ways. The section highlights the collective nature of many of these innovations, their temporalities, the conflicts and negotiations in which they are embedded, and the conditions that enable or constrain their scalability. Much of this analytical foundation was first articulated during the Mértola workshop, where partners discussed concrete examples of drivers and barriers in a comparative fashion, and was subsequently refined through later monitoring and reporting phases.
- ✓ Section 1.5 offers a mapping of interventions already underway or in preparation within the case studies, demonstrating how these interventions position themselves along a continuum between emergent innovations and institutional policy frameworks. This section functions as a bridge to the subsequent tasks of WP2, particularly the experimental activities anticipated in Task 2.4. Its placement within deliverable 2.2 makes explicit the connection between the analysis of innovations and the design of transformative actions, underscoring the continuity between analytical reflection and practical experimentation.

In addition to these thematic components, the deliverable concludes with a comparative synthesis section, which distils the main findings on transformative biodiversity innovations across all nine case studies. This synthesis not only consolidates the insights emerging from the preceding sections but also provides a conceptual and empirical springboard for the parallel deliverables D2.3 and D2.4, which deepen, respectively, the cross-case analysis and the elaboration of transformative pathways.

A Reading Guide to D2.2

This deliverable may be approached as a structured pathway through the core analytical dimensions of biodiversity-related transformations. The opening section retraces the progressive process through which the analytical framework was developed. The subsequent sections guide the reader from the examination of inclusion and exclusion mechanisms to the role of niche innovators and key players, to the analysis of bottom-up innovations with transformative potential, and finally to the mapping of emerging

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interventions. The concluding comparative synthesis connects these elements across all nine case studies and provides a conceptual bridge toward the parallel deliverables D2.3 and D2.4. Together, these sections offer an integrated perspective on how transformative biodiversity innovations take shape, evolve, and interact with governance structures across diverse socio-ecological contexts.

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D2.2

Urban Schoolyard Biodiversity Lab

BC3, Spain

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Summary

Summary of Deliverable

This case study is about schoolyard greening in public pre- and primary schools in Vitoria-Gasteiz, Basque Country, Spain. In concretely, it follows the implementation of a municipal schoolyard greening pilot program initiated in 2022 as a response to a manifesto of the municipal associations of parents demanding healthier and greener school environments a year earlier. Administrated by the city hall and funded by different public grants, as of 2025 14 schoolyards have been renaturalized through replacing them hard with permeable, natural surfaces such as sand and soil and the adding of plants, trees, and lawn areas, nature-based play equipment and garden elements. The process was implemented through the collaboration of different municipal entities and, in various degrees, together with the educational communities of the different schools.

We zoom on to the various challenges derived from a combination of complex administrative structures and responsibilities scattered across different institutional entities, plural imaginaries attached to the role of schoolyards in education and urban planning, and a diversity of actors involved and needed to make the schoolyard interventions successful. Concretely, we disentangle the various challenges, but also potentials of the current program structure together with multiple actors to envision a schoolyard greening program in future, where biodiversity and equity are at center of the design, use, and narrative of the schoolyard.

The overarching research objective is to explore to what extent green schoolyards can be part of a wider transformative change towards a (bio)diverse society. For this end, we applied a participatory action research approach in close collaboration with BIOTraCes societal partner, the Environmental Studies Center of Vitoria-Gasteiz, and the municipal Department of Education leading the program. We further collaborated with representatives of the local educational communities, the main recipients of the schoolyard transformations.

We draw on documents and archival data as well as field- and workshop-based data. We found that the municipal schoolyard greening pilot program in its current state of governance, regulations, and broader paradigms contains both barriers and opportunities for transformative, nature-inclusive change in the social-ecological system. The multi-level governance embedded in two high impact sectors of urbanism and education with their past and current dominating paradigms is still based on unequal (power) relations resulting from rigid and complex top-down structures and furthering human disconnection from nature. However, as actors active in schoolyard transformations navigate these barriers, their initiatives can be considered challengers to current lock-ins.

Overall, we encountered throughout our research a relational narrative shift. This can be seen, e.g., in a variety of actors' stronger emphasis on care as being learned and practiced in the schoolyards towards other peers and nature. This shift implies longer participatory processes, potentially enabling a deeper integration of educational communities into the decision-making process in a way that their concrete needs are at the heart of the schoolyard transformations. The process of learning between institutional and educational community actors has already led to an adaptation of processes to overcome previous shortcomings, leverage current program successes and respond to the educational communities' feedback. This shows potential for an adaptive co-governance form in future of municipal schoolyard greening. This document focuses on the case study's transformative biodiversity innovations, including an analysis of inclusion and exclusion mechanisms, niche innovators and key players, scalable bottom-up innovations, and an initial mapping of interventions.

Transformative Biodiversity Innovations (D2.2)

1.1 Analysis of Inclusion/Exclusion Mechanisms

In the following, we describe the exclusion and inclusion mechanisms and practices. The aspects mentioned are, however, not black and white. That is, some of the current practices identified contain trade-offs that can lead to both inclusion and exclusion.

The nature of the municipal schoolyard greening program being constituted as top-down, adult-centric approach creates exclusionary mechanisms and furthers power imbalances:

First, the top-down approach is based on an **adult-centric perspective of children's needs and well-being**. Children, although primary target group as recipients of the biodiversity innovation, are, as for now, not sufficiently included in the decision making regarding their own schoolyard. This is the manifestation of an overarching societal adult-centric paradigm where children are not attributed to agencies to articulate and make decisions regarding their own needs and wellbeing. This adult-centric paradigm becomes also apparent in the broader hegemonic educational paradigm of the public education sector centering on classroom-based learning to enable standard-based evaluations of pupils (PISA). This educational paradigm has for a long time prioritized cognitive ways of knowing competitive, individual learning, at the expense of other knowledge such as affective and practical ways of knowing, as well as collaborative and relational learning practices that could enable deep connections with nature (Bonal and Tarabini, 2013). While some of these approaches have recently been taken up in educational policy, structures and practices in the education system will take more time to adapt.

This challenges the implementation of alternative forms of learning, such as experimental and embodied methodologies aiming for an increased nature connection that is also more attentive to children's worldviews and perspectives. The current top-down approach to teaching and education more broadly gives little to no space for those alternative human-nature relationships children are or may be developing. In order to overcome the exclusion of children from the decision making concerning their own realities, there needs to be a shift towards children-centric decision making approaches in which children are considered equal actors that know best what is best for them, through e.g. a real integration and participation in the project design and implementation holding decision making power of the schoolyards design, use, and its maintenance. There is further a need to provide educational spaces that enable children to observe, interact, and learn from and with nature at their own pace and without evaluation pressures (O'Brien and Howard, 2016). Few schools exist that are shifting their educational model, e.g. Escuelas libres (Free schools), however, those are private and hence raise issues of justice in terms of who has access to alternative educational models (WS February 2024).

Second, the top-down, adult-centric approach **prioritizes top-down technical and expert knowledge in the choice of schoolyard design**. Research participants mentioned the difficulties of communicating architectural plans of the schoolyard design to the educational communities not used to the technical language and drawings, which caused misunderstandings in regard to the project design (field notes, meetings with municipal technical staff, 2024-25). That is, the use of technical knowledge posed in some school communities as a challenge towards support for biodiversity innovation as it made the understanding of the planned interventions more difficult. Further, the plants chosen for the greening interventions are those that, according to adult experts' knowledge, are most beneficial/instrumental, in terms of climate change adaptation and educational impact – however, in respect to the choice of plants we encounter many different perspectives, ranging from local vs exotic plants, wild vs. botanical, “clean” vs “dirty” nature.

The adult-centric approach to the municipal schoolyard greening program with its prioritization of technical knowledge was also mentioned in the multi-actors workshops

(February and April, 2025): participants belonging to the educational communities mentioned that the whole idea of renaturalization of schoolyards and the framing around nature-based elements does ignore the main function of schoolyards, namely of being places of play. While nature is important, the focus here should be on the children and their need for creative and free play, which can be achieved, among others, through the integration of nature. According to these perspectives, the focus on nature-based elements distracts from their core objective of **integrating experimental and embodied play and learning** in the day-to-day educational activities.

Third, the top-down approach embedded in a scattered **administrative structure prevents bottom-up actors from making decisions regarding the schoolyard intervention**, including its design and implementation. This endangers over the long run wide societal support for biodiversity innovation, as it overruns agency of non-institutional actors. In this specific case of a municipal schoolyard greening program this may further be perceived as process of co-optation in which local policymakers may have instrumentalized a social demand for improved educational environments for their own political agendas, e.g. in municipal elections. The uptake of the manifesto for improved school environments into a municipal program translated the program structure into one shaped and decided by institutional actors. This, in part, is also due to complex governance fragmented across many institutional entities that complicates a more inclusive multi-actor process (Interviews with educational community actors, 2024).

Fourth, following the top-down and technocratic approach to schoolyard greening, **on the discursive level there is an emphasis on the instrumental benefits of biodiversity innovation**. The increase of biodiversity, and ultimately more-than-human actors, is considered a welcomed side benefit, but not core objective of a municipal program titled "renaturalization of schoolyards" (multi-actor workshop, February 2025). This overemphasis on the instrumental framing of urban biodiversity challenges a holistic integration of more-than-human actors through prioritizing values relating to care and community and impedes the creation and advancements of emotional bonds of human-nature relationships. While research participants representing educational actors report anecdotal evidence of changed behaviors of children, including practice of care for the schoolyard, its biodiversity and other children, and a reduction of conflictive behaviors since the greening interventions (notes fieldtrip, 2023, interviews with educational actors 2024), these aspects are still only marginal in the political discourse that frames nature through its instrumental contribution to children's well-being or urban resilience (Kotsila et al., 2021; Neidig et al., 2023). To achieve closer human-nature relationships, the overall narrative of the program needs to be more inclusive of various forms of human-nature relationships. This also includes in-depth evaluations of relationships formed and strengthened by a biodiverse schoolyard.

These mechanisms of exclusion are further being derived from structural injustices, exemplified by educational segregation, that hinder vulnerable communities' participation and integration into the program.

As a result of the points mentioned above, the overarching question regards one of where lies the responsibility to steer change, that is, who should be the main driver of transformative change in the public educational sector. In this case study, parents are often mentioned as key actors. Without their implication in the program, its long-term success remains questionable. Following, the schools that have been considered successful examples of implementing green schoolyards and a changing perspective on (sustainable) education are those with strong parents' associations. Next to the schools participating in the municipal program, there are also some schools that organized the schoolyard transformation bottom-up. This happened in schools with very engaged parents, with in most cases stronger socio-economic profiles. Following, schools lacking a very active and engaged parents' association – as often the case in more marginalized communities – have shown more difficulties in accepting and maintaining biodiversity innovations. This is

deeply embedded in broader societal structures and dynamics of environmental/climate (in)justices.

Both previous research on green schoolyards and our preliminary findings have shown that the success and sustainability of schoolyard greening tend to depend on a few motivated actors in the school communities that push forward the maintenance of the schoolyard and its integration into school activities. Finding these motivated actors among the most vulnerable schools can prove hard, since these schools and their communities already face a lot of challenges, leaving little “extra” time to dedicate to schoolyard greening. There seems to be, therefore, a trade-off between positively impacting the most disadvantaged groups and empowering those dedicated to transforming schools for nature-positivity.

Despite Vitoria-Gasteiz’ municipal schoolyard greening focus on the most underprivileged and segregated schools, the program could not overcome these deeply embedded structural injustices. Even more, the use of a selection criterion based on vulnerability indicators has caused some frustration on the part of the parents’ associations, as the specific criteria for school selection have, however, not been very transparent. That is, it has not been made public why certain schools were chosen for funding while others were not. Upscaling the project will require the establishment of clear and transparent selection criteria for schools. These need to balance the degree of nature access (both in the schoolyard as well as surrounding the school), school vulnerability (in relation to both climate change impacts, such as heat vulnerability, and socio-demographic factors), and the confirmed commitment of the school communities to the greening project.

Inclusion mechanisms in this case study can be found in the program specificities on the smallest, school-based scale:

First, at the core of this biodiversity innovation is the aim to create gender-inclusive, nature-based schoolyard designs. By replacing gender-coded elements such as football pitches with natural features, the city hall seeks to redesign schoolyards in ways that challenge traditional gender roles and stereotypes. Conventional grey schoolyards often prioritize competitive sports, which tend to reproduce gendered power relations and spatial inequalities. Research has shown that girls, in such environments, typically occupy less space and engage less in physical activity— which is especially important at school age to improve psychological wellbeing, physical health and learning capacity (Raney et al., 2023). While the pilot program aspires to address these inequalities, it remains to be seen to what extent the current design of the biodiversity innovation fosters genuinely gender-inclusive spaces.

Second, the use of a vulnerability indicator as a selection criterion for participation in the schoolyard greening program seeks to support school communities that are most marginalized. Here, vulnerability refers to the socio-economic profile of school members, prioritizing schools with a higher percentage of foreign-born students to reduce segregation among children with immigrant backgrounds. In the Spanish context, the Basque Country has the second-highest rate of school segregation for foreign-born children (Murillo & Guiral, 2024). This is largely due to the prevalence of private and semi-private schools, as well as the coexistence of different language models, which, while promoting the Basque language, also complicate the integration of foreign-born students. The issue is particularly pronounced in Vitoria-Gasteiz, where some public schools are composed almost entirely of pupils with immigration backgrounds. Several of these highly segregated schools were selected for the city’s pilot greening project, with the hope that investment in greener, more attractive schoolyards might help retain local families and counteract patterns of school flight. Nevertheless, renaturalizing public schoolyards alone cannot resolve the broader structural issue of educational segregation (Cairns, 2018).

Third, a deeper involvement of children fosters a sense of ownership over the biodiversity innovation and encourages them to care for the schoolyard, its biodiversity, and their school community. Schools that implemented more

comprehensive participatory approaches reported positive outcomes regarding children's sense of ownership and belonging, supporting the development of relational values such as care, stewardship, and community. This was also highlighted by participants engaged in educational and participatory activities within the municipal greening program. Some schools went further by introducing a "care program," in which older students teach younger ones how to look after the schoolyard and its living beings. Such initiatives can strengthen human–nature and human–human relationships essential for building more inclusive, caring societies. However, these practices remain exceptions and largely depend on the initiative of individual schools and parents. Embedding children's participation into the program structure would require additional time and funding to enable meaningful, program-wide involvement in both design and implementation.

Further, the focus on nature-based design encourages play and interaction with natural elements such as trees and plants. Regular contact with nature may help children develop or strengthen their connection to the natural world — especially those who have limited access to green spaces outside of school (Chawla et al., 2014). These relationships are also meant to be reinforced through teaching, by integrating the green schoolyard into the educational process. This is supported, on the one hand, through educational workshops offered to participating schools, and on the other, by including the green schoolyard in each school's educational project—a mission statement outlining the school's vision, objectives, and values.

Lastly, **citizen science programs for monitoring birds and insects can raise awareness of schoolyards as habitats for urban biodiversity while strengthening community connections with nature.** The societal partner is implementing a citizen science program to evaluate the biodiversity impact of the schoolyard transformations, in collaboration with schools and other volunteers. Involving the local communities in the monitoring of flora and fauna aims to democratize science and enhance transparency around municipal biodiversity claims, empowering citizens to both contribute to and critically assess urban greening efforts.

1.2 Niche Innovators and Key Players

Next to the institutional technical actors, such as BIOTraCes' societal partner CEA and the municipal department of education that lead the pilot program and navigate institutional lock-ins to assure program continuity, the main bottom-up niche innovators in our case have been **the educational communities** driven by parents' associations and in part supported by individual teachers. They pushed institutions to address the shortcomings of existing schoolyard designs and initiated transformation efforts independently, **acting as key drivers of change within the social-ecological system.** After identifying issues such as contamination and noise from nearby traffic, limited contact with nature, hard surfaces, and gender-insensitive designs, 22 schools and their parents' associations signed a manifesto in 2021 demanding safe, healthy, and gender-inclusive school environments. Some schools with active parents' associations further started their own greening initiatives, e.g. by bringing plants to the school, raising money through crowdfunding, selling products, etc. for designs to remodel the schoolyards (interview with networks of municipal parents' associations, 2024).

This manifesto generated political momentum, leading a left-wing opposition party to introduce schoolyard greening to the city hall, where it passed unanimously in the form of a municipal schoolyard greening pilot program led by the CEA and the Department of Education. The municipality assumed control of the program, whereas educational communities perceive a lack of transparency and coordination with schools and parents' associations (interviews with local policymakers, 2024). The municipal program furthermore only addresses part of their demands—focusing on greening while omitting others, such as safe school commutes. Implemented by the CEA, the pilot program contains in its design a participatory process, together with the educational communities

(parents, teachers, headmaster) of the selected schools, to discuss and contrast the design proposed by the CEA, with the objective to respond to school's specific needs. The whole educational community could therefore theoretically influence the type of nature introduced, although participation was overall very limited and very few schools did participatory sessions with the school children to determine their preferences for the schoolyards. The final schoolyard designs did not include an analysis of existing bottom-up initiatives of the schools. Plans that the communities had invested their own time and money into were rejected by the city hall, because the municipal project established Nature-based Solutions as the criterium for the project, whereas some of the schools' own designs included non-nature-based elements, such as new play structures, benches, pergolas, etc. (interviews with technical institutional staff and representatives of parents' associations.)

Following, some of these niche innovators thus feel that their agency (including previous efforts of schools) is not recognised and that there is a lack of transparency and communication from the institutional side. We have therefore engaged with the niche innovators by bringing them into a much needed and so far neglected dialogue with institutional actors, to discuss how institutions can better support existing bottom-up initiatives and build on these, and how information and lessons learnt can be shared better. We aimed for countering their frustration by creating a space for dialogue together with institutional actors and empower them to continue their efforts to create more safe, healthy and sustainable school environments, such as in the multi-actor workshops implemented under BIOTraCes.

It must be noted that the niche innovators among the schools are not the marginalized ones. Vitoria-Gasteiz has one of the highest levels of school segregation of students of migrant origin in Europe. In segregated schools, the rate of pupils of migrant origin is often more than 80%, and the rates of poverty are elevated. Since forming part of a parents' association requires paying a fee and having disposable time, many of these segregated schools do not have organized parents' associations. One of the exemplary pioneers in schoolyard greening was thus a school that presented itself in a participatory budget program where part of the allocation of the municipal budget is put to a vote. This school benefitted from the professional expertise of parents, resulting in a strong parents' association and neighborhood mobilization, which enabled it to present a convincing project and garner enough votes - something that would have been nearly impossible for one of the segregated schools. While the municipal schoolyard greening project prioritized these segregated schools in its selection, the budget was much smaller in this case, meaning that schools still had to organize funding for new play structures to make use of the green spaces, which was again much more difficult for segregated schools without organized parents associations. Talking about the empowerment of niche innovators, therefore they needs to consider the material realities of the most marginalized school communities, which are concerned with basic needs such as housing and employment and face language barriers.

The organization carrying out the educational accompaniment for the schools selected for the schoolyard greening pilot can further be seen as another niche innovator. They are promoting innovative teaching practices in and with nature which most teachers did not have any experience with. However, their activities also go beyond the classroom and the schoolyard, with activities that bring the families in disadvantaged schools out to the green belt of the city, unknown to many of the participating families, and trainings not only for teachers but also cafeteria and maintenance staff. Their goal is thus to create awareness among the entire educational community about the importance of nature and about how to come into contact with nature. These sessions and trainings are very promising, since they help spread pedagogical innovations aimed at fostering nature-positivity and have brought children from urban disadvantaged backgrounds into contact with nature for the first time in some cases, which led to overcoming fears and revulsion the children had developed towards nature due to a lack of contact. The agency of this organization is being

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recognized, since it is contracted by the Education Department of Vitoria-Gasteiz. However, very little time is dedicated for these sessions and trainings. Learning in nature is new to most teachers in the schools that are part of the schoolyard greening project. While the educational department has already organized some workshops on the educational accompaniment to the green schoolyards, there is still a perceived lack of awareness of the importance of learning in nature among teachers. Longstanding teaching routines will furthermore be hard to break (interview with environmental education organization, 2024).

When it comes to **existing inclusive mechanisms where the niche innovators can have an impact, there is the school council on the city level**, which acts as a space to bring together institutional (technical staff) and political actors (city counsellors) and the educational community, e.g., representatives of teachers, parents, labor unions, and school headmasters. This space was created to put forward specific demands, de facto it does not have any decision-making power. However, it was through this space that the schoolyard greening idea was presented to the city hall. It is therefore an inclusive mechanism in theory for the niche innovators to present ideas. The non-institutional actors especially criticize the lack of meetings (it is supposed to meet twice a year, but due to municipal elections not even these few meetings have been carried out in practice, with the last meeting happening in 2021) and the little influence the municipal school council has in practice. However, the existence of this space already holds a lot of potential, so it could be strengthened in future.

1.3 Scalable Bottom-Up Innovations for Transformative Change

This case study of a municipal schoolyard greening pilot program responds to challenging aspects of the business-as-usual of two high impact sectors, the education and the urbanism sector. With business-as-usual we concretely refer to, first, the paradigm of classroom-based learning, standardized evaluations of children furthering inequalities resulting from intersectionalities and human-nature disconnection (Delaune, 2019), second, the marginalization of the public educational system and its resulting educational segregation (Diez-Gutiérrez and Palomo-Cermeño, 2023), and third, a focus on instrumental benefits of urban nature, exemplified by concepts dominating current urban planning paradigms, such as nature-based solutions, green infrastructures, or ecosystem services (Tozer et al., 2020). These broader paradigms impact also the standard design of public schoolyards, that so far have received little attention, especially in respect to gender- and nature-inclusive designs.

Figure 1. Renderings of a schoolyard transformation of the first schoolyard, 2022, shared with the educational communities and neighborhoods

Before diving into the existing innovations, it must be noted that this case study given its embeddedness into institutional structures of the public schooling system does not contain purely bottom-up or grassroots movements, as the implementation of innovations is only possible through support of specific institutional actors. That is, in this case study's initiatives pushed from the bottom-up are strongly interwoven with other top-down processes. Although the schoolyard greening program began before BIOTraCes—the first schoolyards were renaturalized in the 2012/2022 academic year—it is still too early for a full before-and-after analysis, as the impacts on biodiversity and human-nature relationships require longitudinal study. Research partners note emerging tendencies, but these remain anecdotal and need deeper investigation. Nevertheless, the program's governance has evolved over time through reflection and evaluation by involved actors, with observable learning leading to adaptations in its structure. The innovation now stands at a critical juncture, as the city hall has yet to decide whether to embed the program in the municipal annual budget after the pilot ends in 2026.

First and foremost, **the municipal schoolyard greening pilot program itself represents a biodiversity innovation. While not purely bottom-up, it emerged from grassroots mobilization by local educational actors in Vitoria-Gasteiz, who collectively signed a manifesto demanding improved public-school spaces.** This manifesto was subsequently taken up by local policymakers as a municipal pilot program for renaturalizing pre- and primary schoolyards. Innovation lies in the cross-departmental collaboration of institutional actors and, at least on paper, a participatory process with schools. It aims to challenge conventional paradigms through long-term goals of co-education, sustainability, and inclusivity. Concretely, schoolyards are envisioned as extensions of classrooms, enabling outdoor learning and creative play through gender-inclusive design. By prioritizing marginalized schools, the program seeks to address historical underfunding and educational segregation. Finally, care for nature and the school community has become an increasing focus, reflecting a gradual shift from instrumental to relational approaches and helping counter early childhood disconnection from and domination over nature.

Whether this innovation has transformative potential depends on its ability to overcome institutional barriers. Currently, the program still emphasizes technical knowledge and instrumental benefits of nature, and its top-down approach leaves room for greater participation by local educational communities in decision-making. A space for dialogue is needed to connect decision-makers with those most affected by the biodiversity innovation. BIOTraCes' workshops have served as connection spaces for educational community and institutional actors, allowing participants to share successes and challenges, and to identify concrete near- and medium-term goals through the lens of transformative potential. Specifically, the workshops brought together actors from the educational communities such as teachers, parents, representatives of the federation of parents' associations, school administrators and a janitor with institutional actors including city councilors, and members of the CEA and education department involved in designing and managing the project, as well as members of the organizations carrying out the educational accompaniment. Workshop 1, held in February 2025, served to establish common priorities for the future of the project between the participating stakeholders and identify successes and challenges that had emerged in the pilot phase. In workshop 2, held in April 2025, actions were co-created to overcome these challenges and ensure a more participatory future upscaling of the project.

In our case study, school-based innovations include garden projects, programs engaging children in schoolyard maintenance, and educational activities fostering human-nature relationships. Their potential for upscale is limited, as they often rely on motivated teachers, parents, or support from institutional actors. Yet these initiatives are crucial for transformative change. Green schoolyards provide opportunities for a relational approach to learning, connecting the school to its wider community and ecosystem. They center experiential, real-world interactions with nature and people, for example through

community service learning in the school garden. The transdisciplinary systems thinking and collaborative decision-making skills developed through such initiatives are precisely what education systems need to equip future generations to address complex problems like biodiversity loss. Actively involving pupils in project-based learning can empower them to apply knowledge for change and thus give agency to pupils instead of paralyzing them with despairing information about climate change and biodiversity loss (O'Brien et al. 2013) (van den Bogerd et al., 2025).

The current Spanish education law encourages these pedagogical innovations, and green schoolyards offer a space to apply them. What is still missing, however, is more training for teachers to become familiar with these new approaches and improving working conditions of teachers by e.g. reducing teacher-student ratios and bureaucratic accountability measures, since developing project-based learning experiences in nature requires more time and effort than simply following a textbook. Key actors for enabling this on the local school level are therefore education administrations at different governance levels, and also universities and their education programs that could offer more training in transformative teaching approaches in nature and labor unions in the education sector who are demanding improvements in labor conditions for teachers (Ó Riada et al., forthcoming).

In the context of the Vitoria-Gasteiz case study, the organization carrying out the educational accompaniment has provided some training sessions on learning in nature that can be seen as an important first step for promoting these pedagogical innovations. The early effects of these innovations have been an increase in interest in the potential of nature for learning and the engagement of children in nature, for example in harvesting fruit in the schoolyard. Further, initiatives such as the care program applied in some schools shift agency of care and stewardship over nature and the community towards the children. Children are thereby being empowered to take ownership over their schoolyard and to create emotional bonds with those spaces they experience daily. This Care Program specifically has the potential for upscale as it can be easily replicated in different educational communities.

Beyond the concrete case study, interview partners referred to the following bottom-up innovations with the potential of upscale and replication in other contexts:

One public school in Vitoria-Gasteiz implemented a thorough participatory design process with children to co-create the schoolyard, responding directly to their needs and wishes. This initiative was entirely driven by the local educational community, which applied for funding through the city's annual participatory budget campaign, where residents vote on community projects. After extensive campaigning and neighborhood support, the school won in 2022, enabling a long-term, child-centered participatory process that placed nature and play at the center. With a relatively large budget of €300,000, the school enjoyed considerable autonomy in project implementation, including flexibility beyond the criteria of the municipal greening program of only including nature-based elements. Today, this schoolyard serves as a local best-case example and inspiration for schools participating in the municipal pilot program. However, schools in the municipal pilot program receive smaller budgets, limiting the scale of their interventions and causing frustration in communities aspiring to similar changes. Access to this bottom-up innovation is also inequitable, as it relied heavily on an active parent association, making the implementation of a similar initiative in a marginalized school more unlikely.

In the Basque Country, alternative educational models such as Montessori and Escuelas Libres are also emerging. These schools emphasize experimental, embodied learning with closer contact to nature, challenging the dominant competitive, classroom-based, top-down teaching paradigm. Most operate as private cooperatives, relying on parental funding, which affects continuity and limits access for marginalized communities. If there are not enough pupils attending a year, some schools have to close down, which leads children to have to change their known learning environment While they represent niche

innovations demonstrating alternative educational approaches, broader societal impact and upscale potential depend on greater recognition and support from public institutions to ensure equitable access.

1.4 Initial Mapping of Interventions

The schoolyard greening process itself represents a departure from the standard approach of paved schoolyards. Bottom-up actions included parents' associations of specific schools bringing plants to schools, initiating schools' gardens, or fundraising for diagnostics and hiring architects draft plans for schoolyard transformations. Further, a cross-collaboration between different municipal schools consisted of launching campaigns that led to the manifesto for safe, healthy school environments. Participatory design efforts by the CEA engaged selected schools, though time constraints limited full participation.

As for now, there are still many uncertainties if the program will be prolonged for the next academic term. Following, a lot of strategies and/or interventions by institutional technical actors are aiming to call attention to and provide evidence of the importance of the program. They are applying a bricolage approach to funding as they are constantly looking for new and diverse funding sources and grants in order to be able to continue the program (field notes, meeting with societal partner). While this is not necessarily challenging current power structures, it is a strategy to navigate political dynamics to be able to achieve stability and continuity of the biodiversity innovation over the long run. This is critical to ensure equitable benefits for all public schools.

Ongoing evaluations include surveys and teacher feedback (regarding the pilot program and its impact on children's emotional state and conflicts), citizen science monitoring of biodiversity impact (focusing on birds and pollinators), and assessment of internal municipal department workflows and dynamics. The idea of these evaluations is to show policy-makers why schoolyard greening matters. The CEA aims to systematize evaluation metrics, including more precise metrics for the biodiversity and climate adaptation impact, the inclusive use of the schoolyard, and the use of new resources in classes. The city's Department of Education increasingly organizes conferences on schoolyards, co-education, sustainability, and inclusivity, inviting scholars, practitioners, and local decision-makers. These forums are a dedicated space of discussion, also with the goal to re-enforce the importance of the biodiversity innovation towards local policymakers.

Opening schoolyards after school hours to the broader neighbourhood, treating them as community spaces or urban parks is a goal, but is currently not happening in most cases, mainly due to open questions about who would be liable if any damaged, injuries, etc. occur in this time. In a workshop pathways were therefore explored to put this into practice, e.g. by establishing municipal regulations that provide guarantees to schools, as well as increasing maintenance resources (workshop 2, April 2025). Opening up schoolyards could raise awareness of their importance and increase social support for the biodiversity innovation. It also aligns with social demands formulated in the manifesto to shift the schoolyard from a purely school-based space to an integrated part of the wider neighbourhood, including safer streets and public access. While institutional actors aspire to replicate this in the municipal program, limited resources, safety concerns, vandalism, and shared administration across departments are other reasons brought forward as a for why it has not happened yet.

BIOTraCes acts as an intervention fostering biodiversity and human-nature relationships through one-on-one engagement and multi-actor workshops, creating a space to discuss reimagined human-nature relationships. Our perception is that this has helped to draw more attention and ultimately generate a space of reflection for justice and equity implication of schoolyard transformations and the role of biodiversity in it. Bringing these topics to a discussion between heterogeneous actors can be a first step towards an imaginary shift of human-nature relationships. Although there is a formal, institutional

space – the commission for schoolyard greening as part of the municipal school council –, that serves on paper as a discussion space regarding the issues of the schoolyard, communication between institutional and educational community actors remains limited. Shared spaces for dialogue are crucial to build trust, exchange perspectives, and adapt interventions to the specific needs of each school. As every educational community is different, there is also not a one-type-fits-all-approach to schoolyard greening.

BIOTraCes workshops have the potential to translate discussions into concrete actions. For example, during the workshops we discussed concrete and feasible actions, such as minimum standards for all public schoolyards in Vitoria-Gasteiz, to assure that all public schools can benefit (workshop 2, April 2025). Further activities under BIOTraCes are planned for 2026, to help translate these workshop outcomes into concrete to-dos for local policymakers. The CEA is further planning to continue some of the BIOTraCes activities beyond the project's end, including the co-creation of a roadmap for schoolyard greening together with diverse educational actors. In the best case, this can contribute through evidence to a prolongation and stabilization of the pilot into a continuous annual budget. It contributes to creating networks of actors engaged in advancing educational system towards co-education, inclusivity, and sustainability, and clearer formulation and communication of concrete goals and expectations of the different actors involved. Ultimately, BIOTraCes through its participatory action approach and its resulting deliverables and scientific outputs can give more weight to the importance of schoolyard greening.

1.5 Discussion

The municipal schoolyard greening program of Vitoria-Gasteiz can be described as a biodiversity innovation that responds to specific paradigms of both the educational and the urban planning sector. While its three long-term aims are framed holistically around co-education, inclusivity and sustainability, its current form of implementing small-scale greening elements and of limited participation of the educational communities does not allow for a holistic school remaking capable of overcoming structural barriers, such as educational segregation or rigid top-down governance approaches and narrow requirements. Given its institutionalized structure embedded in the public education sector, it draws on a mixture of bottom-up, pushed by the educational communities, and top-down processes, initiated by local institutional actors.

For the biodiversity innovation to be sustainable over the long term, the various processes need to be integrated through co-governance of urban schoolyards, supported by public administrations and institutional actors across scales. Local institutional actors should provide better support for those actions initiated by the educational communities and funded through their own resources, such as the implementation of schoolyard designs commissioned by schools. Furthermore, bottom-up involvement is essential for the innovation to realize its transformative potential, as active participation of educational community actors in its use and maintenance is key to generate long-lasting impact. This, however, opens up issues of justice and equity, as marginalized educational communities, e.g. those with a high number of foreign-born children, encounter many barriers hindering them from partaking in schoolyard transformations.

Bottom-up mobilizations in this case study stem from intrinsic motivation and the educational community's willingness to sustain biodiversity innovations over the long term as exemplified by the collective manifesto that initiated the innovation and communities that independently implemented school gardens or nature-based play equipment. However, their capacity to drive broader change is limited by the complex, fragmented administrative governance, which often hinders or only insufficiently supports these bottom-up initiatives. Further, more flexible requirements for schoolyard interventions would facilitate the implementation of schoolyard elements more aligned with educational

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communities' needs and wishes, such as the adding of outdoor furniture that would allow for outdoor teaching.

Throughout this research, many actors emphasized that the success of schoolyard greening often depends on at least one active individual—typically a parent or teacher—with parents' associations frequently acting as niche innovators. However, in the public education context, it is difficult to frame bottom-up movements as primary drivers of change, particularly given the structural inequalities in Spain's private-public educational system. The focus should instead be on institutional actors and how they can support—not merely empower—bottom-up initiatives. This involves shifting decision-making power to local educational communities, especially marginalized ones, allowing them to implement small-scale initiatives with minimal bureaucracy. Importantly, this includes giving children agency by moving from an adult-centric approach to one that recognizes them as political actors in shaping their schoolyards.

Following, emphasis should also be placed on niche innovators driving change from within institutions. From the outside, these actions may not seem radical or transformative but introducing incremental concepts into democratic institutions can embed transformation in systemic structures, gradually challenging the status quo and bringing new visions into public discourse. A key unresolved question is how to enhance the capacity for transformative change among marginalized educational communities. How can they be supported without shifting responsibility onto them? What concrete actions can institutions take to assist schools lacking strong parent associations or engaged teachers?

Five years after the launch of the municipal schoolyard greening program, it remains too early to assess its impact on equity at a broader governance level. Attention to vulnerable and marginalized communities is increasing, but it is unclear whether public funding allocations are addressing structural injustices, such as educational segregation. Given the deep marginalization of some schools, limited, one-time funding is unlikely to overcome entrenched structural barriers.

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D2.2

Herders' knowledge for biodiversity

CER, Hungary

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Summary

Summary of Deliverable

The Hungarian BIOTraCes team works closely with traditional herders, whose knowledge and practices are essential for maintaining Hungary's grasslands. Of the country's one million hectares of grassland, around half a million require grazing to preserve their exceptional ecological value. These ancient, species-rich habitats depend on extensive, well-timed, and skilfully managed grazing—something only experienced herders can provide. Yet the number of herders is rapidly declining, not because their work is obsolete, but because society and key sectors such as conservation and agriculture overlook their indispensability. As socio-ecological and economic pressures intensify, herders must continuously adapt, drawing on both inherited and newly developed knowledge. The project therefore explores how tradition-based innovations can support pastoral communities and strengthen their role in biodiversity conservation.

The case study aims to identify pathways for revitalizing pastoralism, shifting societal perceptions of herders, and improving the regulatory and support systems shaping their work. Pastoralism is an ancient, adaptive profession, but recent policy and administrative changes—often intended as support—have made it more difficult to practice. Today, herders' contributions remain undervalued, even though their management of livestock and pastures sustains biodiversity and produces high-quality foods derived from plants inedible to humans. Proper grazing is one of the few agricultural activities that enhances biodiversity rather than undermining it. In a context of accelerating climate change, the adaptability of pastoralism and the depth of traditional ecological knowledge make it vital for Hungary's future.

The research spans the entire country, documenting herders' knowledge, connecting communities across regions, and encouraging forms of self-organisation that strengthen their collective voice. This is the first national effort to foster broad professional cooperation among herders, at a moment when pastoralism faces existential threats. Working with an internally diverse and historically marginalized group raises important ethical considerations: researchers must build trust, respect cultural boundaries, and acknowledge the social isolation many herders experience. Particular attention is given to supporting older herders, encouraging young people to enter the profession, and working with the recently established Hungarian Women Herders Group.

The team has organized "Forum of Hungarian Herders" meetings to facilitate dialogue with policymakers and other stakeholders, sparking new ideas and helping clarify long-standing challenges. International exchanges have further broadened herders' perspectives and stimulated technological and organisational innovation. Emerging examples suggest that meaningful transformation is possible but preserving traditional ecological knowledge and enabling its evolution to require long-term support.

In sum, herders today face not only ecological change but also shifting regulations, social expectations, and economic pressures. Safeguarding biodiversity and food security in Hungary depends on strengthening pastoralism. Supporting a new generation of "conservation herders" is therefore central to the transformative aims of this project.

Transformative biodiversity innovations (D2.2)

1.1 Analysis of Inclusion/Exclusion Mechanisms

In Hungary, the maintenance and support of grazing livestock would greatly benefit not only ecological and livestock interests, but also food security. Yet a fundamental problem in society is that ordinary people and decision-makers do not take into account or even perceive the potential economic power of local communities in extensive livestock production. In fact, society as a whole has moved away from traditional forms of ecological knowledge as a result of technological advances and considers them outdated and unnecessary. As a consequence, there is no real demand from society for the transfer and maintenance of this knowledge - which in many ways would be in the interest of the community and humanity. Of course, in this case we are not only talking about knowledge, but also about a number of traditional ways of life, of which herding is only one element. Moreover, herders, due to their unique cultural background, also do not pass on their knowledge to others, or do so with greater difficulty. As the number of herders has been drastically reduced, those entering the profession are increasingly likely to be people who are learning from outside. However, the cultural resistance previously expressed by herders towards them persists, making the transmission of knowledge even more difficult. Inevitably, those who start out in extensive livestock production without a herder to guide them are part of the process. In some cases, these people carry out their activities with experience from other cultural contexts, sometimes from other nations, even with extensive marketing activities. This process poses a huge threat to traditional herding, as their own cultural existence and local practical experience, refined over hundreds of years, are being suppressed. In addition, if their views were taken into account by decision-makers or forums on certain issues, herders would not be the ones who would be heard in biodiversity debates and decision-making processes.

The problem is twofold. On the one hand, the internal characteristics of herders' societies have so far not allowed for the effective transmission of knowledge, or even for its growth and addition. Herders' self-organisation and advocacy is extremely low. Although there are some small positive examples and results, in general they have almost no influence on the decision-making processes that affect them. Moreover, individual herders have in the past been portrayed by the various media as mere curiosities, preserving the past rather than sharing their professional knowledge and experience. On the other hand, apart from the traditional externalities (e.g. the appearance of costumes and tools at festivals), society does not feel and understand the need to preserve the traditional ecological knowledge of herders. In many cases, even middle managers working in the extensive livestock sector do not have the knowledge to manage and work with animals more efficiently and with less harm to livestock and people. As a result, they have no realistic view of the professional skills of the herders and the potential results of their work. The overall result of the process outlined is that herders, to the extent that they are aware of them, have neither social nor economic appreciation. As technology advances in animal husbandry, the human presence is being minimised, thus contributing to the gradual disappearance of the herding profession and knowledge.

Efforts to halt and reverse this process have been and are being made at various levels. In this case, it is again worth taking a closer look at the internal reactions of herders and the processes taking place in society and economically.

Herders - and here it is worth highlighting some of the herders who were born into the pastoral system - are slowly realising the need to pass on their knowledge. Although it has been an extremely slow process for historical reasons due to cultural difficulties, they have clearly started to learn and practice how to welcome and teach young herders from outside the profession. Their advocacy is not expected to develop from internal impulses for a long time, but the need for change has already been expressed. In this respect, our experience is that women in pastoralism are much more effective self-organisers than men. The Hungarian Women herders' group (3.;7.), which was set up a few years ago, is a testimony

to this, following the Spanish example. It is of particular importance for the future advocacy body to be able to represent the whole herding community of the country, all its regions and all its participants from different backgrounds. The series of Forum of Hungarian Herders (2.;4.) launched under the BIOTraCes project will greatly contribute to the formation of a common opinion and professional image of the Hungarian herding community. During our field participatory research, we also try to facilitate this by building personal contacts between herders, even between distant regions. Based on our results so far, we have reached the next stage: if we researchers are asked to formulate opinions, give presentations or even consult with decision-makers (we are sometimes asked to do so), we inform the herders in advance and hold consultations to gather as many opinions as possible. In addition, we try to bring herders with us personally to each of these occasions, so that they can take part in the discussions, represent their interests and influence the processes around them. Of course, this is also a slow learning process for herders (and for ourselves). As the number and intensity of connections increases, communication between herders and stakeholders and decision-makers with different interests becomes more frequent. Herders are no longer thinking solely on their own behalf but have begun to think on the scale of a national herding community. This way of thinking could prove very useful in the future, if they are indeed the first to succeed in setting up their own advocacy organisation. (1.;7.)

That said, you don't necessarily have to think in terms of a single organisation, a single lobby. Learning from the example of the Women herders' group (3.;7), it is worthwhile to help the emergence of several representative groups, organised by territory, age and other principles, each with different needs and difficulties. It may also be useful to have separate representation for each group, in order to avoid the possibility of repeated marginalisation within the herders' community, which could easily occur for cultural reasons.

We need to approach the processes in society in a completely different way than we approach pastoral communities. Different issues and realities can be brought to the attention of different stakeholders and social groups with different agendas. At the same time, all stakeholders and decision-makers have one thing in common: as private individuals, they all use social media. Since pastoralism is not explicitly involved in any form of policy formulation or other formal organisational initiatives, it is through social media channels that attention can be directed towards them by providing professionally and humanly relevant content. This is obviously not only possible through trade magazines and professional websites, but even more so through platforms that are frequently used by the public (e.g. YouTube). These are the tools that can be used to inform the wider society and, in some cases, to encourage a response from professional decision-makers and conservation and other stakeholders working with herders.

It would be inappropriate to establish the involvement of herders in policy-making by requiring them to directly perform tasks in designated organisations. At present, while we are trying to introduce and involve pastoralists in person, we are clearly distracting them from their day-to-day work. There is therefore a need to develop professional representation directly involving the herders, but there is a lack of a hybrid intermediary or organisation that can play its role in a professional and ethical manner in the policy-making sub-processes. Therefore, it is not only the development and adaptation of the herders that is needed, but the development of a team with a new approach and hybrid knowledge may be the most appropriate solution.

If the right policy decisions are taken in the future, it is equally important to educate and retrain professionals from conservation and other organisations. This could include, on the one hand, basic information on herding, so that other stakeholders understand the needs and situation of herders. On the other hand, priority should be given to initiating appropriate communication between all stakeholders and all levels of stakeholders.

Currently, there are conservation rangers working in several National Park Directorates who are willing and able to consult and work together with herders. In some cases, this

means that they seek solutions, half-solutions and unofficially authorised options that are beneficial for the work of the herders and for biodiversity, by understanding their tasks and their situation. Unfortunately, in these cases, the situation can easily change due to employer policies or even staff changes in the National Park Directorates. Thus, the park rangers in charge can provide very useful ad hoc assistance to the herders, but in the long term this unstable situation can easily change. In the long term, it is essential to set as a long-term objective not only the restructuring of regulatory and support systems, but also the proper education and information, including training of professionals who come into contact with herders, in higher education on the necessary subjects. (2.;4.)

As there are currently only bottom-up initiatives to involve different voices in policy and initiative support, we have very limited room for manoeuvre in terms of the instruments that can be used. In the future, we need to keep a constant eye on emerging opportunities. At the moment, the most rational experience is that independent researchers and experts are best placed to take up the issues of herding, grassland biodiversity and water management with their own unique solutions. As the public sector cannot be relied on to provide a stable basis for the foreseeable future, we can make our voice heard more effectively through forums organised by others and ourselves, agricultural exhibitions, media platforms that are relevant to the profession and the subject, or through professional communities with a broad (professional or general) audience.

1.2 Niche Innovators and Key Players

We started working with some of the Niche Innovators and Key Players in our case study years ago, while others have already been brought on board through the BIOTraCes project.

First, we can name the researchers and our own research team. Our research group has a kind of social networking asset that makes it easier for us to reach e.g. media coverage, middle and sometimes top management decision-makers, various task forces and persons in nature conservation and other professional bodies, etc. These assets were previously unavailable to the main actors in our case study, for the herders. On the other hand, however, over decades of working together, a working relationship - and in many cases a friendly relationship - has developed with the majority of herders, which has gradually made it possible to map their society and their situation, to bring their opinions together and to channel them towards the achievement of objectives. At the same time, it is of key importance to us that we do not want to publish opinions/evidence based on scientific results ourselves. Partnership with herders, according to cultural and other ethical and scientific norms, requires that we are fully equal partners in the process of setting goals and finding ways and methods to achieve them. In fact, our research team is trying to play a mediating role in several contexts. Internally, first of all, by reconciling and translating cultural differences between herders, by refining attitudes that are a source of difficulty, we are slowly succeeding in building a national network of friendships and professional relationships between herders and communities that can work together more and more effectively. By integrating them as an external element into herding society in a unique way, we can also suggest to them ways of thinking about and applying methods, both theoretical and practical, which they are then willing not only to consider but, if our suggestions and ideas are correct, to apply and disseminate among themselves. At this point, we can say that the herders generally acknowledge the involvement of our research team in their cause. In fact, it is more than that. Beyond acknowledgement, they are looking directly for opportunities to ask us for help or for what they believe they can help us with. Our achievements and results are beginning to strengthen the identity, voice and will of the community, as well as their sense of the practical importance of their profession. It also, in some cases, provides herders with opportunities (socially or personally) that they would find unimaginable without working with us. The practices that we propose, and embrace are seen by both herders and researchers as having the potential to make a

significant positive difference to improving the biodiversity status of grasslands. We ourselves seek to complement, rather than supplant, the traditional ecological knowledge of herders with the useful social, economic and professional practices of the present day, which are slowly being not only adopted but increasingly demanded by herders. We also seek to play a mediating role between different stakeholders and decision-makers in the implementation of biodiversity restoration measures. By synthesising the widely consulted expert opinions of herders (and other stakeholders), we aim to come up with proposals that are appropriate to the current context and system, for the benefit of herders, on practical and regulatory issues, both locally and nationally. Knowledge-sharing initiatives are multi-disciplinary in nature and target groups, but our work has also led to the development of reliable channels of communication within and between stakeholder groups.

The second important group of Niche Innovators and Key Players is the international research community. On several occasions, the BIOTraCes project has held face-to-face meetings and international conferences where Hungarian herders have exchanged ideas with foreign researchers working with herders. This process is very positive, as Hungarian herders can learn about foreign practices and international examples in a safe environment. The ideas gathered in this way are adapted by the herders to their own circumstances and are used in all areas of pastoralism. Natural-ecological conditions have shaped different methods of herding even within Hungary, not to mention the diversity of other countries in Europe. For this reason, practical examples from abroad, for cultural or practical reasons, or because of differences in the herding conditions, often provide Hungarian herders with more theoretical guidance. What they can use more effectively are issues related to the social and economic environment, regulations and support (e.g. building advocacy, social engagement, knowledge transfer/education, land relations, market opportunities and conditions, employer and employee conditions, etc.). In addition, building international relations has several messages for Hungarian herders: a confirmation that not only in Hungary there is still pastoralism, but that there are still herders living and working in almost every part of the world whose work and knowledge is needed by humanity. Pastoralism in many countries has already started long before to exchange experiences and best practices at international level, from which both useful knowledge and strength can be drawn. In addition, for the first time in the history of Hungarian pastoralism, we have reached the point where herders themselves are beginning to develop medium and long-term relationships in international arenas. Through these contacts, they can meet not only researchers, but also herders of other nationalities during personal visits abroad, with whom they can sometimes exchange theoretical and field knowledge. The participation of herders in international conferences, both at home and abroad - which we coordinate - is a powerful support to this process. Here too, of course, particular attention must be paid to research ethics! On our part, we need to be careful about the situation we create for the participants to meet, and we are the assurance to the Hungarian herders that we are seeking to establish meaningful professional relationships for them. When engaging foreign researchers, we also apply the principle that we seek to involve colleagues with due caution and ethics in our joint work. In the longer term, joint work with foreign researchers and herders could even lead to the possibility of adapting international regulations and support schemes in the future.

Since a very large part of the grasslands grazed by herders are protected areas, members of the conservation rangers managed by the National Park Directorates have an important role to play in our case study. We are working with a number of conservation rangers who see and understand the practical benefits of pastoral grazing for biodiversity. Unfortunately, this is not a common perception among public conservationists, so the number of conservation rangers who seek to work with herders is not high. In addition, there is a general mentality in public conservation that conservation regulations are to be respected at all costs, even at the expense of nature. For a long time, there were serious conflicts between conservationists and herders. Today, there are dedicated professionals who are on good terms with herders and are flexible enough to help them to thrive in the

area of conservation regulations and their practical implementation. As these relations have long been hostile, building trust between the parties is key to the future of herders and biodiversity. The conservationists who attend our meetings and successfully engage with stakeholders have a great influence on herders. Having experienced positive examples, they often maintain professional contacts and are themselves more courageous in taking initiatives towards the conservation rangers in their area. The number of rangers who have successfully communicated is not yet high, but their constructive example is extremely helpful. Thanks to them, many common conservation interests can be pursued in the field work of the herders. After receiving correct and professional information, herders typically seek solutions that benefit both conservationists and their environment. This not only results in successful conservation management. Herders, who in many cases have a tenancy in a protected national park area, are also in a more secure position, as national park authorities can treat them as partners in the long term, in the hope of continued successful cooperation. On the other hand, herders, in their own interest, are increasingly open to coordinating their own knowledge and methods with conservationists, who can better understand the needs of herders and the necessity of their activities. The conservationists in question must exercise the utmost discretion towards herders and livestock farmers, of course, otherwise this nascent but fragile relationship could easily be destroyed. However, the contribution and involvement of the trusted rangers is fully recognised and supported by the herders. There are opportunities for us to successfully develop this relationship further. The Forum of Hungarian Herders (2.;4.) we organise and other meetings we attend provide excellent opportunities for this.

The main Niche Innovators and Key Players are of course the herders themselves. Our work with herders started long before the BIOTraCes project was launched. This gave us the advantage of being able to think beyond the four-year project. The involvement of the herders was very slow and step-like. Getting to know and working with each herder was done individually. In the process of developing good professional and not infrequently friendly relationships, we were often directed to other herder friends. In this way, we were able to get to know their communities and their people in a significant coverage. Although we initially sought to involve them in certain roles, this has now become a reciprocal back and forth in many cases. In effect, the herders involved us in their world in a similar way.

Working with us, they have made significant progress in a number of areas. This applies to the individuals and communities involved. The most important of these is the recognition that Hungarian herders face entirely new challenges and that the survival of their profession depends on their own adaptation. The process, though slow, has reached a tipping point. Even among those herders who were born into the profession, more and more of them believe that their knowledge should not be kept as a secret but must be passed on to interested young people. Although the issue of replacement raises very serious concerns, pastoralism has one major advantage over other agricultural sectors: it is the easiest to adapt to changing natural conditions. However, they have reached a stage where it is not only possible, but in some cases even advisable, to incorporate into traditional methods elements of new technologies, breeds and practices that they can benefit from. (2.;4.;5.) Our community-building activities also help herders who have come to identify problems to effectively share their opinions and experiences with other members of the community. Herding communities in landscapes with different characteristics, and other communities based on age, gender, animal breeds and technologies, are also undergoing increased transformation and development. This is partly because some of these groups did not exist a few years ago. Examples include the Women herders group, active herders participating in the Forum of Hungarian Herders (2.;4.), the emerging Young Pastoralists group, etc. The engagement of particular herders and communities is handled differently by different stakeholders and interest groups. As there is as yet no officially registered representative body, their views are typically received with mixed perceptions by the profession. In many cases, the civil sector is almost enthusiastic about the herders' manifestations, but at the same time they are not able to deal with them from a livelihood perspective. In most cases they are seen as traditionalists, not as agricultural actors with

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potential. In terms of the use and consumption of the food and raw materials of animal origin produced by herders, the civil sector could support them with its purchasing power, but the achievements of our modern world have in many cases driven them out of the market for economic or cultural reasons.

The results of the work between herders and researchers are difficult to present in that the most noticeable changes are taking place in the development of the herders' personalities and professional skills. We are increasingly successful in opening up the herders' society to the world. They are discovering and developing new social interactions, economic methods, and networks that would have been unimaginable 10-15 years ago given their cultural and social background. In fact, the basic conditions have been created for the potentially emerging new generation of the pastoral society to take advantage of the benefits offered by science, technology, and society more freely. What is more, the currently active generations of herders are also contributing to this process, are learning themselves and, in some cases, trying to pass on their knowledge to young people.

1.3 Scalable Bottom-Up Innovations for Transformative Change

Extensive livestock farming in Hungary is being significantly reduced by intensive technologies and breeds, which often require less labour and, in some respects, less expertise. Moreover, even in this sector there are already problems with a lack of reliable labour. A further negative factor is that intensive farming methods have become an unsustainable form of farming for mankind in the long term, under today's drastically extreme and changing ecological conditions, with enormous environmental pressures and ecological damage. At the same time, animal products can be fully produced by extensive grazing livestock farming, which would be extremely beneficial to our natural environment and biodiversity. But this requires special knowledge and special people: herders. Today's modern society is unaware of the value that herders can produce meat, milk, dairy products and other goods from grasses that cannot be eaten by humans. In addition to changes in the natural environment, herders are increasingly influenced by various local and international regulations in the fields of nature conservation, agriculture, animal welfare, animal husbandry, commercial activities, etc. In addition, they are marginalised by society in many ways. Policies do not take into account the real needs of the sector and pastoralism in particular is not taken into account.

In our country, there are more than half a million hectares of grassland that require traditional pastoral grazing to survive. In many cases, these are protected grasslands of high natural value, with outstanding biodiversity value also. The preservation of these areas is in the common interest of humanity. According to experts in all aspects of conservation and ecology, extensive grazing by Hungarian herders is now essential for maintaining grassland ecosystems and biodiversity. Through grazing, treading and dunging, livestock influence the vegetation and micro-cover of grasslands and, through this, their rich fauna and natural processes. The grazing of extensively grazed livestock requires appropriate temporal (year, month, day, period of the day) and territorial distribution and planning, depending on the weather, according to what the herders believe is needed to maintain healthy grasslands. Maintaining a healthy grassland - and thus biodiversity - is an elementary goal for herders, as it enables them to sustain and increase the livestock that provide their livelihoods. This is why the saying is common among herders around the world: "the herder sees the pasture through the mouth of the livestock". Accordingly, herders have been fighting for centuries to ensure the survival and health of grasslands and thus biodiversity.

The innovations that have been or are being launched from the bottom up for biodiversity include:

Herder schools

International relations and the organisation of the International Year of Grasslands and Pastoralists in 2026, it was discovered that many countries across Europe have herding schools with a long history. Spanish and French schools are the most numerous, but there are also schools, seminars and small courses in Italy and other countries. Many aspects of this are of interest to us, as saving the knowledge of Hungarian herders and setting a new generation on a successful career path is an increasingly urgent key issue for the future of pastoralism. Our long-term plans include the establishment of a herder school in Hungary. Although this will most likely be beyond the timeframe of the BIOTraCes project, we can lay the foundations within this framework.

In Hungary, pastoralism is dwindling partly because of the cultural and professional isolation of its own society. On the other hand, young people are unaware of the profession and the opportunities it offers and are not aware of its conditions and do not see it as a realistic livelihood. Although there were courses in sheep farming and extensive livestock farming and breeding in the second half of the last century, these had disappeared by the turn of the millennium. In our opinion, even if a herding school were to be set up in Hungary at this time, the expected number of students and the employment rate of graduates in the profession are highly doubtful. Therefore, we need to look not only at the theoretical and practical knowledge system of the schools and the way in which it is transmitted, but also at the background to the establishment and maintenance of the schools and their social and professional environment. In this context, theoretical research and information collection have been and are being carried out. Furthermore, we are organising personal contacts so that Hungarian herders and hopefully later on the maintainers and teachers of the Hungarian herder school can meet and exchange experiences with the expatriates first hand.

This innovation cannot be considered traditional, because the traditional herder society has always had strong reservations about people entering the profession from outside over the centuries. Moreover, at no time in our history has there been such a shortage that separate institutions are needed to replace the livestock breeders and herders. By supporting the creation of an institution, herders are therefore initiating innovation within their own society. No significant external support for these purposes has been received so far, but some proposals have been put forward to some policy actors and to the heads of some agricultural training institutions. A realistic plan can be drawn up if we plan to carry out a personal visit to the Spanish herder schools. We must pay particular attention to the following issues:

- ✓ Why does Spanish society consider it necessary to maintain these schools? Was there a social need in the first place, or did it have to be created? If so, how was it achieved?
- ✓ What were the social, economic and environmental processes that led to the creation of these schools?
- ✓ Who founded and maintained the schools and from what resources?
- ✓ What is needed to run the schools (space, technologies, materials, resources, livestock for practical education, etc.)?
- ✓ Who, how and what is taught?
- ✓ What are the key aspects that society recognises as necessary and successful for schools to operate?

The establishment of a herders' school in Hungary would in many ways help the long-term cause of conservation and restoration of herders and biodiversity. On the one hand, the establishment and maintenance of the institution and the creation of employment conditions will involve both governmental and professional executive bodies, which in turn will make the presence of herders a clear signal and a fact for society and decision-makers. Accordingly, the advocacy of herders and the recognition and informed use of their

traditional ecological knowledge in biodiversity restoration work may become increasingly important in policy-making. (4)

Knowledge library/archive

within the framework of the BIOTraCes project, an extensive collection of traditional ecological knowledge of Hungarian herders and the physical and intellectual background of working with pastoral livestock, as well as their innovations, has been launched. The knowledge is being recorded through video, photographs and audio recordings. In addition, we try to experience them in their physical reality, as this is how the knowledge and procedures needed to work with livestock can be truly understood. Of course, the herders themselves prefer to share their knowledge with others who are willing to actively help them in their work. The material collected and to be collected is extremely varied. On the one hand, the tasks to be carried out around the livestock, and on the other hand, we collect and record information about the herders themselves. The material is handled in several ways. Some materials have already been published - for example on the Wall of Hungarian Herders in the Herders' Museum on Hortobágy. Other material, however, contains information that is sensitive from a personal, regulatory or other point of view (animal health regulations, conservation and agriculture, animal husbandry regulations, animal welfare, personal information, etc.) that would be unethical and inappropriate to share from the herders' point of view. Making much of this material public would have serious negative consequences for the individual herders and their farms. The simple reason for this is that our current society's perception and regulatory system, which is extremely detached from nature and elements of traditional agriculture, does not know why particular traditional practices are necessary and beneficial to animals, humans and ecosystems alike. In some cases, sharing of materials is not even recommended among herders for cultural reasons. Therefore, we are still looking for appropriate solutions for the use of sensitive materials in the future. What is certain is that, although the society and the regulatory environment of our time do not explicitly seek to preserve or support the survival of traditional pastoral knowledge - in some cases, they actually discourage it - we are working for the future. Changes in the regulatory environment and the anticipated future pressures of ecological change could easily create an increased demand for herders' knowledge. So, in fact, whatever happens to the herders who are still actively working today, we will always have at our disposal the extensive material collected on the traditional ecological knowledge of Hungarian herders and the practical use of modern developments and combinations of traditional elements. (4)

Advocacy, community groups

Our case study is about a group that is marginalised in many ways. Within the Hungarian herders' community nationally, there have been small traditional communities since time immemorial and within them further marginalisation can be observed. These are mainly related to age and occupational ranking. In our work, particular attention is paid to active herders, young herders and women in pastoralism. Their representation is not expected to take place for a long time because of internal motivation, but the need for change has already been expressed. In this respect, our finding is that women herders are much more effective self-organisers than men. The Women herders group in Hungary, which was set up a few years ago, is a testimony to this, following the Spanish example. It is of particular importance for the future representative body to be able to represent the whole pastoral community of the country, all its regions and all its participants from different backgrounds. The series of the Forum of Hungarian Herders (2.;4.) launched under the BIOTraCes project will greatly contribute to the formation of a common opinion and professional image of the Hungarian herding community. During our field participatory research, we also try to facilitate this by building personal contacts between herders, even between distant regions. Learning from the example of the Women herders group, it is worthwhile to help

the emergence of several groupings, organised by territory, age and other principles, each with different needs and difficulties. It may also be useful to have a separate representation for each group, in order to avoid the possibility of repeated marginalisation within the herders' community, which could easily occur for cultural reasons. The socio-economic-political background and process of setting up interest representation bodies should also be observed from existing practices abroad, mainly in Spain and France. (4)

1.4 Initial Mapping of Interventions

On the one hand, our methods - which differ from the usual policies - are extremely limited, and on the other hand, they typically do not affect any central regulations but rather help to resolve local problems or minor infrastructure and communication errors or barriers through bottom-up initiatives. In order to halt the decline in biodiversity, we must help preserve both the herders themselves and their traditional ecological knowledge. At the same time, we cannot rely entirely on practices that have proven successful in previous decades and centuries, as our rapidly changing ecological, natural, and human environment requires completely different methods and survival strategies. That is why we must consider the innovation of traditional ecological knowledge and its coordination with other scientific disciplines as a goal.

The interventions and experiments used in our case study can be divided into two groups in terms of their direct impact on biodiversity conservation and restoration (e.g., recording the traditional ecological knowledge and methods of herders and transferring this knowledge directly influences the results of land management), or have indirect positive effects (e.g., changes in the regulatory environment, social processes and attitudes, and economic and employment conditions make it easier for the pastoralist community to manage and survive). The two options differ in that one focuses on maintaining activities aimed at preserving biodiversity, while the other focuses on the survival of those who possess the knowledge and practices necessary for biodiversity conservation, i.e., herders and livestock farmers.

A fundamental principle in the implementation of our case study is that we must make significant use of the traditional ecological knowledge of local communities when developing the local regulatory environment. At present, this is not being implemented at any level or in any area in the agriculture and nature conservation sectors or in physical work. This is a highly unconventional approach, which even the research community must learn through joint work with herders and other local stakeholder communities. The resulting knowledge, communication opportunities, and practical solutions can greatly contribute to positively influencing the biodiversity of the areas managed and affected by herders in our case study. At the same time, the prospects for regulatory changes in the near future are not at all positive. The slow bureaucratic system is unable to respond to the needs and demands arising from ecological and climatic changes. Therefore, we must apply methods that enable us to create knowledge, record it, and maintain it among stakeholders in its functional (physical and intellectual) environment, and develop innovative methods together with stakeholders and other social partners. This leads to another extremely important method used in our case study, which differs significantly from general practices: strengthening local communities by stimulating their internal self-organization through external interventions. We are trying to initiate a self-generating process in which external interventions (such as our empowering activities, community and network building), the personal knowledge expansion and involvement of stakeholders (primarily herders) in issues and processes that affect them will create the need and opportunity for local herders and their families with traditional ecological knowledge to form a national advocacy group and express their professional opinions on social and economic issues that strongly affect them, as well as on the regulatory environment for nature conservation. At the same time, within the current political and infrastructural system, community expression does not represent a real and authoritative means of

influencing processes. Accordingly, our goal is to create community group(s) that are uniquely built from the bottom up and can be integrated in some form into the political and economic infrastructure. We believe that this will ensure the development of restraining effects and supportive practices that take biodiversity interests into account. (2.;4.)

When it comes to evaluating methods and results, our task is difficult because our work within the BIOTraCes project is only part of our temporal and geographical activities. Our research group began working with shepherds long before the project started. Establishing effective communication with them, the cultural environment, and the nationwide coverage of our tasks imposes temporal and spatial constraints on our work that make it impossible to achieve our goals within a four-year project. In addition, the drastically and extremely rapidly changing conditions in agriculture – and especially in animal husbandry – require us to constantly rethink and innovate. We must constantly review not only the main topic of our case study, but also innovations and opportunities related to our own work processes and methods. Therefore, in many areas of our case study, we cannot report on long-term successes, as unpredictable elements and factors can arise at any time during our work (a good example of this is the emergence of the foot-and-mouth disease virus in the spring of 2025 after 50 years, which fortunately has since been contained in the country).

The methods listed earlier can be considered groundbreaking solutions in every respect, as previously no one in the research community, decision-making circles, or economic environment had represented Hungarian herding on a scientific and economic basis, nor had there been any realistic attempts to do so. (In a cultural sense, numerous efforts have already been made in this regard, but despite their significant value preservation work and other achievements, these attempts have largely contributed to the current outdated and traditionalist view of herding, and subsequently to a sharp decline in its financial and professional standing.) Since our methodology had never been used to approach herders before, we are witnessing a slow but completely unique process – one that naturally comes with enormous professional and ethical responsibility. Traditional research approaches and previous common practices have therefore been completely replaced or transformed in our work. Obviously, our own research methods were the first to be renewed. Subsequently, with the change in the environment and attitude of stakeholders, the development of common methods and goals could begin, which over time also included numerous social, cultural, scientific, and economic practical innovations. So our most notable achievement is that the Hungarian pastoral community we researched entered into a partnership with the research community we represent in various theoretical and practical ways. We are currently working on spreading this as widely as possible, not only in the broadest possible research environment, but also with the aim of further developing and extending the partnership to economic and decision-making actors. At the same time, this is an extremely slow and complex social and cultural process, which left to its own devices would halt the spread of partnerships. Therefore, in order to preserve and restore biodiversity, in some respects it is not the development of scientific results that we consider to be effective, but rather the initiation and implementation of social processes. These processes are expected to play a positive role in maintaining biodiversity in the future, but none of our activities can be considered an exclusive solution. Assessing ecological processes and exploring possible interventions is equally important as identifying the effects of social processes. (1)

1.5 Discussion

In the Hungarian case study, we strive to ensure the continuity of traditional ecological knowledge, which is essential for the preservation of biodiversity, to help adapt traditional ecological knowledge to innovative solutions, and to contribute to the adaptation of social groups that possess, maintain, and practice traditional ecological knowledge (Hungarian herders and livestock farmers) to today's challenges. In fact, we have previously described the adaptation process that pastoralism has undergone over hundreds or even thousands

of years, but today it has become much more difficult in the drastically changing ecological and human environment of the last 150 years, in all its aspects. The next step in the evolution of Hungarian pastoralism can be interpreted both as a struggle for the survival of their own society and knowledge, and as a struggle to save our natural environment and biodiversity.

As a result of this approach, traditional knowledge and innovative practices are constantly being collected, which will be essential for the survival of Hungarian herding and the maintenance of pastures and livestock. At the same time, the practical reinterpretation and real use of this knowledge will not be realized in the present, but in the future. As the world of herders is shrinking in many ways (declining and degrading pastures; declining number of livestock; declining number of herders; cultural loss/cultural transformation; negative changes in employment and occupational-economic conditions), the maintenance of the current form of herding cannot be guaranteed. It is conceivable that, as in many other countries around the world, a shock effect will be needed in human society (and especially in Hungary!) for the role of pastoralism in food production and ecological processes to be highly valued. We have seen similar examples internationally for many years, in global scale. Hungarian pastoralism is an extremely important element of the culture of the Carpathian Basin. Although our goal is to continuously maintain the pastoral society, the social behaviour that has developed over many centuries has unfortunately threatened the long-term survival of their communities in the 21st century. Considering the laws of evolution, it cannot be foreseen that the centuries-old cultural and social system of Hungarian pastoralism will disappear completely, or not. In this regard, our own research work must focus on preserving values and collecting the widest possible range of traditional ecological knowledge, data and technological skills. This will provide the basis for a partial re-learning of the science of herding in the future. Herders – and here it is worth highlighting certain herders who were born into the profession – are slowly recognizing the need to pass on their knowledge. Although this is a very slow process due to historical reasons and cultural difficulties, they have clearly begun to learn and practice accepting and teaching young herders who come from outside the profession. It is unlikely that they will develop their own advocacy group for a long time to come, but they have already expressed a desire for change.

Society, or parts of it, are capable of responding appropriately or inappropriately to ecological problems. However, we cannot leave these responses to random decision-making. Accordingly, comprehensive knowledge transfer and communication between sectors and social groups is necessary, from which innovative solutions can emerge. In practice, we cannot expect results based on the experiences and practices of the last century when it comes to preserving biodiversity. According to our scientific understanding, we have never occurred conditions of nowadays in the Carpathian Basin since human memory began. We must respond to environmental changes that we have never had to adapt to before. Accordingly, current and future practices affecting biological diversity and ecological processes must rely on a variety of methodologies: the traditional ecological knowledge of local communities, the experiences of other countries in similar circumstances and processes, the international scientific solutions, and completely new innovations—and the most effective combinations of these all. Of course, the question for the future will be how this new knowledge and methodology will affect the cultural and social conditions of traditional communities, and what unexpected events may occur in terms of society and the ecological background.

In Hungary, extensive animal husbandry is being significantly reduced by intensive technologies and breeds, which often require less labour and, in some respects, less expertise. In addition, problems are already emerging in this sector due to a lack of reliable labour. Another negative aspect is that intensive livestock farming has become a form of agriculture that is unsustainable in the long term for humanity in today's drastically extreme and changing ecological conditions, causing enormous environmental stress and ecological damage. At the same time, animal products can be produced entirely through

extensive grazing, which would be extremely beneficial for our natural environment and biodiversity. However, this requires special knowledge and special people. The special knowledge also requires new and special methods. This is, why we are trying to launch innovations from the bottom up in the interest of biodiversity: a school for herders in Hungary, the knowledge library about the traditional ecological knowledge of herders, and the advocacy of Hungarian herders for the first time.

We must accept as a fundamental fact that the current structure of Hungary's political, regulatory, and economic infrastructure does not allow for anything other than bottom-up initiatives, and even then, many forms of such initiatives are made impossible by various interests. Therefore, we can only choose research and intervention methods that are fully understood and supported by local communities and are also useful for the entire pastoral community of the country. In this way, the pastoral community, which otherwise holds many different views, will be able to present a unified professional stance on certain issues within the policy and institutional frameworks. Although their voice does not yet carry much weight in the decision-making and regulatory environment, they can be expected to gradually become involved in lower and middle-level consultation processes. However, none of this can happen without research partnerships. At the same time, research results are less likely to be implemented in agriculture, so herders and researchers working with herders are trying to jointly enter the policy gap they are trying to create for themselves. If these efforts are successful, herders and their supporters will have a greater opportunity to influence processes that strongly serve the interests of biodiversity as well as their livelihoods.

D2.2

Mértola Future Lab

Case

CES, Portugal

November 2025

Authors

Luciane Lucas dos Santos and Fernanda Belizário

Summary

Summary of Deliverable

The Mértola case study (Mértola Future Lab) explores how regenerative governance and community-led initiatives can offer transformative responses to desertification, climate change, and rural abandonment. The focus of the Mértola case study is to examine how regenerative practices can be activated through local food systems to enhance community resilience in a context shaped by ecological degradation, rural depopulation, and socio-economic marginalization.

Known for its rich historical heritage and striking semi-arid landscape, Mértola, a municipality in the Baixo Alentejo Region in Portugal, today faces major ecological and socio-economic challenges. These include population decline, aging demographics, limited economic opportunities, and increasing climate vulnerability. Yet, this apparent fragility has also opened space for experimentation with innovative, inclusive, and sustainable alternatives.

Mértola is one of the pilot sites of the BIOTraCes project, which investigates how biodiversity can be protected and regenerated through just and inclusive governance. In this context, the Mértola case highlights the value of a participatory approach to ecological transition. Mértola's case is particularly relevant because it links environmental regeneration with social justice by mobilizing local knowledge, fostering intergenerational dialogue, and promoting a diversity of actors and experiences. Similarly, this case allows us to reflect upon the relevance of intersectional lenses to go a step further in terms of environmental justice, with underrepresented groups taking benefit from environmental betterments and being less affected by an unequal environmental burden.

At the heart of this process is the Mértola Future Lab, a local strategy towards ecological transition that gathers a range of initiatives and projects to this end, as well as a diversified group of organizations committed to be part of a collectively designed strategy to face climate change in a semi-arid area. Mértola Future Lab addresses key regional concerns such as climate adaptation and biodiversity regeneration, while also tackling social and economic resilience. It is worth recalling that 47% of Mértola's surface is already affected by high rates of soil degradation (Roxo, Casimiro & Tiago, s/d), which points out not only the environmental problem but also the impacts on agricultural practices.

This local strategy co-designed and co-implemented by different local organizations and stakeholders - highly animated by the Mértola City Council - has managed to bring together public institutions like the Mértola City Council and the Santana de Cambas' Community Meeting House, educational institutions such as local schools, associations and NGOs such as the Guadiana Valley Business Association and the Agency for the local development in the Southwest Alentejo (ESDIME), and grassroots associations like Terra Sintrópica. Mértola City Council and Terra Sintrópica Association play a pivotal role in this BIOTraCes' case study as they are the societal partners in the case, welcoming the CES team and helping us understand the cross-case strategy in Mértola engaging a diversified set of organizations.

What makes the Mértola case unique is the networked approach to transformation. Terra Sintrópica and Mértola City Council do not act alone—it is part of a broad coalition that includes public authorities, NGOs, schools, vocational training centers, research institutes, and regional development agencies. Many of these partners are also involved in the Mértola Food Network, a participatory governance model that brings different actors together around the shared goal of food safety. This collaborative ethos ensures that regeneration is not treated as a technical fix, but as a deeply social and political process that requires engagement, negotiation, and redistribution of power and resources.

In terms of funding, the sustainability of these efforts relies on a mosaic of national and international sources, including foundations such as Stiftung Drittes Millennium and the

Transformative Biodiversity Innovations

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Leopold Bachmann Stiftung, EU funds (notably from the ERDF via COMPETE 2020), and cross-border cooperation programs like POCTEP (Interreg Spain-Portugal). Programs like the Healthy Neighborhoods Programme also support specific projects that address social vulnerabilities through ecological action.

In sum, the Mértola case offers a vivid example of how small rural communities can become laboratories for regeneration and resilience. By placing community participation, environmental justice, and local sovereignty at the center of ecological transformation, Mértola challenges the dominant narrative that rural peripheries are doomed to decline. Instead, it invites us to see such territories as fertile grounds for reimagining the relationship between people, places, and biodiversity.

Transformative Biodiversity Innovations (D2.2)

1.1 Analysis of Inclusion/Exclusion Mechanisms

Exclusionary Practices

Although syntropic agriculture and regenerative practices are being tested in Mértola, much of Alentejo's agricultural paradigm remains rooted in conventional, large-scale farming models. These dominant models prioritize market logics, water-intensive methods, and standardized production (Nathan, 2023). Exclusion is also reinforced by subsidy structures and public procurement laws. CAP (Common Agricultural Policy) incentives in Portugal often prioritize conventional agriculture, limiting access to resources for small producers practicing regenerative methods. Additionally, EU procurement directives, which mandate selection based on lowest price, disadvantage local farmers and discourage biodiversity-oriented food systems.

Power asymmetries play a central role in marginalization. Perspectives aligned with industrial agriculture and centralized planning often dominate political discourse and policy implementation at a regional and national level. As a result, local producers and elderly residents with land-based knowledge are rarely consulted in broader territorial planning.

A cultural mismatch also sustains exclusion. Prevalent imaginaries of Alentejo — as a region of open plains, cereal crops, and hard manual labor — perpetuate resistance to alternative ecologies and regenerative farming. These imaginaries act as mental lock-ins that hinder change, casting new practices as incompatible with the region's perceived identity.

Inclusive Mechanisms

Despite these exclusionary tendencies, Mértola also demonstrates noteworthy inclusive mechanisms that contribute to a more just and effective biodiversity governance.

Mértola City Council has fostered a horizontal approach that brings together diverse actors—from school cooks and farmers to technicians— in shared decision-making spaces like the Mértola Food Network. This network provides a forum for co-creation and coordination across food production, procurement, and distribution, helping ensure that regenerative practices are locally grounded and collectively supported. Besides, Mértola, through its co-governance model, has stimulated different practices, more connected with biodiversity regeneration, in neighboring municipalities such as Alcoutim, Castro Verde, and Ourique. Partnerships in biodiversity regeneration projects have been particularly common. A good example is the partnership between the Mértola City Council, the Alcoutim City Council, TSA and the Forest Owners Association of Cumeadas do Baixo Guadiana for converting degraded forest ecosystems of monoculture of stone pine, eucalyptus and acacia in the semi-arid territories of Mértola and Alcoutim into native forest (Mértola, website, 2022).

The municipality of Mértola has shown openness to participatory governance beyond rhetoric. For example, despite restrictive procurement laws, it has implemented significant changes in collective catering systems in schools and care centers, prioritizing local and organic food. These changes, though technically complex and legally constrained, were made possible through collective coordination and trust between actors.

Central among these is the regenerative framework of syntropy, promoted by the Terra Sintropica Association (TSA). This philosophy underpins many of Mértola's participatory projects and has become a guiding principle in fostering inclusive biodiversity strategies, even when the name syntropy has not been evoked.

Several targeted initiatives have also promoted inclusion. The "Shelter Land" project, co-led by TSA and international partners, provides Afghan refugees with training in syntropic

agriculture, integrating them into local regeneration efforts. This initiative not only addresses environmental goals but also supports social inclusion and capacity-building for marginalized groups. Projects like “Grandmother’s Kitchen” and “There’s a Party in the Forest Garden” illustrate efforts to bridge generational divides and validate the knowledge of older residents. These initiatives recognize the role of elderly women in preserving healthy food practices and foster intergenerational exchange. The use of convivial tools such as music, painting, and storytelling helps make regenerative knowledge accessible and emotionally resonant, reinforcing a sense of ownership among participants.

Nonetheless, inclusion remains a dynamic and contested process. Differences persist between progressive and conservative factions in the municipality. While TSA and allied actors have created an “experimental space” of governance and imagination, a considerable part of the population remains uninformed or disconnected from these initiatives. This “two Mértolas” dynamic points to the need for improved communication and mobility support (e.g., transportation from remote parishes) to ensure broader participation.

1.2 Niche Innovators and Key players

A. Terra Sintrópica Association (TSA)

As a pioneering actor in regenerative agriculture, TSA is a key actor in Mértola’s transformative ecosystem. Their approach is rooted in syntropy—a concept that emphasizes mutualism and co-evolution between humans and non-humans—as the basis for biodiversity regeneration and socio-political renewal.

B. ESDIME (Agency for Local Development in the Southeast Alentejo)

ESDIME has consistently operated at the interface of development policy and ecological innovation. It has introduced techniques such as holistic grazing and keyline water retention design to the regional landscape, created local funding instruments to support small farmers in adopting biodiversity-friendly practices.

C. Mértola Biological Station (MBS)

MBS is both a scientific platform and a local innovation hub. It contributes to biodiversity research and promotes educational programs that link ecological theory with applied action. As a core partner in the “Mértola—Laboratory for the Future” initiative, EBM advances interdisciplinary approaches to address desertification, soil erosion, and climate adaptation.

D. Mértola Food Network (MFN)

MFN is a collaborative network composed of institutional and community members who share responsibilities in redesigning local food systems. It fosters horizontal governance structures, mutual accountability, and intergenerational learning. Through regular meetings and participatory forums, FMN exemplifies collective agency and shared vision in the context of biodiversity and food sovereignty.

E. Mértola Future Lab

A more recent yet increasingly influential player is the *Mértola Future Lab*, an innovation platform aimed at envisioning and co-producing long-term strategies for ecological transition. Coordinated in close synergy with MBS and animated by MCC and other local

actors, the Future Lab functions as both a think tank and an experimental space, mobilizing young researchers, policymakers, and local stakeholders to reimagine land use, sustainability, and community futures.

The Influence of Niche Innovators and Key Players

The agency of these actors is increasingly recognized at both local and national levels. Some of them are internationally recognized - researchers and activists from different countries coming to Mértola to see what has been done in the territory for soil regeneration and biodiversity.

Their legitimacy stems not only from the visible outcomes of their projects — such as restored soils, educational gardens, or altered procurement models — but from their process-oriented approaches. These niche players promote co-design, long-term experimentation, and knowledge exchange, which are critical for systemic change.

- ✓ **TSA's syntropic training programs** have been challenging imaginaries of what agriculture can be in semi-arid regions.
- ✓ **ESDIME's food sovereignty agenda** has been introducing alternatives to the subsidy-dependent monoculture paradigm.
- ✓ **MBS' research networks** offer scientific validation and technical tools that support policy experimentation.
- ✓ **MFN's collective decisions** have changed public procurement routines, prioritizing local and healthy food over industrial products.
- ✓ **The Future Lab's strategic foresight** brings long-term thinking into local planning and helps bridge generational divides in imagining biodiversity futures.

The Centre for Social Studies (CES) is a recognized research institution committed to democratizing knowledge and revitalizing human rights through approaches that are democratic, participatory, and decolonial. With a strong impact in the social sciences and humanities, CES has engaged with several of these innovators through meetings, interviews and participant observation, and will co-host public events throughout 2025-26. CES was also invited to attend MFN meetings and conducted a focus group with its members. This session helped the network identify key communication gaps — particularly with youth and elders — and collaboratively develop an action plan aimed at supporting biodiversity regeneration and transforming food systems.

CES also established ties with the Future Lab, TSA and MCC to explore participatory methods and examine the role of imagination and narrative in biodiversity restoration. Ongoing conversations aim to develop future-oriented workshops with rural youth and community leaders.

It is important to emphasize that these key players are highly developed in both their intervention and research strategies. As such, CES does not assume a central or leading role in driving innovation within the field. On the contrary, we position ourselves as a supportive and respectful partner, acknowledging the deep expertise and strategic clarity already present among the local actors.

How Innovators Engage with the Community

Each of these niche players maintains strong connections to the community:

- ✓ TSA works directly with elders, refugees, and school children.
- ✓ ESDIME facilitates farmer-to-farmer knowledge exchange.

- ✓ MBS and the Future Lab engage students and researchers in applied ecological research and scenario planning.
- ✓ FMN connects institutional kitchens to small-scale producers and families

1.3 Scalable Bottom-Up Innovations for Transformative Change

A. Identification of Existing Innovations

In Mértola, innovations related to biodiversity are deeply tied to regenerative agriculture, participatory governance, and local food systems. These innovations differ markedly from conventional top-down or business-as-usual policies by rooting their transformative potential in collaborative learning, knowledge co-production, and experimentation. Three core innovations stand out:

A.1 Syntropic Agriculture and Terra Sintropica Association (TSA)

TSA plays a leading role in implementing syntropic agriculture in the region.

The Shelter Land Project exemplifies the potential for both biodiversity restoration and social inclusion. Hosting Afghan refugees and training them in syntropic practices, the project promotes intercultural learning, local knowledge exchange, and the integration of marginalized groups into regeneration efforts.

A.2 Mértola Biological Station (MBS)

MBS, part of the broader strategy "Mértola: Laboratory for the Future," represents institutional innovation. It combines research, vocational training, and service provision (e.g., soil analysis, game management plans) in a context where ecological transition is a survival strategy. MBS challenges the perception of Mértola as a place with no future by attracting researchers and providing youth with new vocational pathways linked to biodiversity and agroecology.

A.3 Food System Innovations: The Mértola Food Network (MFN)

The MFN is a group where local producers, public officials, cooks, technicians, and social organizations jointly develop strategies to enhance local food systems. Its initiatives include transforming school menus, supporting proximity agriculture, and integrating biodiversity concerns into collective catering.

B. Transformative Potential and Equitable Access

These innovations propose system-level shifts in the way land, food, and knowledge are managed. Their "nature positive" orientation is evident in the promotion of soil regeneration, agro-biodiversity, sustainable diets, and equitable inclusion. However, equitable access remains a challenge, particularly for isolated communities, low-income residents, and elderly populations. Residents in remote villages still face structural barriers such as lack of transportation and local markets. Similarly, the Roma community remains underrepresented in regeneration initiatives. Addressing these inequalities is essential to scaling the innovations inclusively.

C. Integration of Cultural and Epistemic Diversity

A notable feature of Mértola's approach is the integration of cultural and epistemic diversity. TSA's methods include participatory and experiential activities like the Therapeutic Garden Project, which combines art, memory, and ecological care with older residents. These initiatives foster new narratives and imaginaries about the territory, bridging the gap between scientific and traditional ecological knowledge.

The regeneration discourse in Mértola avoids technocratic imposition. Instead, it recognises the agency of local actors, particularly the elderly, whose knowledge is considered vital to the success of land-use changes. Syntropic agriculture, in this context, is not just a technique but a method of social inclusion and mutual recognition.

D. Social Networks and Key Stakeholders

The strength of the innovations relies on a dense and responsive social network involving:

- ✓ TSA and its core team
- ✓ MBS researchers and staff
- ✓ Mértola City Council (especially the Vice-President)
- ✓ ESDIME (development agency)
- ✓ Local producers and cooperatives
- ✓ Educators, school cooks, and healthcare workers
- ✓ Community members, including children and the elderly

E. Diachronic Analysis: From Initiation to Effects

E.1 Prior to the emergence of regenerative practices, Mértola's socio-ecological system was characterized by soil degradation, emigration, and dependency on EU subsidies tied to conventional agricultural practices. Public procurement followed price-based criteria, sidelining local producers.

E.2 Today, the impact of these innovations is visible in various dimensions:

- ✓ School and community catering include local and organic produce.
- ✓ New vocational pathways in agroecology and wildlife management are emerging.
- ✓ Youth are slowly being re-engaged with rural futures.
- ✓ Dialogue on water retention, dryland farming, and regenerative pastures is gaining ground.

1.4 Initial Mapping of Interventions

The regeneration strategy underway in Mértola aims to go beyond conventional biodiversity protection by grounding actions in community participation, ecological experimentation, and regenerative economics. However, a central challenge persists how to make these practices visible and accessible to the municipality's 106 dispersed populations, many of whom remain unaware or disconnected from the regeneration underway.

CES, in collaboration with Terra Sintrópica (TSA) and the Mértola City Council (MCC), carried out a second round of focus groups (FG2_PT_02-25, see Deliverable 2.4). designed to deepen understanding of local perceptions, and more importantly, to engage residents ensuring that all seven parishes were represented, and that citizens from various social positions—not only institutional actors—were heard.

A key strategy involves transforming participation from passive consultation to active learning. For instance, at the end of the focus groups, participants were offered organic baskets produced by TSA. This was more than a symbolic gesture, but a pedagogical act: a way to materialize what regeneration means—tangible, edible, rooted in the territory.

Through taste, people learn what is being grown regeneratively and how it impacts soil, health, and autonomy.

The strategy proposed in the action plan will include community communication proposals, participatory tools that include a children's diary project documenting biodiversity, a "Nursery of Experiences" featuring workshops on traditional knowledge and memory-based planting, and economic regeneration activities like discussions on community redistribution and local entrepreneurship.

To monitor progress, metrics include participation diversity, engagement with communication tools, and feedback on inclusion and relevance. The initiative challenges top-down conservation by rooting biodiversity protection in everyday life and by co-designing solutions with the community. Lessons learned emphasize the need for inclusive language, culturally resonant methods, and infrastructure that supports care and mobility—key considerations for future interventions under Task 2.4.

1.5 Discussion

The Mértola case offers a distinctive lens through which to reflect on the complexities of implementing transformative change via biodiversity-focused bottom-up interventions. It encapsulates both the promises and the limitations inherent in efforts to foster ecological restoration in regions marked by desertification, depopulation, and entrenched economic and cultural practices. The findings from the various sections—especially the analysis of niche innovators, scalable innovations, and participatory gaps—reveal that while progress is evident, the broader structural conditions demand both respecting community rhythms and critical scrutiny from researchers and institutional actors alike.

One of the critical contributions of this case lies in challenging the traditional hierarchy of expertise in sustainability transitions. As noted in earlier sections, organizations such as Terra Sintropica (TSA), ESDIME, and the Mértola Biological Station (MBS) do not operate as satellites of research or university-led design; they are fully fledged nodes of innovation in themselves. In this context, CES situates itself as an interlocutor, someone that brings in reflexivity, supports critical dialogue, and engages in co-learning, rather than leading or imposing interventions.

This epistemic posture not only fosters trust but aligns with the very principle of regenerative governance—transcending extractive forms of knowledge production to embrace collaborative, situated, and plural epistemologies. In this sense, the discussion reaffirms that innovation in Mértola is about creating the cultural and emotional infrastructure for people to imagine different futures.

The co-governance structures observed in Mértola—particularly the functioning of the Food Mértola Network and the participatory ethos behind MBS and TSA—provide fertile ground for rethinking how collective responsibility can be enacted. These networks, while still navigating tensions related to power asymmetries, funding competition, and differing ecological visions, demonstrate an impressive capacity to hold diversity and disagreement without paralysis.

Yet, as the focus group feedback and action plan reflections suggest, this co-governance model remains somewhat more prevalent to "institutionalised" stakeholders. Ordinary citizens from the 106 dispersed populations in Mértola's territory continue to face barriers to meaningful engagement, be it due to isolation, lack of information, or structural socioeconomic constraints.

The implications are clear: interventions must go beyond organizational partnerships and reach deeply into the socio-spatial fabric of the region. This involves acknowledging the multiplicity of knowledge and lived experiences that are often overlooked when participatory processes privilege the most visible or already-organised actors.

A salient thread across the entire process is the evolving understanding of participation— not merely as attendance at meetings or approval of plans, but as the capacity to shape the terms of engagement.

In this sense, the goal is not to mobilize people for “our” sustainability agendas, but to identify points of resonance with their lived realities and help unlock their capacity for autonomous action.

Several actors—particularly MBS and TSA—are actively working to counteract the prevalent narrative that positions Mértola as a land of no future. Through education, youth engagement, and hosting international researchers and refugees, they are crafting new imaginaries of possibility grounded in the soil, biodiversity, and intercultural cohabitation.

While the innovations in Mértola are impressive in scope and ambition, the discussion also highlights key equity gaps that require ongoing attention. The underrepresentation of the Roma community, the misrecognition of women's role in the community's resilience and knowledge, the challenges faced by isolated elderly populations, and the limitations posed by inadequate transportation infrastructure all point to a need for more inclusive frameworks.

These are not minor obstacles. They speak to the layered inequalities that can undermine otherwise well-designed ecological strategies.

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D2.2

Social opportunities in ecological recovery

MRU, Lithuania

November 2025

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Summary

Summary of the deliverable

There is a global momentum behind acknowledging the pressures on rivers and the need for prompt and coordinated action to restore them. The Anykščiai dam case study examines one of Lithuania's and Europe's most common river restoration challenges: restoring fragmented and degraded rivers and improving habitats for biodiversity in the contexts where support from society and local communities is lacking. Located in the small town of Anykščiai in northeastern Lithuania, the Šventoji River is an ecological corridor of national importance and a symbolic feature of Anykščiai town. Yet, like many European rivers, it has been altered by the construction of dams. The Anykščiai dam, originally built for hydropower but now functionally obsolete, remains a major barrier to ecological connectivity. It obstructs fish migration, degrades river habitats, and drives biodiversity loss. At the same time, the dam has become a visible part of the town's landscape and cultural memory, creating difficulties in discussions about its future. This case sits at the intersection of urgent need for coordinated environmental action and local socio-cultural realities. At the European level, as many rivers are no longer free flowing due to heavy fragmentation, the Water Framework Directive and the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 call for restoring good ecological status in rivers and reconnecting at least 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers. Lithuania's national environmental policies and action plans recognize the need for action, and scientific assessments identify the Anykščiai dam as one of the country's priority barriers for removal due to its ecological impact and limited socio-economic value. However, translating these policy frameworks into local practice is limited by a number of factors, including weak prioritization of river restoration in political agendas, stakeholder opposition, limited financing, and weak community support and willingness to accept environmental change related to river restoration. Past efforts to initiate discussions on dam removal showed that without collaboration and shared commitment, progress stalls, underscoring the need for collective responsibility. The BIOTraCes project takes up this challenge by investigating how participatory action research (PAR) can support transformative biodiversity governance. Working with societal partners the project explores how inclusive and creative engagement methods can reframe contentious debates into opportunities for dialogue and co-creation. Through stakeholder interviews, media and policy analysis, and experimental participatory practices, the research seeks to understand how residents, authorities, businesses, and cultural actors construct meaning around the river, and how these meanings can be included in decision-making processes and creating a shared future for the Šventoji River, where biodiversity thrives and the river becomes an integral part of the community. The significance of the Anykščiai case lies in both its ecological and social dimensions. Ecologically, dam removal offers an opportunity to restore natural riverine processes and habitats for the migratory fish. Socially, the case reveals how histories, identities, and attachments to place shape environmental governance. It demonstrates that biodiversity restoration requires building trust, integrating plural knowledge systems, and creating genuine spaces for shared decision-making in addition to technical solutions. In this sense, the Anykščiai dam is a symbol of the broader challenge of reconciling ecological sustainability with strengthening community engagement and to encourage local ownership and leadership in environmental action across Europe.

Transformative biodiversity innovations (D2.2)

1.1. Analysis of Inclusion/Exclusion Mechanisms

Exclusionary practices

In our case study, exclusionary dynamics do not stem directly from opposition to environmental goals (e.g. anti-environmental sentiment), but from more subtle processes: uneven flows of knowledge, limited opportunities for bottom-up environmental engagement, strong attachments to familiar human-shaped landscapes, and a broader societal detachment from the river and its biodiversity due to low dependence on them for livelihoods and well-being. Across nearly all interviews, a clear message emerged: community members feel a strong and sincere attachment to their river. Their connection to nature is formed through daily experiences, such as swimming, walking, observing seasonal changes, or angling, rather than scientific knowledge alone. Many participants expressed genuine affection and appreciation for the river's vitality, though their understanding of what constitutes a "healthy" river often differs from institutional or academic perspectives. This highlights both the depth of local connection to the river and the existing gaps in knowledge related to biodiversity and the ecological changes associated with restoration efforts. This difference does not signal disinterest but reveals an opportunity to connect diverse ways of knowing. Community perspectives, grounded in lived experience and sensory engagement, complement the formal biodiversity knowledge that circulates within scientific, NGO, and regulatory spheres. Strengthening dialogue between these domains can foster more inclusive, grounded, and co-created understandings of biodiversity and its role in community well-being — from recreation and cultural identity to food and everyday enjoyment of the river. Early initiatives to introduce dam removal in the community were primarily communicated by emphasizing the ecological goals of river restoration — particularly the improvement of salmonid migration. While nature-centred, they were less anchored in localized, tangible, and emotionally resonant narratives that could have connected more naturally with community members. In the absence of clear arguments showing how the project would benefit the community according to its own values and priorities (for example, interviews indicate that history and landscape aesthetics are valued more highly than financial savings), and without concrete, place-specific scientific justification that residents perceived as trustworthy and independent — including environmental impact assessments, models, visualisations, simulations, or storytelling grounded in the specific river and townscape — many residents were left to imagine the project's outcomes on their own. Rather than engaging with clear, relatable, and locally meaningful information, they had to rely on speculation, which limited the development of informed and confident support. At the same time, the discussion around dam removal became politicized. Some community members perceived the initiative as being led by particular institutional or interest groups rather than as a shared, community-centred effort. These perceptions, though not necessarily grounded in opposition to restoration itself, reflected broader concerns about inclusion, transparency, and trust in decision-making. Acknowledging and addressing these sentiments provides valuable opportunities to foster dialogue, strengthen trust, and build collective ownership of environmental change. The early communication approach also tended to overlook experiential and place-based forms of knowledge — such as memories of childhood swimming areas, observations of seasonal water changes, or local stories about fish populations. Although these insights may not appear to relate directly to environmental action needed, embracing these ways of knowing can help connect intended environmental measures with lived community experience and communities needs. This, in turn, can lay the foundations for more inclusive, trusted, and enduring forms of environmental stewardship.

Economic considerations further shaped local perspectives in nuanced ways. Businesses connected to tourism, such as kayak rental operators, expressed diverse views on the dam's influence. Some saw its removal as a chance to enhance safety for kayakers —

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especially given the history of tragic accidents at the dam site — while others felt the dam's presence had little impact on their operations or even benefited their businesses. Meanwhile, several hospitality and entertainment businesses voiced concerns that lowering the reservoir could alter the scenic character and recreational appeal of riverside areas. These perspectives underscore the need to understand how environmental actions influence local economies and livelihoods, and how such concerns can be addressed within the project planning process. Recognizing these interconnections does not imply the pursuit of a universal compromise. While constructive agreement should be encouraged, it is not always achievable, and the possibilities and limits of consensus must be communicated transparently. What is essential is establishing a shared understanding of where common ground exists, where it does not, and how environmental decisions can proceed with clarity and accountability, including an honest consideration for the needs of the local businesses. Through open dialogue and transparent communication, environmental restoration can advance in ways that acknowledge economic sensitivities while maintaining a long-term vision of ecological renewal. At the institutional level, hierarchical decision-making remains visible. National goals for restoring longitudinal river connectivity are in place, yet their implementation at the local level progresses slowly. Respondents noted that information about planned projects is often presented in formal formats that are difficult to access or understand—for example, materials written in technical or non-user-friendly language or announcements that are not widely advertised. As a result, communication is not perceived as clear, relatable, or meaningful, and processes for inclusion or co-creation are also limited. Consequently, formal public hearings tend to unfold mainly between political representatives and institutional authorities, leaving local environmental perspectives less visible. This can reinforce the perception that responsibility for environmental stewardship lies primarily with external actors, such as national institutions or the EU. Within this context, existing power dynamics can unintentionally overlook the diversity of local perspectives — from those strongly committed to environmental restoration to others who value the dam's cultural or historical significance. When these place-based insights by anglers, seasonal-residents, local environmental activists, community leaders etc. are not taken into consideration, environmental action can become vulnerable to scepticism and mistrust, even when its goals are widely beneficial. Strengthening participatory mechanisms and valuing local experience alongside formal expertise can support more balanced, inclusive, and context-aware river governance — one that aligns policy objectives with lived experience and the community's longstanding care for the river. A lack of societal support and meaningful social inclusion can leave biodiversity policies structurally fragile. When communities do not fully understand, recognize, or trust the intentions behind conservation measures, even well-designed policies risk becoming brittle. The transformative potential of biodiversity conservation depends on whether society and local communities can see its benefits, relate it to their own values and lived realities, and feel encouraged to support and participate in the process.

Inclusive mechanisms

Despite these challenges, important foundations for more inclusive engagement are being established and gradually strengthened. Our open-ended interviews functioned as both a method of data collection and a modest social innovation. They created an open, respectful environment where community members could engage in dialogue about dam removal with curiosity and confidence. The conversations offered space for participants to share their experiences, express concerns, and formulate ideas and needs related to environmental decision-making. In doing so, the process fostered trust, reflection, and a sense of shared ownership over the future of the river.

The community demonstrates strong potential for bottom-up environmental innovation. A well-established culture of forest protection, supported by grassroots initiatives, shapes a broader appreciation for the natural living environment and the quality of life it provides.

Many respondents described the Šventoji River as a core element of the town's identity and emphasised how nature contributes to everyday wellbeing. Across interviews, there was also a clear sense of admiration for nature itself — a recognition of its intrinsic value, not only its practical benefits for people. While individual perspectives varied, this respect for nature was still apparent and visible throughout many discussions. All this provides fertile ground for expanding environmental stewardship to include river ecosystems. Local actors engaged in eco-tourism, forest bathing, and nature-based education already embody relational values that connect well-being, livelihood, and care for the environment — forming promising nodes of local leadership. Strengthening and connecting these initiatives could play a pivotal role in advancing river restoration efforts. While external partners can help catalyse dialogue and provide resources, lasting transformation grows from within — emerging through locally grounded leadership and the community's own evolving sense of environmental responsibility and belonging. National-level NGOs have played a leading role in bringing the issue of dam removal to public attention. Their initiatives have advanced political advocacy, shaped environmental priorities, and raised public awareness, helping to lay the foundations for national discussions on ecological restoration. If relationships between NGOs and local communities evolve, there is growing potential to complement policy-oriented work with participatory approaches that strengthen local capacity, foster dialogue, and nurture shared ownership of river restoration efforts. Several interrelated factors emerged as particularly important in fostering greater inclusion in river restoration discussions:

- **Environmental impact assessment and visual tools:** Residents frequently emphasised the need to clearly understand how dam removal would affect both the local landscape and the river's ecological dynamics. They sought practical, place-specific information about how water levels would change across seasons, how this might influence access to the water, the attractiveness and usability of existing infrastructure adapted to current water levels, how riverbanks would look, and what implications these changes could have for safety. Many also highlighted the importance of environmental impact assessments, scientific studies, and model simulations that could visually convey expected changes in hydrology, water levels, and ecosystem dynamics, as well as clarify the scope of construction works. Participants stressed that such assessments should address practical concerns, including potential implications for flood risk. Overall, community members expressed a strong appreciation for technical expertise and expected analyses that are both scientifically rigorous and communicated in an accessible, transparent manner.
- **Education and localized narratives:** Ecological restoration becomes more relatable when biodiversity gains are explained through locally meaningful examples. Framing restoration outcomes in relation to specific, valued species — such as iconic or culturally important fish — makes change personally and emotionally relevant. Involving local environmental actors in shaping and communicating these narratives further strengthens trust, relevance, and continuity between scientific and community perspectives.
- **Co-creation workshops:** The co-creation workshops may provide opportunities for participants to explore their relationships with the river and its impoundment, articulate shared needs, and envision future possibilities. Creation of place-identity maps allows community members to reflect on meaningful sites and activities connected to the river. Discussions also considered how the functions of the dam could be reimagined or substituted through alternative solutions, fostering creativity, collaboration, and a sense of collective ownership over the river's future.

Interestingly, the most transformative innovation in our case may be social rather than technical — the practice of genuine dialogue. By moving from one-way information delivery to the cultivation of open conversations, new pathways for agency, mutual understanding, and connection are beginning to emerge. Inclusion and exclusion are not fixed conditions;

they are dynamic processes that evolve over time — shaped by every meeting, every story, every map, and even every silence. In this case study, moments of exclusion often arose from well-intentioned actions that were not fully communicated, while inclusion has taken root through patient dialogue and a willingness to engage with people on their own terms. Effective restoration in Anykščiai depends on revitalising the river and improving how information is shared, understood, and used in decision-making and planning. Creating space for different forms of knowledge and experience related to the Šventoji can strengthen ecological outcomes and build a more informed, constructive relationship between the community and the river.

1.2. Niche Innovators and Key Players

In our case study of Anykščiai, identifying niche innovators and key actors required a more attentive and relational approach. Unlike regions with highly visible “champions” of change, the forces driving biodiversity innovation here are quieter — dispersed across multiple roles and often only beginning to take form. Instead of large, coordinated movements, we observed small yet meaningful initiatives: individuals, informal groups, and everyday community dynamics that signal the early roots of transformative potential. Though their influence may appear subtle, these actors play a crucial role in shaping how biodiversity practices emerge and evolve within the region.

Three main types of niche innovators emerged during our fieldwork:

1. Environmental NGOs

At the national level, environmental NGOs focused on fish conservation and the promotion of free-flowing rivers play a vital role in raising public awareness, educating youth, collaborating with governmental institutions, and addressing illegal activities such as poaching. Their extensive experience and expertise provide an essential foundation for advancing river restoration initiatives. Positioned at the intersection of science, policy, and community engagement, these organizations are well placed to serve as key partners in future efforts to strengthen river health and biodiversity stewardship.

2. Local nature-connected individuals

Within the community, a self-organized group has formed around a shared appreciation of nature and strong personal connections to the local environment. Many community members engage in activities such as forest bathing, angling, kayaking, boating, organising hiking trips, environmental education, eco-tourism, and cold-water swimming — practices that reflect a deep, experience-based connection to the place. Although they may not formally identify as “environmentalists,” their everyday engagement with the river and its surroundings positions them as promising catalysts for grassroots innovation and locally grounded stewardship.

3. Soft-bridge builders: researchers and intermediaries

Our team, drawing on backgrounds in psychology and counselling, placed particular emphasis on fostering constructive dialogue, cultivating relationships, and recognizing the diversity of values — ecological, cultural, and social — that shape local perspectives. Throughout the process, we remained mindful that nature itself represents a central stakeholder in this case, not merely a backdrop to human activity. While we did not seek to drive community change directly, our relational, participatory, and attentive approach created openings for reflection and connection — spaces where grassroots energies and local initiatives may gradually take root.

It is also worth noting that technical experts and academics can play a complementary role in this process by fostering technically grounded, non-political discussions with community members, addressing local concerns through accessible communication and professional

expertise. In doing so, they can help translate complex ecological information into shared understanding, reinforcing trust and enabling informed participation in environmental decision-making.

The innovators identified in this study contribute in distinct yet complementary ways to river restoration.

1. **National NGOs.**

Operating primarily at the national scale, environmental NGOs bring valuable knowledge about environmental issues, policy experience, and advocacy skills. When their activities include and empower local residents, they can effectively bridge scales of governance, transforming potential distance into trust and shared purpose. Their influence is well established in policymaking and environmental planning, and with greater local collaboration, they hold strong potential to enhance community-level engagement and understanding.

2. **Local nature-oriented individuals.**

Community members who engage in practices such as forest bathing, eco-tourism, or river-based recreation are deeply embedded in the local social fabric. Their credibility stems from being recognized as “one of us” — neighbours, peers, and caretakers of familiar landscapes. Their contributions to biodiversity and environmental awareness often arise organically, as a natural extension of everyday life rather than formal activism. This authenticity and emotional connection to place offer a powerful foundation for nurturing locally grounded stewardship and collective care for the river

3. **Researchers and intermediaries.**

Researchers and other intermediaries serve as important bridges between institutional structures and community realities. Although external by background, their participatory and empathetic approach positions them as trusted collaborators. By emphasizing listening, dialogue, and co-learning, they help weave connections between scientific knowledge, policy priorities, and lived experience. This bridging role is essential for creating inclusive, adaptive, and trust-based approaches to river governance.

Interestingly, the “agency” of non-human actors — particularly the river itself and its components, such as fish — played a significant symbolic role in discussions about river health. Nature-connected individuals often described the river and its species not as passive background elements but as co-inhabitants — living systems deserving of respect. This recognition of more-than-human agency, though not always articulated explicitly, represents a subtle yet important form of innovation in itself.

Influence and recognition

The recognition of these niche innovators varies greatly:

- Environmental NGOs are widely recognised for their national-level contributions to policy, advocacy, and education. In local contexts, however, they are often seen as external actors, which can limit trust and reduce the impact of their engagement on issues such as the dam. At the same time, interviews showed that environmental voices exist within the community itself, often expressing concerns and values similar to those raised by NGOs, yet remaining less active and/or visible. Strengthening the presence of environmental voices and organisations locally — through education, dialogue, and place-based engagement — could help demonstrate that ecological restoration is not only a national priority but also a matter of local relevance and benefit. Local individuals who are strongly connected to nature hold significant social credibility, yet they are not currently organised or engaged specifically around river restoration. As a result, their potential to

contribute to local dialogue and support for restoration remains largely untapped. Our research-based efforts to build bridges were met with openness and thoughtful curiosity. Participants frequently asked whether our engagement was genuinely participatory or guided by predetermined agendas. Through transparency—being clear about our own positions while remaining attentive and willing to listen—we were able to foster a degree of trust. Although our work has not yet transformed local dynamics, many interviewees expressed appreciation for the opportunity for open dialogue, suggesting that sustained relational practices could gradually strengthen recognition and long-term impact.

Thus, while none of these innovators (yet) drive large-scale change, their combined presence is helping to loosen rigid frames around what the river could be.

The approaches brought by niche innovators have some similarities, but to some degree differ from mainstream conservation practices:

- NGOs advocate for the most effective practices from an ecological perspective, including dam removal, and they generally resist diluted solutions that weaken environmental outcomes. Their role often involves drawing attention to difficult or long-standing problems that require decisive action, positioning them as one of the more ambitious voices in river restoration debates.
- Local nature-appreciating individuals, by contrast, bring a relational and experience-based perspective to discussions about the river. Their focus is less on technical details and more on values, emotional connections to the environment. They act as informal stewards of place-based values, grounding environmental discussions in lived experience rather than in formal policies or quantitative targets.
- Our research activities represented a form of relational science that values both technical expertise and lived experience, seeking to integrate them in dialogue.

These differing approaches challenge traditional "inform/instruct" models of conservation by introducing participation, emotion, memory, and belonging into biodiversity dialogues.

Involvement of niche innovators in field activities

Due to the specifics of the case study, there has been no structured collaboration with niche innovators beyond the research interviews themselves. Our engagement has mainly taken the form of **conversations** – open-ended, relational, and oriented toward listening rather than directing.

- **Environmental NGO representatives** were included among the interviewees. They shared their views on river health and fish conservation, adding valuable perspectives to the broader understanding of biodiversity challenges. However, their involvement remained largely at the level of discussion rather than active participation in local initiatives.
- **Locally connected individuals** also took part in the interviews, offering reflections closely tied to their lived experiences with the river. Their voices were deeply personal and grounded in long-standing relationships with nature, though not organized into formal advocacy efforts. Through these contributions, they articulated the meanings the river holds in everyday life and highlighted how the bond between the community and the river could be strengthened in future restoration efforts.
- As **researchers**, our role was to support diverse actors and create space for these conversations to unfold in a transparent, respectful, and emotionally attentive manner – recognizing plural values and perspectives. We also sought to strengthen the foundation for future engagement by encouraging preparedness, building

expertise, and providing scientifically grounded information to ensure that the community can make informed decisions about the future of the river and the dam. We made conscious efforts to demonstrate our willingness to accompany the community in its own reflections. This relational approach, while modest, has already begun to soften some of the defensiveness that often surrounds discussions of ecological change.

Engagement with niche innovators has focused on establishing relationships and dialogue. We see this as essential groundwork for future biodiversity restoration efforts that are rooted in the community itself.

Conclusion: the quiet power of small innovations

In sum, while Anykščiai does not currently have a high-profile movement for river restoration or biodiversity innovation, the groundwork is being laid through diverse and complementary channels:

- **National NGOs** keep the scientific and policy discussion alive.
- **Local nature-connected individuals** maintain a cultural and emotional link to the river.
- **Research-based relational engagement** introduces new models for addressing complex environmental issues.

These niche innovations demonstrate meaningful ways of fostering dialogue, rebuilding trust, and expanding collective imagination — all of which are essential for inclusive environmental governance. In a context where top-down solutions have often met resistance, these emerging practices are shaping the conditions for broader and more enduring transformations. Here, innovation is not defined by spectacle or speed, but by patience, care, and the steady creation of foundations on which deeper ecological and social change can take root.

1.3. Scalable Bottom-Up Innovations for Transformative Change

In the context of our case study, innovation is understood as a place-based and context-sensitive process — one deeply tied to local circumstances, relationships, and timing. Innovation for river biodiversity conservation depends strongly on context and should align with local needs, values, and capacities. In this case, many of the actions that qualify as “innovative” from the perspective of biodiversity and participatory research may appear simple on the surface, yet they represent forms of social innovation. Effective communication is essential: information must be understandable, accessible, and relatable to community life, clearly demonstrating the ecological and community benefits that restoration can bring. Alongside this, creating open spaces for dialogue, strengthening trust between institutions and communities, and developing holistic, long-term responses to complex challenges help establish the conditions for meaningful engagement. Providing technical knowledge on ecological restoration further reinforces this foundation. Taken together, these efforts function as soft innovations that rebuild trust, enhance legitimacy, and support shared ownership of environmentally significant decisions. In a community where public trust is growing, biodiversity awareness is expanding, and participatory practices are taking shape, these initiatives lay a strong foundation for lasting transformation by linking scientific integrity with social inclusion. The same principle applies to participatory practices: in some settings, creative co-creation methods — such as theatre, art-based workshops, or interactive mapping — can inspire rapid engagement and imagination. The introduction of such methods is highly positive when well-timed, as effective innovation depends on sequencing; building trust and communication before introducing more complex tools ensures lasting participation and stronger outcomes. Thus,

context-sensitive innovation involves recognizing that (I) small steps can become radical when they shift entrenched patterns; (II) innovation is measured by the extent to which it opens new social possibilities for biodiversity and community well-being; and (III) meaningful change begins by meeting people where they are and fostering transformation from within their realities. In essence, innovation here is defined by relevance, timing, and relational care rather than by sophistication. In our case study, bottom-up biodiversity innovations are emerging through early seeds of transformation — small, scattered practices and community initiatives that are beginning to take root. Recognizing and nurturing these seeds with care and continuity is vital for the long-term restoration of biodiversity along the Šventoji River. Supporting and empowering environmental voices within the community is a valuable approach. In river-related contexts, however, these voices can be few, as changes in ecosystems are often visible mainly to specialists and dedicated enthusiasts. These small groups frequently seek collaboration and support from national-level actors to strengthen environmental advocacy locally.

Existing innovations and their transformative potential

At present, we see two main clusters of activity that could be considered emerging bottom-up innovations:

1. Local nature-appreciating individuals and informal networks

While there is no formal grassroots movement for river restoration, our interviews showed that an unorganised group of residents express strong concern for the river and recognise the need to address the challenges created by the dam. Bringing these voices into formal processes could strengthen local advocacy for restoration. Interviews also revealed a broader set of residents with deep, often personal connections to nature, though not always to the river itself. Many are engaged in forest conservation, eco-tourism, or nature-based wellness activities. While their current efforts are not focused on river biodiversity, they represent an important foundation for future engagement. Their practices reflect a stewardship-oriented perspective that values ecosystems for their intrinsic and long-term vitality rather than short-term utility.

2. Relational research approaches and trust building

Our own role as researchers introduced a soft innovation into the local dynamic: a way of approaching the community based on relational trust, emotional acknowledgment, and careful listening. By prioritizing open-ended interviews, transparency, and dialogue, we demonstrated that sensitive topics like dam removal could be discussed. This method itself—low-cost, highly replicable—offers a scalable model for fostering biodiversity dialogue and may aid in creating space for more change oriented, well-informed discussions.

Both of these innovation pathways differ from mainstream conservation practices, which often emphasize technical fixes or regulatory compliance without deep engagement with the cultural and emotional landscapes of local communities. What makes these innovations "nature-positive" is their potential to realign community attention towards living ecosystems rather than static, human-engineered landscapes. Instead of framing rivers as infrastructure to be managed, these emerging practices see rivers as dynamic, living systems worthy of respect, restoration, and coexistence. Notably, in many conversations, the river itself emerged as a key non-human actor — a symbol through which residents connect to the broader ecosystem. Discussions about time spent by the river, leisure activities, and observations of nature — such as birds, fish, vegetation, or changes in sedimentation processes over the years — became important entry points for discussing ecological matters with local residents. At the same time, our relational engagement model promotes a slower, more participatory form of biodiversity action — one that recognizes local needs, beliefs and values rather than dismissing them. Access to these emerging

innovations is uneven. People already connected to nature through livelihoods (e.g., eco-tourism operators) or personal values are more likely to engage. In contrast, other residents – especially those for whom the river is primarily a backdrop to daily life – may remain excluded unless engagement efforts are extended thoughtfully and respectfully. Integrating grassroots dynamics into formal planning creates a strong opportunity for more effective biodiversity action. By actively connecting institutional actors with community members, project planning and implementation can better reflect local needs and perspectives. This approach strengthens engagement, builds community support, and contributes to more durable and successful restoration outcomes.

Networks and social relationships

The social network supporting these innovations is still loose and mostly informal. It includes:

- Residents with connections to the river and biodiversity (usually anglers, e.g. fly-fishing enthusiasts)
- Residents passionate about local nature (but often not identifying as "activists"),
- Local organizers of eco-cultural festivals,
- Small business owners involved in nature-based tourism,
- Researchers facilitating trust-based engagement,
- And a few NGOs operating at the regional and national level.

However, connections between these actors are often weak or fragmented. Building stronger links—especially connecting personal attachments to broader ecological narratives—will be essential for scaling transformative change.

Diachronic insights: observations rather than comparisons

Because we did not conduct a systematic before-and-after evaluation, we cannot definitively describe changes in community attitudes or biodiversity practices over time. Our fieldwork represents only a **snapshot**: a careful listening to how the situation feels and is perceived *at the time of our study*.

What we can say is that, based on interviews and community conversations:

- Many residents noted that previous discussions about the dam and river restoration were largely initiated by political or external actors and were often perceived as politicised or ideological, rather than grounded in genuine environmental concern or clear, evidence-based arguments for action. Conversations that lacked clear technical or scientific justification struggled to build trust, dialogue, and support. In contrast, information presented as case specific in a factual, transparent, and technically grounded manner was regarded as trustworthy, reflecting a broader preference for scientific expertise over political rhetoric or bureaucratic argumentation, such as meeting policy goals.
- During our engagement, people frequently expressed interest and willingness to discuss the river and its future, provided that the conversation remained transparent, respectful, and connected to their lived experiences. A recurring theme across interviews was the desire for concrete, localized information about the ecological impacts of potential changes — such as effects on water levels, public safety, landscape, adaptations to existing infrastructure.

Thus, while we do not claim to have measured any transformation, we can say that many community members appeared open to learning and reflection — provided that future engagement continues to be handled with care, respect for local knowledge, and the

gradual building of trust through expertise and professionally delivered solutions rather than quick fixes. Our experience suggests that **the conditions for dialogue are present** – but must be nurtured patiently and relationally, rather than assumed to exist by default.

Challenges and opportunities

While promising, these innovations are still young and face risks:

- **Fragmentation** among local actors,
- **Limited biodiversity knowledge** among residents,
- **Potential for misinterpretation** (e.g., seeing impoundment as "natural" habitats to be preserved),
- **Lack of participatory engagement** methods.

Addressing these challenges will require:

- Long-term commitment to community-centered dialogue,
- Recognition of the emotional and historical attachments to the river,
- Investment in building local leadership for biodiversity,
- And policies that allow time for trust and informedness of the community to grow, rather than rushing processes in the name of efficiency.

Closing reflection

In the Anykščiai case, transformative change is most likely to unfold through steady, grounded processes of dialogue, trust-building, and the growing embrace of relational values toward the river. These emerging forms of soft, social innovation are modest in scale yet significant in impact, strengthening the social foundations for lasting ecological renewal. The transformative potential of restoration in Anykščiai comes from strengthening participation. This involves ensuring access to information that is accessible, understandable, independent, and relevant to community life, building a shared understanding of environmental issues, and creating meaningful opportunities for people to engage in planning and decision-making. Incorporating community perspectives can foster a situation where residents not only support but also help lead environmental change. Listening to local voices, recognising community values, and integrating them into planning are essential steps in this process. Sustaining and expanding these practices allows biodiversity goals to take root both in policy frameworks and in the everyday relationships and practices that connect the community to its environment.

1.4. Initial Mapping of Interventions

In our case study, the development of interventions to foster biodiversity restoration was approached in a more grounded manner. Early in the research process, we reviewed national and international dam-removal case studies, scientific literature, media reporting, and expert insights from countries with large-scale ecological restoration practice. Our consultations with international experts experienced in dam removal showed that projects are most successful when they are grounded in local realities and align with how communities think and live. Experts noted that a project should have clear roots in the community and ideally emerge from local perspectives, which was not very strong in this case. Approaches that reflect local values help build genuine participation and more constructive dialogue. Engagement should involve the community and address its recreational, cultural, environmental, and everyday needs, while respecting how people understand the river and their relationship with it. It became clear that any intervention must begin by building trust through credible expertise, strengthening local understanding

through communication that residents find accessible and understandable, and recognising the cultural values and emotional ties people hold toward the existing landscape, including the impounded river. International experience shows that rapid, top-down actions can provoke resistance when they overlook these cultural and historical meanings. While contexts vary, the evidence is consistent: integrating community perspectives alongside environmental and cultural considerations greatly increases the likelihood of achieving successful and lasting ecological restoration, including the removal of barriers that prevent rivers from functioning naturally. We also considered creative community engagement approaches, such as theater-based methods, which have been successfully used by our societal partner (a theater director) in other sensitive social contexts in Lithuania. However, we reflected and concluded that introducing theatrical participatory methods would not be suitable for our context. The case is currently at a stage where relational dialogue and transparent information sharing are essential, providing space for genuine discussion and reflection. Such discussions should be supported by communication grounded in expert knowledge and presented in ways that are accessible and understandable to residents. This includes clear visualizations, models, and environmental impact assessments that are tailored to the local context. It should be transparent what kinds of changes are expected, giving communities the opportunity to express their needs and proposals. At the same time, the process must be honest about the limits of what can be addressed, so expectations remain realistic and participation remains meaningful. Thus, while inspired by more experimental methods, we recognized that the true innovation required here lies in fostering genuine dialogue supported by contextual, technical, and evidence-based information, **along with gradual relational work and a willingness to address community perspectives**. Engagement must reflect a commitment to addressing community needs that could be affected by the project, ensuring that all concerns—ecological, hydrological, public safety-related, cultural, and beyond—are acknowledged and thoughtfully addressed. Our planned interventions focus on continuing and deepening structured conversations. Based on insights gathered so far, we have identified several potential soft interventions that could move beyond business-as-usual conservation approaches. These ideas aim to centre community relationships and emotional connections to the river as the foundation for future biodiversity work:

- **Relational interviews:** continue conducting interviews and informal conversations, offering community members opportunities to share their diverse values, needs, experiences and hopes regarding the river's future. These exchanges can strengthen mutual understanding and help identify shared values and common ground that support collaborative action.
- **Localized information campaigns:** if opportunities arise, we could encourage environmental stakeholders and planners to address community questions—through visual materials, models, or other tools that help make technical information more relatable and meaningful. Such efforts could offer context-specific, evidence-based insights that are easy to understand, for example, illustrating how river water levels could change in the premises of the town.
- **Discussion workshops:** organize workshops where community members can meet in a supportive setting to voice concerns, ask questions, exchange ideas, and collectively explore visions for the river's future. **Supporting local nature ambassadors:** Encourage individuals who already hold strong personal ties to nature (but are not formal environmental activists) to foster peer-to-peer conversations within the community and to advocate for restoration in an inclusive and inspiring way.

These possibilities are not yet formalized. They reflect directions that could be pursued depending on future community interest, readiness, and evolving relational dynamics.

A fundamental innovation in our context is the shift from information delivery to relationship-building. Instead of promoting technical solutions alone, we aim to strengthen the social fabric around the river, recognizing that healthy ecosystems and healthy

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communities must evolve together. Ecological decision-making, in this sense, becomes an opportunity to empower the community by encouraging participation and ensuring access to evidence-based information.

The possible course of action includes:

- **Building a more diverse picture of interests and perspectives** through ongoing interviews and informal conversations.
- **Exploring small participatory actions**—such as collaborative visioning workshops—provided that suitable preconditions are in place.
- **Considering larger public activities** (such as exhibitions, co-design sessions, or consultations), if such actions are deemed appropriate in later stages of the process.

This approach emphasizes responsiveness and co-creation, fostering conditions where ideas and actions can emerge organically from within the community. Rather than prescribing solutions, it seeks to nurture community-driven momentum for river restoration, empowering local actors to shape and lead biodiversity initiatives.

1.5. Discussion

In our case study, exclusion from biodiversity decision-making stems from several factors: communication that does not effectively inform the local community about the need for environmental action, strong values rooted in the cultural landscape, unresolved questions about the changes that environmental action would bring, and limited approaches for involving the community, environmental voices, and even scientific experts in governance processes. Together, these factors reduce the momentum needed for socially robust biodiversity action. Most respondents in the Anykščiai community viewed nature as a core value of their town and expressed genuine care for the nature and the river. Their understanding of biodiversity is shaped through personal relationships with the river and its species. These everyday observations often foster strong stewardship attitudes and, in some cases, align with scientific evidence, though proposed solutions may differ. For example, older residents recalled that fish populations declined after dams were built on the Šventoji River. At the same time, a range of perceptions emerged across the community. While many anglers, especially those engaged in fly fishing, shared views consistent with scientific perspectives, others believed that the reservoir had developed new ecosystems that had adapted to changed conditions. These interpretations reflect real ecological processes, but they do not always align with scientific frameworks for assessing ecological value. People rarely speak in terms of “*ecological degradation*” or “*restoration*.” Instead, they relate to the river through deeply personal and experiential lenses—memories of floods, ice jams, and the dam’s construction; recollections of fish abundance; or everyday experiences such as bathing, fishing, or kayaking. As Fox et al. (2016) observe in their study of dam conflicts in New England, what is often interpreted as resistance is more accurately an expression of place-based identity. The river, even with its dam, becomes intertwined with personal, familial, and collective memory—so that change can feel not like progress, but like loss. This becomes stronger when discussions focus on the idea of “removal” rather than “restoration”. In our interviews, several respondents noted that “it’s easier to destroy than to create,” emphasizing the need for decisions that are careful, well-considered, and respectful of what the community has built over time. Several residents also linked their hesitation to past experiences with poorly planned or rushed decisions that affected the town, which contributed to diminishing trust in public projects. A key challenge concerns the way knowledge is shared and understood. Early proposals for dam removal in Anykščiai did not fully connect with local values or provide site-specific studies, visual projections, or impact assessments that could help residents understand potential changes. Without this information, people relied on their own assumptions, leading some to worry about flooding, bank erosion, fish losses, or reduced recreational access. At the same time, the lived knowledge held by residents — their stories,

observations, and everyday experiences — had no clear channel for contributing to the discussion. These forms of “embodied, historical, and moral knowledges,” as described by Fox et al. (2016), offer important insights that can strengthen planning when they are acknowledged and integrated. Building processes that connect expert assessments with local experience can support clearer understanding, reduce uncertainty, and create a stronger shared basis for decision-making. On the institutional side, we observed willingness to engage but a lack of know-how—particularly at the national level—as well as limited capacity in terms of financial, human, and technical resources to effectively involve communities and to anticipate how such efforts might be perceived locally. National policies are translated to local and regional authorities, and debates are typically conducted through public hearings. However, although these hearings are open to the public, they do not provide the same depth or quality of dialogue as, for example, co-creation workshops. As a result, communities are more often formally *informed about* interventions rather than *involved in* shaping them, leaving them without a true sense of participation or ownership in decisions that directly affect their surroundings. This mirrors the micropolitical dynamics Fox et al. (2016) describe when power is seen as coming from “somewhere else,” even good ideas can feel imposed. A stronger foundation for policy implementation emerges when people feel genuinely included in shaping decisions. When communities have a voice and see their perspectives reflected, they are more willing to support change and more confident in the direction it takes. Recognising local values linked to the landscape strengthens this foundation, helping restoration efforts be understood not as external interventions, but as shared projects rooted in local identity and collective responsibility. By building this sense of participation and belonging, environmental action gains both durability and deeper public commitment. By conducting face-to-face interviews, we sought to create space for discussion and reflection. These conversations showed that community perspectives are deeply rooted in lived experience. People spoke about their direct relationship with the river, demonstrating how strongly the river figures in their daily lives. Many residents swim, kayak, and fish in the Šventoji, and they also pay close attention to its seasonal changes, recalling past floods, ice jams, and shifts in water levels. Their observations reflect substantial local knowledge of how the river behaves. We also identified untapped potential among residents already engaged in forest protection, eco-tourism, nature-based education, angling, and hiking. These activities show a strong existing relationship with the environment that could, with appropriate support, be extended toward greater engagement with river ecosystems. Practical steps such as targeted information sessions, community-led monitoring, or opportunities to share local observations can help strengthen awareness and encourage more integrated thinking about the river and its role in community life. National actors, such as academics and NGOs, contribute valuable scientific knowledge and policy expertise. Their next step, however, may lie in moving from delivering expertise to building local capacity—supporting communities to take the lead, rather than leading on their behalf.

To foster inclusion, we suggest to proceed with these actions:

- **Evidence-Based Communication and Visualisation Tools:** Respondents emphasized the importance of transparent, independent, and factual communication supported by visual tools such as environmental impact assessments and modelled visualisations of potential landscape changes. These instruments were perceived as essential for depoliticising the debate and fostering trust by demonstrating technical aspects of the project and scientific justifications. Respondents noted that technical specialists should address community concerns, including potential ecological changes, changes in hydrological events (e.g., floods and ice jams), changes in water levels in the premises of the town, risks to public safety, alterations to landscape appearance, and effects on infrastructure, wells, upstream and downstream communities, and recreational areas, etc.
- **Co-Creation and Participatory Processes:** The respondents highlighted the value of co-creation workshops and participatory methods as mechanisms for

fostering local ownership of project outcomes. Engaging communities through inclusive dialogue helps address their needs, hopes, and perceptions of the landscape, while recognising and validating their lived experiences. Such collaboration was seen as vital for building new connections between communities and the river, creating shared understandings, and replacing outdated narratives with more constructive, future-oriented relationships. Some members of the communities noted that some of the surrounding buildings and infrastructure can be used for communities' activities.

- **Empowerment of Local Environmental Voices:** Strengthening local environmental representation was identified as a critical factor in ensuring that environmental interests are represented in decision-making processes. This empowerment enhances transparency, inclusivity, and the perceived fairness of environmental governance.

The most meaningful intervention in our case is the creation of space for open discussion and reflection—shifting away from politicized debates aimed at persuading the public. This represents the kind of groundwork on which lasting transformation depends. Inclusion and exclusion in our case stem from limited institutional capacity in time, expertise, funding, and staffing, as well as uneven access to information. Formal procedures, such as public hearings, are an important, yet relying on them alone does not create the kind of engagement needed to build community support. This often leaves residents informed in a procedural sense but not fully involved in shaping decisions. As a result, lived knowledge rooted in observation, memory, and everyday experience is not consistently incorporated into planning. To build a future where biodiversity is genuinely reflected in decisions and embedded in long-term planning, this gap needs to be addressed. Strengthening the connection between scientific guidance and active public involvement can create the support necessary for lasting ecological success. We advocate for real change built on soft innovation together with strong biodiversity leadership. This means bringing together different perspectives, seeking common ground, and giving local communities the power to shape, and, if possible, to lead the future of their town and its river. The path is not simple. Yet within these challenges lies a profound opportunity: to renew the bond between people and the river, to rebuild trust, and to create a future where environmental restoration strengthens both the landscape and the community that depends on it.

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D2.2

High Nature Value Farming

UBB, Romania

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Summary

Summary of Deliverable

The Romanian case study examines how biodiversity conservation can coexist with sustainable rural development in the Sighișoara-Târnava Mare region, one of Romania's largest Natura 2000 areas, covering approximately 85,000 hectares. This landscape boasts remarkable biodiversity, featuring over 1,000 plant species, 55 endangered bird species, and 23 endangered mammal species, including wolves, bears, and wildcats. It also reflects centuries of coexistence between people and nature through traditional farming, grazing, and cultural practices. Today, these high-nature-value farmlands are increasingly threatened by land abandonment, agricultural intensification, depopulation, and economic inequalities that particularly affect marginalized groups such as Roma communities. At the heart of the case study lies the challenge of aligning biodiversity protection with the social and economic realities of rural life. Traditional land management once ensured both ecological and cultural balance, but changes in policy and market structures have weakened these systems. The decline in small-scale farming, the loss of communal herding, and the erosion of traditional knowledge have disrupted ecological processes. At the same time, migration and aging populations have reduced the number of active land stewards. As a result, pastures are overgrown, water resources are drying up, and biodiversity tied to open landscapes is in decline. Research combining participatory workshops (implemented in June 2024) reveals that local people understand nature through relational and emotional experiences rather than technical definitions. They value the landscape for its beauty, productivity, and significance, seeing it as an integral part of their identity. However, their knowledge and perspectives are often excluded from decision-making dominated by top-down policies. Building inclusive governance requires revaluing traditional ecological knowledge and fostering cooperation among farmers, scientists, NGOs, and policymakers. Several community-led innovations demonstrate potential for transformative change. Efforts to restore hay meadows, protect native species, revive orchards, and reintroduce buffalo grazing have not only enhanced biodiversity but also strengthened local identity and tourism. Education, shared learning networks, and environmental awareness initiatives are proving effective in engaging both adults and children. Yet, obstacles such as climate change, weak policy enforcement, and short-term economic pressures continue to hinder progress. The case study shows that enduring biodiversity regeneration depends not only on ecological restoration but also on revitalizing the human communities that care for nature. Sustainable transformation emerges where conservation supports local livelihoods, respects cultural traditions, and empowers people to act collectively. In these Transylvanian villages, human resilience and ecological renewal are inseparable foundations for a sustainable future.

Transformative Biodiversity Innovations (D2.2)

1.1 Analysis of Inclusion/Exclusion Mechanisms

Exclusionary practices that marginalize perspectives often influence biodiversity discussions and decision-making processes. These exclusionary practices are shaped by embodied values, social attitudes, flows of knowledge, and economic structures that prioritize epistemologies over others. By excluding diverse perspectives, particularly those of local communities, biodiversity policies risk being ineffective and disconnected from the realities on the ground.

Embodied values and social attitudes play a significant role in determining who participates in biodiversity governance. Historically, scientific knowledge produced in academic institutions was privileged over traditional ecological knowledge (TEK), systematically excluding local communities. As one participant in the workshop noted, "When I think about nature (...), it's a place where I don't see anything cultivated, just meadows or forests, without any kind of crops" (Participant_Biertan). This highlights the disconnect between academic ecological studies and the lived experiences of local communities. Despite their extensive knowledge of local ecosystems, many traditional land users find their insights undervalued in policymaking.

Additionally, there is a perception that local rural people's ways of knowing are outdated and unsuitable for modern conservation efforts. This perception reinforces the exclusion of communities that have co-evolved with their environments over centuries "If we have biodiversity, it means that we have been quite sustainable so far" (Participant_Biertan). This perspective highlights the depth of traditional knowledge, yet conservation efforts often impose externally designed frameworks that fail to incorporate these localized understandings. A participant from Biertan emphasized how exclusion is frequently unintentional but still present: "We cannot promote tourism at all if what we promote is not embraced by the community. Because it will not be sustainable, it will just be a trend, and that is why everything we discuss is important" (Participant_Biertan). This highlights the importance of local voices in conservation planning for long-term success.

Furthermore, local perceptions of nature are deeply embedded in cultural identity. In Saschiz, a participant emphasized the connection between water and heritage: "For me now, it means water. Water as a resource for food, drinking water, household water, water for animals" (Participant_Saschiz). This demonstrates how communities perceive nature not as an abstract ecological concept but as an integral part of their daily survival and culture.

Flows of knowledge and marginalization. Knowledge production and dissemination are also political processes. Scientific research is often conducted in ways that exclude or fail to engage with local perspectives. When biodiversity policies are formulated without meaningful consultation, they risk alienating those who have the most at stake. Often, policies are imposed without consideration of local contexts, resulting in confusion and resistance among the affected populations. In many cases, decision-makers assume that scientific assessments alone provide an objective basis for policy, overlooking the experiences of those who interact with the environment on a daily basis. Access to information is often unevenly distributed. Rural communities frequently lack the necessary resources to participate in decision-making, leaving them vulnerable to exclusion. One participant noted: "Local communities are not well informed about legislation and do not comply with it. Everyone is minding their own business" (Participant_Biertan). This lack of inclusion reinforces power imbalances, as only those with the means and knowledge to navigate bureaucratic systems can influence policies. Moreover, as one participant from Saschiz pointed out, the decline in traditional knowledge directly impacts the management of natural resources: "Thirty years ago, we used to bathe in the valley, but now there's barely any water flowing" (Participant_Saschiz). This illustrates how ecological degradation is a consequence of environmental factors and the sidelining of traditional management

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practices. Another voice from Biertan shared concerns about the decline of traditional ecological knowledge: "I remember when I moved [...], I was super impressed by all the biodiversity, by the flora [...]" (Participant_Biertan). This highlights how knowledge is lost when communities are excluded from biodiversity governance.

Economic practices and systemic exclusion: Economic structures reinforce exclusion in biodiversity discussions. Many local communities rely on subsistence agriculture, small-scale farming, or pastoralism – practices that are often marginalized in broader economic policies. "Small farmers... They have the most to lose. First, they have nowhere to sell their products because of our policies... I saw on TV just now that those who grew tomatoes are throwing them away, they can't even sell them for 80 bani" (Participant_Biertan). This reflects how economic marginalization leads to both financial insecurity and political disenfranchisement. Economic incentives and funding mechanisms also favor large-scale conservation initiatives that prioritize tourism or industrialized resource management over community-based solutions. This contributes to the displacement of traditional livelihoods and disrupts existing relationships between humans and nature. This demonstrates how external economic pressures reshape rural landscapes in ways that disadvantage those most reliant on the land. When traditional livelihoods are not considered in biodiversity policies, rural communities struggle to balance conservation requirements with their economic survival. A participant from Saschiz explained how industrialized farming practices are replacing traditional crop rotation systems, which affects soil health: "For twenty years, my father-in-law has only planted corn on the same plot" (Participant_Saschiz). This demonstrates how modern agricultural practices, often encouraged by economic policies, undermine the ecological knowledge embedded in traditional farming techniques.

Power dynamics in biodiversity decision-making: Power imbalances are embedded in biodiversity governance. Government agencies, NGOs, and academic institutions often dominate conservation narratives, bypassing local voices. When policies are formulated without input from those directly affected, they risk alienating communities and getting resistance rather than cooperation. Additionally, conservation initiatives prioritize scientific assessments over local experience, reinforcing an epistemological hierarchy marginalizing TEK. This creates a dynamic in which local communities are expected to conform to external conservation models rather than co-developing solutions that align with their lived realities. As one participant noted, the role of local knowledge is often ignored despite its long history of effectiveness: "Our pastures used to be properly maintained, but now no one takes care of them" (Participant_Saschiz). This erosion of local land management practices highlights the consequences of exclusionary governance.

Inclusive mechanisms

Inclusive mechanisms for biodiversity conservation: Various mechanisms can be implemented to foster inclusion and empower marginalized groups to counteract these exclusionary practices.

a) Strengthening participatory governance

One of the most effective ways to promote inclusion is through participatory governance. This involves engaging local communities in decision-making processes. Community-led conservation initiatives and co-management agreements can help bridge the gap between scientific and local knowledge. This is also reflected in the implemented interview guide, where we used "nature" instead of "biodiversity", as per the local community's position. This highlights the need for conservation discourse to be adapted to local understandings of nature, ensuring inclusivity.

b) Recognizing and valuing traditional knowledge

Policies should formally recognize and integrate traditional ecological knowledge as a legitimate form of expertise. This can be achieved through legal frameworks that protect local land rights, funding for community-led research, and platforms for knowledge exchange. One participant in Saschiz discussed how traditional knowledge, especially related to water management, has been overlooked: “In our area, it was, you know, it was very important, being a Saxon area, that almost all houses, all households had a well in the yard.” (Participant_Saschiz). Biodiversity governance can benefit from centuries of accumulated wisdom by restoring and incorporating such traditional ecological practices.

c) Supporting sustainable local livelihoods

Ensuring that biodiversity policies align with the economic needs of local communities is important for their success. Many rural populations rely on traditional agricultural practices that should be recognized and supported within conservation frameworks. One participant from Saschiz emphasized the importance of sustainable land use: “Mowing is a bit mechanized [...] a lot now, because no one mows traditionally anymore [...]” (Participant_Saschiz). This shift from traditional practices highlights the need for conservation programs to support the continuation of sustainable land management techniques.

d) Creating platforms for community engagement

Inclusive conservation requires spaces where local voices can be heard and actively participate in decision-making. As another participant in Saschiz pointed out, knowledge-sharing is a crucial part of conservation efforts: “Elderberry, for example, at grandma’s cellar, local elderberry...” (Participant_Saschiz). This illustrates how local ecological knowledge is embedded in daily life and should be preserved as an integral part of conservation strategies.

By embracing local perspectives and prioritizing inclusive mechanisms, biodiversity governance can become more effective, equitable, and sustainable in the long run.

1.2 Niche Innovators and Key Players

Biodiversity conservation within the case study areas of Malancrav, Boiu, and Saschiz is driven by a variety of niche innovators and key players who can contribute to transformative change. These include traditional knowledge holders, community members engaged in sustainable practices, conservation-oriented organizations, and individuals maintaining traditional ecological relationships with the landscape.

Traditional knowledge holders and local experts

Traditional knowledge holders are one of the most valuable yet often overlooked groups driving biodiversity conservation. In Malancrav, older community members hold extensive knowledge about local flora and fauna, including medicinal plants and sustainable land management. One participant recounted: “When I got married in the ‘80s, in Malancrav, there was Lele Dobriță, I know she knew, as there were two or three Roma families. And there were the elders who knew all kinds of... and my mother-in-law, being a vegetarian, would bring her mushrooms of all colors, but she never got sick. She knew the place, the timing, and everything” (Participant_Malancrav). This highlights the role of traditional foragers in maintaining biodiversity through careful selection and sustainable harvesting of forest resources. Similarly, in Boiu, local knowledge about natural cycles and the use of organic materials remains deeply ingrained in community practices. “In the local pharmacopeia, I believe around 10-15 plants are regularly collected. From the wild flora, people also cultivate aromatic or condiment plants, which also have medicinal values” (Participant_Boiu). These individuals play an important role in maintaining knowledge continuity about medicinal plants and sustainable harvesting methods. Their expertise

ensures that plant populations are not overharvested, directly contributing to biodiversity preservation.

Small-scale farmers and pastoralists

Traditional agricultural and pastoralist practices are crucial in maintaining biodiversity, particularly in areas where intensive monoculture has not yet become the dominant practice. In Saschiz, rotational grazing and small-scale farming remain prevalent, as one participant explained: "Pastures should be maintained by those receiving subsidies, as almost all pastures are allocated to farmers. In the past, when there weren't large farmers and big herds, everyone had a small flock or two or three sheep. Just enough to have a lamb for Easter [...]" (Participant_Saschiz). These practices help sustain soil health, promote biodiversity, and prevent overgrazing. Some small farmers also practice intercropping and rotation to maintain soil fertility and increase yield diversity. "My father-in-law has planted corn on the same plot for twenty years. This isn't sustainable, and we should return to rotational farming like our grandparents did" (Participant_Saschiz). This suggests that while some traditional farming methods are being phased out, a strong knowledge base and advocacy for their revival remain.

Local conservation enthusiasts and citizen scientists

Citizens, scientists and individuals dedicated to monitoring biodiversity play a crucial role in environmental protection. In Saschiz, one participant shared their experience of observing biodiversity changes: "I was looking at my phone. This was a researcher saying that the coolest beech forest is here. And we have important beech forests. And they are beautiful, as he was also saying they are beautiful" (Participant_Saschiz). This interest in local biodiversity, combined with the use of technological tools, supports conservation efforts by documenting changes in forest composition and species presence. Community members also observe changes in animal populations: "There are more deer every year. I think they are doing well here" (Participant_Saschiz). Such firsthand knowledge can complement scientific studies and improve conservation strategies.

The Influence of niche innovators and key players

Despite their contributions, many niche innovators face challenges in gaining formal recognition for their knowledge and efforts. Traditional knowledge holders are often marginalized in official conservation discussions. "I was telling them today at the workshop about what a tragedy it was when the mushroom collectors passed away. In one year, both were gone. And with them, the knowledge was lost." (Participant_Saschiz). The loss of local biodiversity experts leads to gaps in sustainable harvesting practices and knowledge transmission. In some cases, small farmers are also voiceless due to policies favoring large-scale agricultural enterprises. A participant from Boiu explained: "All the forests in the area are either recently planted, especially coniferous forests on Țopa and here on the hill behind, or forests under exploitation - traditional system, but through the forestry office, which requires partial exploitation, so no clear-cutting" (Participant_Boiu). While intended for conservation, these policies sometimes overlook the role of local farming systems in preserving biodiversity.

Expanding the recognition of local knowledge: To ensure sustainable conservation efforts, bridging the gap between traditional knowledge and formal conservation science is necessary. "It is important to have someone who knows what to collect and whom people trust" (Participant_Malanrav). Recognizing and integrating this knowledge into official conservation frameworks can lead to more effective and locally accepted biodiversity protection strategies.

Involvement of Niche Innovators

Efforts have been made to integrate niche innovators into biodiversity conservation through knowledge-sharing initiatives, collaborative projects, and participatory conservation programs.

Community engagement and knowledge exchange: One way of fostering biodiversity conservation is through active knowledge exchange. As one participant in Saschiz explained: "In the past, there were many more - they used to call the buffalo 'balanele', which is quite ironic. And now there are only a few left" (Participant_Saschiz). This suggests that even as traditional knowledge and livestock practices decline, efforts to sustain them can reinforce conservation. Additionally, community members in Saschiz discussed how traditional knowledge regarding water management has been largely forgotten: "Thirty years ago, we used to bathe in the valley, but now there's barely any water flowing" (Participant_Saschiz). This loss of traditional ecological awareness highlights the importance of documenting and preserving such knowledge.

Collaborative conservation initiatives: In Boiu, initiatives to protect biodiversity include structured management of forest resources and controlled exploitation: "Timber exploitation. All the forests in the area are either recently planted, especially conifers on Țopa and here on the hill behind, or forests under exploitation - traditional system, but through the forestry office" (Participant_Boiu). These community-involved projects help ensure that conservation efforts are balanced with economic needs.

Formalizing traditional knowledge: In Malancrav, discussions are underway to integrate local expertise into conservation. As one participant noted, "It is important to have someone who knows what to collect and in whom people trust" (Participant_Malancrav). This suggests a potential pathway for formalizing local ecological knowledge within broader conservation frameworks.

Expanding the role of technology in conservation: Digital technology and social media platforms offer opportunities for niche innovators to document and share their knowledge. Mobile applications for identifying plant species, recording wildlife sightings, and mapping ecological changes provide community members with the tools to participate actively in conservation efforts. For example, in Saschiz, individuals who monitor biodiversity and share their findings contribute valuable insights into local ecological trends.

Encouraging community-based ecotourism: Ecotourism presents an opportunity to integrate local knowledge holders into conservation-based economic models. Tourists are often drawn to authentic cultural and natural experiences, incentivizing communities to preserve traditional practices and natural landscapes. In Saschiz, a participant highlighted the importance of local tourism: "We have an area for promenades there. Everyone goes to see the bear. In the evening, the bear comes out, and people take pictures" (Participant_Saschiz). This demonstrates how the presence of wildlife can support ecotourism, benefiting both conservation and local livelihoods.

The biodiversity conservation landscape in Malancrav, Boiu, and Saschiz is shaped by numerous key players, including traditional knowledge holders, citizen scientists, and small-scale farmers. While these individuals and groups play a crucial role in maintaining ecological balance, they often face marginalization and exclusion. Recognizing and integrating their expertise into formal conservation efforts is essential for creating inclusive and sustainable biodiversity policies. Expanding community-based conservation approaches and fostering economic incentives that align with ecological sustainability can further strengthen biodiversity protection in these regions.

1.3 Scalable Bottom-Up Innovations for Transformative Change

Identification of existing innovations

APOLD village

Bottom-up innovations for biodiversity conservation often emerge from local knowledge, traditional practices, and community-led initiatives. The workshop in Apold revealed various innovative approaches that support biodiversity at the local level, distinguishing them from conventional top-down policies.

One significant bottom-up innovation is the identification and conservation of native species, such as the Albăstrelul Transilvan (Latin name: *Pseudophilotes bavius hungaricus*, Figure 1). This butterfly species has also been preserved through local ecological efforts. This initiative represents a transformative approach as it recognizes the value of native species in fostering biodiversity and attracting eco-tourism: "... o să vină mulți turiști să îl vadă (fluturele)." (Participant_Apold)

Figure 1 *Albăstrelul transilvan* Source: EuropaFM, 2024.

Another notable initiative is the protection of ancient trees such as secular oaks (*stejarii seculari*). These trees are considered more than just natural resources; they hold identity and intrinsic value for the community: "Secularii, pentru noi... nu merita costurile ca să îl tai, pentru că... ce faci cu el? El e un monument al naturii. Te bucuri de el"/ "Secular trees, for us... it wasn't worth the cost to cut it down, because... what do you do with it? It's a monument of nature. You enjoy it." (Participant_Apold) working for Romsilva). This perspective reflects a shift from economic exploitation to conservation-driven thinking.

BIERTAN village

Biodiversity conservation efforts in Biertan are deeply rooted in the community's traditional knowledge and local practices, which differentiate them from conventional business-as-usual policies. These bottom-up innovations focus on sustainable land use, the protection of native species, and traditional ecological practices that have been preserved over time.

A significant innovation highlighted in the discussion is the conservation of traditional vineyards and terraces, which are essential in maintaining local biodiversity: "Dealul acesta unde a fost vița de vie a fost foarte important. Acuma nefiind exploatate, și-au mai pierdut... dar în continuare au o importanță din punct de vedere al esteticii"/ "This hill where the vines were was very important. Now that they are not exploited, they have lost

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some of their... but they still have an importance from an aesthetic point of view"/ "(Participant_Biertan). Although not actively cultivated on the same scale as before, these terraces continue to contribute to landscape biodiversity and serve as historical and ecological landmarks.

Protecting water sources such as the Biertan River is another innovative effort. The community recognizes the river's declining water levels and its ecological importance: "Are un debit foarte scăzut cel puțin... comparativ cu acum 20 de ani chiar... Semnificativ de mic."/ It has a very low flow rate, at least... compared to 20 years ago even... Significantly low." (Participant_Biertan). This awareness has led to community discussions on ways to protect and possibly restore the water body's ecosystem.

Another transformative practice is the traditional maintenance of grasslands and meadows, which supports high biodiversity. Community members emphasize their importance: "Tot ce ține de câmpii, de unde se cultivă porumb, fânețe, pajiștile."/ Everything related to the fields, where corn is grown, hayfields, meadows" (Participant_Biertan).

BOIU village

In Boiu, several bottom-up innovations promote biodiversity at the local level, differentiating them from conventional business-as-usual policies. These innovations rely on traditional knowledge, sustainable land use, and ecological practices that have been preserved over generations.

One notable innovation is the local use of construction materials derived from natural resources. As a participant noted, "Aici s-a folosit întotdeauna piatra de construcție locală". /" Local building stone has always been used here." (Participant_Boiu). This practice ensures that the local environment is not excessively altered by imported materials, preserving the ecological balance.

Another key innovation is the careful management of forest resources: "Pădurea e o resursă foarte importantă și gestionată cu multă atenție de localnici". / "The forest is a very important resource and is managed with great care by the locals." (Participant_Boiu). This approach contrasts with mainstream logging practices that prioritize profit over sustainability.

Additionally, using organic fertilizers such as manure has been an integral part of traditional agriculture: "Și bălegarul că noi l-am folosit."/ "And the manure that we used" (Participant_Boiu). This practice naturally enriches soil quality, reducing dependency on synthetic fertilizers that can hurt biodiversity.

A unique biodiversity-supporting feature in Boiu is the community's relationship with local stork populations: "Că oamenii le iubesc. Deja sunt repere pentru noi, la cuibul la stația de autobuz, deci mai mult de atât [...]" / "Because people love them. They are already landmarks for us, at the nest at the bus station, so more than that [...]" (Participant_Boiu). Storks are not just birds, but also symbols of local ecological health, demonstrating how biodiversity is intricately intertwined with community identity.

MALNCRAV village

In Mălâncrav, several bottom-up innovations have emerged to promote biodiversity at the local level, setting them apart from conventional business-as-usual policies. These innovations are deeply rooted in traditional practices, community knowledge, and sustainable land use, making them transformative.

One such innovation is the revival of traditional orchards: "Livada pot să zic că valoare de identitate. Avem și sărbătoarea mărului". / "I can say that the orchard has an identity value. We also have the apple festival." (Participant_Malancrav). This event, centered

around the apple orchards, reflects how agriculture and biodiversity coexist while fostering local identity and economy.

Another key initiative is the creation of small ponds (heleșteein Ro language), which were initially developed for practical reasons but have since become essential biodiversity hotspots: "Acum 20 de ani era unul singur în partea de sus a satului". / "20 years ago, there was one alone at the top of the village". (Participant_Malancrav). Over time, these small water bodies have expanded, benefiting local wildlife and community members who use them for recreation, irrigation, and livestock watering.

SASCHIZ village

Several bottom-up innovations have been identified in Saschiz that promote biodiversity at the local level. These innovations are rooted in traditional land-use practices, water conservation, and the sustainable management of forests and meadows.

One notable innovation is the importance of water conservation. Community members emphasized: "Apa ca și resursă pentru hrană, apă de băut, apă menajeră, apă de adăpat animale." / "Water as a resource for food, drinking water, household water, water for watering animals." Water shortages have become a pressing issue, with some participants recalling: "Noi acum 30 de ani făceam baie în vale, dar acum nu mai putem că aproape nu mai curge." / "30 years ago, we used to bathe in the valley, but now we can't because it almost doesn't flow anymore". (Participant_Saschiz). This has led to efforts to restore traditional water sources such as wells and fountains.

Another significant innovation is the revival of traditional meadow management. Participants stressed the value of pajiști (meadows) and păduri (forests): "Pajiștile ar fi. Pădurea e foarte importantă." / "The meadows would be. The forest is very important". (Participant_Saschiz). Traditional haymaking (cosit) and rotational grazing are still practiced, although increasingly mechanized: "Acuma...Cositul e un pic mecanizat [...] foarte mult acuma, că nu mai prea cosește nimeni tradițional." / "Now [...] Mowing is a bit mechanized [...] a lot now, because no one really mows traditionally anymore." (Participant_Saschiz). This nature-positive approach differs from mainstream intensive agriculture, prioritizing yield over biodiversity.

Additionally, biodiversity-friendly farming practices remain a key component of local agriculture. Some community members lament the overuse of monocultures: "Peste tot porumb. Și, după părerea mea, un pic exagerat." / "Corn everywhere. And, in my opinion, a bit overdone." (Participant_Saschiz). Others highlight the importance of crop rotation: "Păi așa am învățat la școală...La școală așa am învățat că rotația culturilor e bună." / "Well, that's what I learned at school...That's what I learned at school that crop rotation is good" (Participant_Saschiz)

Another innovation lies in wildlife protection and ecotourism, particularly on deer, wild boars, and large carnivores. While conflicts with wildlife exist, some community members acknowledge the touristic appeal of seeing bears in their natural habitat: "Toată lumea merge să vadă ursul. Seara iese ursul, fac poze". / "Everyone goes to see the bear. In the evening, the bear comes out, and they take pictures" (Participant_Saschiz).

SOARD village

In Soard, various bottom-up innovations have been implemented to sustain biodiversity at the local level. These practices are rooted in traditional knowledge, sustainable land use, and natural resource management, differing from conventional business-as-usual approaches.

One such innovation is recognizing and conserving natural water sources: "Apa e un element destul de important pentru noi". / "Water is a pretty important element for us".

(Participant_Soard). Traditional wells and small water bodies have been preserved, and their importance is well understood: "Sunt bălți din astea mici temporare pe pășune, joacă un rol important pentru menținerea bivoliilor și a vacile." / "There are these little temporary ponds in the pastures, that are important for buffalo and cows' existence" (Participant_Soard).

Another important innovation is the conservation of pasturelands and their integration with traditional farming practices. Participants noted that some pastures are naturally rewilding due to abandonment: "Aici chiar vedem pe deal o pășune care probabil în primii 15 ani de abandon și împădurire nu mai revine la starea aia de pășune inițială" / "Here we see a pasture on the hill that probably in the first 15 years of abandonment and afforestation will not return to its original pasture state" (Participant_Soard). This highlights the importance of actively maintaining these habitats to sustain biodiversity.

Additionally, sustainable forestry practices have been increasingly recognized: "Regenerarea naturală, normal, cum să nu. E un proces al naturii." / "Natural regeneration, normal, of course. It's a process of nature" (Participant_Soard). This stands in contrast to mainstream forestry approaches, which often rely on intensive extraction without allowing time for regeneration.

A significant biodiversity-supporting practice is the protection of mature and dead trees as habitats: "Păi în mare majoritate, deci sunt habitatele marginale - arborii pentru biodiversitate și arborii morți." / "Well, for the most part, so it's the marginal habitats - the biodiversity trees and the dead trees." (Participant_Soard) Instead of removing them for timber, community members recognize their value for local wildlife.

Evaluating transformative potential and equity in access

APOLD village

These innovations demonstrate a nature-positive approach by integrating biodiversity conservation with cultural and ecological resilience. The conservation of species like Albăstrelul Transilvan and the protection of secular oaks illustrate a deeper recognition of biodiversity as an integral part of community identity rather than just a resource for exploitation. However, access to these innovations remains inequitable, especially for marginalized groups such as small-scale farmers and ethnic minorities. The transcript highlights concerns that some community members are unable to leverage biodiversity-friendly practices due to economic constraints: "Nu au unde să își vândă produsele în primul rând, că în politica noastră [...]" [They have nowhere to sell their products in the first place, given our policies [...]] (Participant_Apold).

Additionally, biodiversity innovations should integrate cultural and knowledge diversity. The workshop participants noted that certain traditional practices, such as medicinal plant use, have been undervalued: "Ce mai poate da valoare de identitate la plante sunt cunoștințele locale care folosesc aceste plante." [The local knowledge that uses these plants gives them their identity value.] Preserving these traditional ecological knowledge systems ensures that bottom-up innovations remain inclusive and effective.

BIERTAN village

These community-led innovations have strong transformative potential because they integrate biodiversity conservation with cultural heritage and traditional land-use knowledge. They differ from mainstream conservation efforts, which often rely on rigid policies that may not consider local socio-economic contexts. The community acknowledges that its biodiversity has been preserved precisely because traditional land-use practices have not been abandoned: "Dacă avem biodiversitatea, înseamnă că am fost destul de sustenabili până acum." ["If we have biodiversity, it means that we have been quite sustainable so far."] (Participant_Biertan)

However, access to these innovations is not always equitable. Some community members face economic constraints that make it challenging for them to engage in biodiversity-friendly practices. As one participant noted: "Nu mai au animale oamenii, ce mai sunt fermieri?" [People no longer have animals, so what kind of farmers are there?] (Participant_Biertan). The decline in traditional farming and pasture maintenance is linked to the migration of younger generations to urban areas, resulting in a decrease in the number of active land stewards. Despite this, biodiversity efforts remain closely tied to cultural and knowledge diversity. The community values both historical and ecological aspects of its landscapes: "Pentru că multă lume vine și întreabă 'Wow, dar ce-i cu dealurile acestea?'" [Because many people come and ask, "Wow, what's up with these hills?"] (Participant_Biertan). Recognizing local landscapes as heritage sites suggests that conservation efforts are closely tied to cultural identity and rural livelihoods.

BOIU village

These biodiversity innovations hold strong transformative potential because they prioritize coexistence with nature rather than exploitation. Unlike industrialized agriculture, which often prioritizes yield over ecological stability, Boiu's traditional farming practices maintain biodiversity: "Tot ce ține de câmpii, de unde se cultivă porumb, fânețe, pajiștile." [Everything about the fields, where corn, hay, and meadows are cultivated.] (Participant_Boiu).

However, access to these practices is not always equitable. Some community members face barriers due to economic challenges or regulatory constraints. For instance, traditional livestock grazing has been restricted by legal changes: "Ni s-a spus că nu au ce căuta animalele pe drum județean. E interzis prin lege." [We were told that animals have no business on the county road. It's prohibited by law.] (Participant_Boiu). This demonstrates a clash between traditional sustainable practices and modern regulations. Additionally, the integration of biodiversity conservation with cultural traditions is evident in events like the folkloric festivals and seasonal celebrations: "Serbările, sănzienele, sărbătoarea culesului..." [The celebrations, the Sânzienele, the harvest festival...] (Participant_Boiu). These festivals highlight how biodiversity-friendly practices can align with cultural heritage, strengthening ecological and social resilience.

MALANCRAV village

These community-led innovations hold strong transformative potential by integrating sustainability with cultural and ecological resilience. Unlike top-down conservation efforts, these practices are shaped by local knowledge and traditions. The revival of orchards, for example, preserves traditional agricultural landscapes while promoting biodiversity. However, access to these innovations is not always equitable. Economic barriers and modern land use regulations limit some community members from engaging in sustainable practices. For example, traditional grazing is restricted by new policies: "Ni s-a spus că nu au ce căuta animalele pe drum județean. E interzis prin lege." [We were told that animals are not allowed on the county road. It's prohibited by law.] (Participant_Malancrav). This presents challenges to maintaining traditional biodiversity-friendly farming practices.

Furthermore, these biodiversity innovations are closely integrated with cultural traditions. For example, seasonal celebrations and folklore events reinforce the importance of nature: "Serbările, sănzienele, sărbătoarea culesului..." [The celebrations, the Sânzienele, the harvest festival...] (Participant_Malancrav).

This demonstrates that conservation efforts in Mălâncrav are focused on protecting species and preserving both cultural identity and local ecological knowledge.

SASCHIZ village

These biodiversity-friendly innovations have strong transformative potential as they integrate sustainability with cultural heritage and rural traditions. Unlike industrial agriculture or large-scale forestry, these local practices foster long-term environmental resilience. However, access to these innovations is not always equitable. Some community members struggle due to economic challenges and modern regulations restricting traditional practices. These limitations challenge the viability of small-scale farmers in adopting biodiversity-friendly methods. These innovations are also deeply integrated with cultural traditions and local knowledge systems. Events such as “sărbătoarea rabarbarului” (The Rhubarb Festival) and other community-driven celebrations highlight how biodiversity is recognized and celebrated as part of local identity.

SOARD village

These biodiversity friendly innovations have strong transformative potential because they integrate environmental conservation with traditional land-use practices. Unlike intensive agriculture or deforestation, these community-led practices help maintain long-term ecological stability. One challenge is land ownership disputes, which sometimes hinder conservation efforts. A local example of such a conflict is: “Pentru o baltă s-au certat o viață întreagă și... Pai a cui e. Nu era a lui nimeni, nici a lui ăsta, nici a lui ăla. El vrea să fie a lui, ăla a lui, și au murit amândoi și balta a rămas aici.” [They argued over a pond for a lifetime, and... Well, whose is it? It belonged to nobody, neither to this one nor to that one. One wanted it to be his, the other wanted it to be his, and both died, and the pond remained here.] (Participant_Soard). Cultural and traditional practices remain deeply intertwined with biodiversity conservation. Seasonal celebrations, like “carnaval al sânzienelor” [the carnival of the Sânzienne], reinforce local identity while promoting nature appreciation.

Social networks and stakeholders in biodiversity innovations

APOLD village

Biodiversity conservation in Apold is shaped by a web of relationships among farmers, researchers, conservationists, and community members. Local farmers play a central role, adopting biodiversity-friendly agricultural practices often supported through agri-environmental schemes such as APIA: “APIA are și programul de agromediu... te ajută cu niște bani – domnule, nu coseșc până în data de 15...” [APIA also has the agromedium program... it helps you with some money – sir, I don’t harvest until the 15th...]. Researchers and environmentalists contribute scientific expertise, as illustrated by one initiative introducing the Albăstrelul Transilvan: “Dom’ profesor a adus șase exemplare și le-a pus pe movile.” [The professor brought six specimens and placed them on the mounds.]

Community members, meanwhile, sustain biodiversity through everyday land stewardship and traditional ecological knowledge. Yet, social change has weakened this continuity: “Tineretul e plecat, muncesc pe ogoarele altora...” [The youth are gone; they work on someone else’s fields...]. Public authorities influence conservation through regulation but often face implementation challenges. As one participant noted, “Comunitățile locale nu prea sunt informate de legislație și nu prea respectă.” [Local communities are not very informed about the legislation and do not really comply.]

The relationships among these actors determine how information and resources circulate. Limited collaboration between policymakers and practitioners often results in ineffective implementation and local frustration: “Noi aici încercăm 3 fluturi să-i salvăm și 4 capre negre. Nu le va merge.” [Here we try to save three butterflies and four black goats. It won’t work out.]

BIERTAN village

In Biertan, biodiversity conservation relies on interactions between community members, farmers, researchers, and policymakers. Farmers and landowners manage the fields and pastures that form the ecological backbone of the area, while researchers document and support traditional conservation methods. Elders preserve local ecological knowledge, recalling times when "Bătrânii chiar respectau natura. Nu săpau, nu interveneau." [The elders truly respected nature. They did not dig, nor did they intervene.]

Public officials and policymakers shape the regulatory framework but often remain disconnected from local realities. Tourism and cultural organizations have emerged as new actors, promoting eco-tourism and linking heritage conservation with biodiversity goals. Despite strong local commitment, institutional support is inconsistent, and gaps in communication persist: "Comunitățile locale nu prea sunt informate de legislație și nu prea respectă." This disconnection highlights the need for stronger coordination between local actors and decision-makers to sustain and scale up conservation practices.

BOIU village

In Boiu, biodiversity conservation depends on collaboration among farmers, shepherds, foresters, local officials, and environmental advocates. Farmers and shepherds maintain traditional land use and grazing systems that support biodiversity, while foresters and woodworkers engage in sustainable resource management. Community elders act as custodians of ecological memory, but their influence is waning as younger generations move away. Public authorities are responsible for implementing environmental regulations, which sometimes create unintended obstacles to traditional practices. Tourism and cultural advocates promote eco-tourism, though development pressures are increasing: "Oamenii se duc și își fac cabanele lângă pădure." [People go and build their cabins near the forest.]

Overall, information and resource exchange among stakeholders remains limited. Bureaucratic constraints often restrict rather than enable biodiversity-friendly practices, forcing villagers to navigate complex legal barriers despite their ecological commitment.

MĂLÂNCRAV village

In Mălâncrav, conservation efforts are anchored in a dynamic network of farmers, shepherds, foresters, elders, public authorities, and tourism actors. Farmers and foresters maintain practices that reflect long-standing traditions of sustainable land use, while elders pass on knowledge about ecological rhythms and land management. However, state regulations sometimes conflict with these local practices, constraining innovation.

Community engagement remains strong, yet bureaucratic barriers disrupt traditional systems, as reflected in the remark: "Nu mai au animale oamenii." [People no longer have animals.] Such challenges underscore the need for policy adjustments that align formal conservation frameworks with community-based approaches.

SASCHIZ village

In Saschiz, biodiversity conservation is the result of the interaction among community members, local authorities, environmental organizations, and economic actors. Farmers and shepherds sustain pastures through haymaking and grazing, while elders preserve ecological knowledge related to plant collection and water management. Public authorities regulate land use but sometimes impose measures that contradict traditional conservation practices. Ecotourism and cultural initiatives foster awareness of local biodiversity, yet institutional support remains inconsistent.

As one participant observed, "Comunitățile locale nu prea sunt informate de legislație și nu prea respectă." [Local communities are not very informed about the legislation and do not really comply.] The statement reflects a broader need to strengthen collaboration and communication between policymakers and local communities, thereby reconciling policy goals with the lived realities of rural communities.

ȘOARD village

Biodiversity conservation in Șoard depends on cooperation among farmers, shepherds, elders, public authorities, and conservationists. Farmers and shepherds shape local biodiversity through their land management practices, while elders transmit knowledge of sustainable practices, such as rotational grazing. Public authorities and forestry officials play regulatory roles, yet these often conflict with traditional land uses. Despite high local awareness, the lack of adequate compensation for conservation discourages participation: "Acum sunt destul de receptivi... Ca aici nu apare nici o compensare încă dată pentru acei arbori." [Now they are quite receptive... but there is still no compensation yet for those trees.]

These tensions highlight the broader challenge of aligning community engagement with policy mechanisms that can effectively sustain biodiversity in practice.

Diachronic analysis: Change over time

Biodiversity conservation is an evolving process shaped by social, economic, and environmental factors. This diachronic analysis examines changes in participation, involvement, conflicts, and challenges in biodiversity conservation across Apold, Biertan, Boiu, Mălâncrav, Saschiz, and Șoard. By assessing past practices, current constraints, and future potential, we identify key trends affecting the sustainability of biodiversity efforts.

Participation & involvement

Historical (traditional practices): Historically, biodiversity conservation was deeply ingrained within these communities. Traditional land management techniques, such as sustainable grazing, organic farming, and resource sharing, have balanced human activity and ecological stability. Elders followed nature-friendly practices: "Bătrânii chiar respectau natura. Nu săpau, nu interveneau [...]" [The elders truly respected nature. They did not dig, nor did they intervene [...]. Similar sentiments were echoed in Biertan, Boiu, and Saschiz, where local communities viewed land stewardship as a responsibility rather than an economic asset.

Present (modern constraints and transitions): Economic pressures, urban migration, and modernization have led to a decline in traditional biodiversity conservation practices. Many younger residents have left rural areas, resulting in reduced engagement in farming and conservation. As one participant in Biertan noted: "Cine a putut a plecat... nu a mai fost interes." [Whoever could, left... there was no more interest.] Similarly, Apold has witnessed decreased participation due to economic hardships: "Noi nu mai avem zăpadă. Seceta nu a început vara..." [We no longer have snow. The drought didn't start in the summer...]. Government regulations and economic policies have also reshaped engagement. In Boiu and Mălâncrav, traditional livestock grazing practices have been restricted due to road safety laws: "Dacă tot n-avem drumuri... Au zis că nu mai scot ciurda că e drum de importanță județeană." [If we don't have roads... They said they won't let out the cattle anymore because it's a county-important road] (Participant_Boiu). Despite their long-standing cultural and economic significance, these restrictions limit community members' ability to maintain biodiversity-friendly land use.

Future (potential outlook and revival opportunities): Despite the challenges, many participants express hope for a revival of biodiversity-friendly practices. The growth of eco-tourism, sustainable development initiatives, and cultural revival efforts is seen as an opportunity to reintegrate conservation into local economies. Participants acknowledge that infrastructural improvements could open doors to conservation-related tourism: "Cu drumul asfaltat, deschide drumul turismului..." [The paved road opens the way for tourism...] (Participant_Apold). A similar perspective is seen in Biertan, where there is hope for increasing conservation awareness: "Cu timpul o să conștientizăm tot mai mult chestiile astea, sper cel puțin." [I hope that, over time, we will become more aware of these things.] (Participant_Biertan). However, stronger policy support and community engagement strategies are necessary for these initiatives to succeed.

Conflicts & challenges in biodiversity conservation

1. Large carnivore management: A central point of contention across all villages is the increase in large carnivore populations, particularly bears and wild boars. Farmers experience economic losses due to livestock predation and crop destruction, with limited governmental support: "Da, ursul mi-a stricat... acum o lună... 4 oi, fără despăgubiri." [Yes, the bear killed... last month... 4 sheep, without compensation.]; "Aseară au trecut 2 urși." [Two bears passed through last night.]; "Acum și mistreții și căprioarele, se plâng lumea de ele!" [Now, both wild boars and deer... people are complaining about them!]. While some community members recognize the ecological benefits of these species, others argue that they pose an economic and safety threat, creating a need for balanced conservation strategies.

2. Agricultural land abandonment vs. Conservation: Rural depopulation has resulted in abandoned agricultural land, leading to negative and positive ecological consequences. Some participants see rewilding as beneficial for biodiversity, while others worry about the loss of productive farmland: "Pășunea devine pădure, ăsta nu e tocmai un lucru rău." [The pasture turns into a forest; that's not necessarily bad.]; "Expansiunea arbuștilor după abandon." [Shrub expansion after abandonment]. This conflict highlights the need for land-use policies that balance conservation goals with sustainable agricultural practices.

3. Urbanization and declining engagement: Youth migration to urban areas is losing traditional ecological knowledge and reduced participation in biodiversity conservation: "Satele sunt întregi care nu mai există." [Entire villages no longer exist.]; "Odată ajunși în comunități, nu mai au desfacere cum aveau mai demult." [Once they arrive in the community, they no longer have the market access they used to have.] Developing policies to attract and retain younger generations and make conservation-related employment viable is crucial for sustaining long-term biodiversity efforts.

4. Policy and bureaucratic obstacles: Government regulations, while aimed at conservation, sometimes restrict traditional practices that have historically supported biodiversity: "Exploatarea lemnului se face prin ocolul silvic... fără tăieri la ras." [Timber exploitation is done through the forestry district... without clear-cutting.]; "O baltă s-au certat o viață întreagă și... ăsta vrea să fie a lui, ăla vrea să fie a lui." [They fought over a pond for a lifetime... One wants it to be his, the other wants it to be his.] (Participant_Șoard). Balancing regulatory frameworks with local realities will be essential to fostering sustainable conservation practices. Biodiversity conservation across these villages has undergone significant transformations. While traditional practices once ensured sustainability, modern constraints have led to a decline in engagement. However, the growing awareness of environmental issues and the potential for eco-tourism present opportunities for revitalization. Addressing conflicts related to large carnivores, land abandonment, youth migration, and regulatory barriers will require collaborative efforts between policymakers and local communities.

Cross-Villages analysis

Across the six villages, several recurring themes emerge regarding the relationship between biodiversity, land management, and community identity.

Declining engagement in traditional practices is a widespread issue. Migration has reduced the number of younger residents in Biertan, Saschiz, and Mălâncrav, resulting in fewer stewards of traditional agricultural and land management techniques. In response, some communities, particularly Apold, Saschiz, and Mălâncrav, are turning to eco-tourism to revitalize local economies and revalue traditional knowledge within a contemporary context.

Tensions between wildlife conservation and farming further complicate local livelihoods. In Boiu, Saschiz, and Mălâncrav, recurrent damage from bears and wild boars generates frustration among farmers and challenges collaboration with conservationists. Conversely, in Apold and Biertan, conservation focuses on less conflict-prone species such as pollinators and birds, where initiatives to protect butterflies and storks are better aligned with community interests and agricultural practices.

Regulatory barriers also shape how these villages manage their natural resources. Farmers in Mălâncrav, Boiu, and Șoard report restrictions on traditional grazing, which limits their ability to maintain pastures sustainably. Meanwhile, Biertan and Apold highlight the difficulties caused by unclear biodiversity regulations, illustrating the persistent disconnect between local needs and higher-level governance structures.

Approaches to forestry and pasture management vary considerably. Șoard and Saschiz have prioritized sustainable forestry practices, including tree conservation and meadow restoration. In contrast, Apold, Biertan, and Mălâncrav emphasize preserving historical land-use patterns, such as orchards and vineyards, as a strategy to maintain biodiversity while sustaining local heritage.

Finally, local identity and cultural heritage remain closely tied to biodiversity across these communities. In Apold and Biertan, conservation of pollinator species has become a symbol of community pride and ecological responsibility. Mălâncrav and Saschiz, on the other hand, connect biodiversity preservation with seasonal festivals and traditional practices, ensuring that environmental stewardship is embedded within the social and cultural fabric of village life.

For guidance on navigating changes, see Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of those who successfully or unsuccessfully navigate natural changes

Profile of those who can more easily navigate challenges resulting from natural changes	Profile of those who struggle to navigate change
<p>Large agricultural entrepreneurs (although they also already experience drought);</p> <p>People who move from the village to the city and have financial resources;</p> <p>Solar energy investors;</p> <p>Informed individuals;</p> <p>Communities where people collaborate and are open to experimentation;</p> <p>Communities that include formal institutions, the church, and NGOs that collaborate and form a shared vision for</p>	<p>Small farmers – in cases where they do not collaborate;</p> <p>Small businesses that rely on nature's functionality – for example, drought and lack of water affecting tourism;</p> <p>Local communities with a high proportion of elderly individuals;</p> <p>Lack of information, lack of knowledge;</p> <p>Local communities where trust among people is lacking;</p>

<p>the community, valuing nature and taking a proactive approach to new challenges.</p>	<p>Local communities lack innovation, collaboration, and a shared vision that reactively approaches natural changes.</p>
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1.4 Initial Mapping of Interventions

a) Community-led festivals and gastronomy supporting biodiversity

One intervention in the Saschiz area is the revival of local food heritage through community festivals. The Rhubarb Festival in Saschiz, organized by the Women’s Neighborhood Association (Vecinătatea Femeilor) of Saschiz, is an example. For over a decade, local women have transformed a traditional Saxon culinary practice (cooking with rhubarb) into an annual celebration that attracts visitors and supports biodiversity-friendly farming. The festival, now drawing over 1,000 tourists each year, features rhubarb soups, pizzas, jams, and syrups made from locally grown produce, as well as craft stalls and cooking workshops for all ages. By creating demand for rhubarb and other traditional crops, the event incentivizes villagers to maintain home gardens and orchards instead of abandoning them. It thus links cultural gastronomy with conservation: success is achieved informally through growing attendance and the pride of local producers, as well as formally through the creation of new market outlets for biodiversity-based products (an online shop now sells Saschiz rhubarb goodies nationwide). Participation is highly inclusive (local housewives, farmers, and artisans), and they co-create the festival. The Saschiz Town Hall and NGOs, such as ADEPT, have supported these festivals as partners, demonstrating a collaborative governance model. This grassroots initiative challenges conventional top-down rural development by proving that small-scale, place-based food heritage can drive sustainable tourism and livelihood. Indeed, the number of tourists to Saschiz doubled between 2011 and 2016 (from 6,000 to over 12,000) after such community-led events took off (further information at <https://mytransylvanianvillage.wordpress.com/>), suggesting that conserving HNV farmland through celebrating its products is a viable intervention strategy.

b) Reviving traditional land use and crafts as innovative interventions

Several interventions in the Saschiz region aim to revive traditional land uses and crafts as a means of restoring biodiversity and promoting community welfare. In the nearby village of Mălâncrav, for instance, a historic Saxon apple orchard (dating to the 15th century) was rescued from abandonment and transformed into Romania’s first certified organic orchard. With support from the Mihai Eminescu Trust (MET), the entire 108-hectare orchard, with over 215 plant species and 100 bird species, was replanted with fruit varieties and managed with ecological methods. A small juice factory now produces about 20,000 liters of organic apple juice annually, sold in hotels and markets, and the orchard provides permanent and seasonal jobs for villagers. Notably, a nursery for old Transylvanian fruit tree varieties was established on-site to preserve genetic diversity and supply local farmers with saplings. This intervention builds on a niche innovation, traditional extensive orcharding, translating it into a modern social enterprise. Its success is measured both in biodiversity terms (dozens of wild plant and mammal species thrive in the orchard) and socio-economic terms (local employment and a revenue stream that makes conservation financially sustainable (further information at <https://www.mihaieminescutrust.ro/>). It also consciously involves the multi-ethnic community (Romanians, Saxons, Roma) in the stewardship of their natural heritage, illustrating inclusive practices. Back in Saschiz itself, the revival of Saxon pottery traditions is another socially embedded innovation. Saschiz was famed for its cobalt-blue pottery centuries ago, but the craft had nearly vanished. In 2015, Fundatia ADEPT (a local NGO) established a Pottery Training Center. Young people from across the Saxon villages were trained in ceramic skills to re-launch traditional pottery production. Today, pottery workshops not only produce beautiful traditional wares for sale but also serves an educational purpose: tourists and local schoolchildren can participate in hands-on pottery workshops, learning about the cultural heritage of the area. By blending

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craft revival with experiential tourism and youth vocational training, this initiative challenges the conventional view that heritage crafts are relics; instead, it positions them as drivers of rural innovation. The ADEPT foundation explicitly targets disadvantaged groups for employment in such projects, indicating a social inclusion angle (for example, training and hiring unemployed local youth or members of the Roma community in the ceramics workshop). The project's impact is evident both informally, in the renewed interest among local youth in their heritage, and formally, through the creation of new jobs and a tourist attraction, with the pottery center becoming a must-visit site for those touring the UNESCO-listed Saxon villages.

c) Participatory conservation, education, and inclusive governance

A hallmark of the Saschiz region's interventions is the participatory and inclusive approach to environmental management. Rather than relying on top-down enforcement, NGOs and community groups have promoted co-management of resources. For example, the village of Viscri (a neighboring locality) has a large wood-pasture with ancient oak trees, which has been maintained through a community-managed grazing system. Traditional rules and collective decision-making by villagers (including shepherds from all ethnic groups) have kept this wood-pasture in excellent condition, with significant biodiversity value. This common wood-pasture remains well-preserved through traditional agricultural practices and hosts a rich species diversity – a living example of how participatory governance can outperform "business-as-usual" intensive agriculture in conservation outcomes. In Saschiz itself, communal grazing associations have been formed with guidance from NGOs, to organize pasture use in ways that prevent overgrazing and reward local herders for sustaining the flora-rich meadows. Indeed, by 2010, ADEPT had facilitated the establishment of six grazing associations and conducted workshops with over 250 farmers to promote agro-ecological practices. One tangible result was a dramatic increase in uptake of agri-environment schemes: six times more farmers enrolled in biodiversity-friendly farming subsidy programs in the Saschiz area compared to nearby communes without such outreach. This is a formal success indicator that demonstrates how participatory advisory interventions can translate niche sustainable practices (such as rotational grazing and late hay mowing) into broader adoption. Local farming communities also participate in knowledge-sharing workshops on topics such as adding value to farm products and sustainable forest management, often led by or in partnership with ADEPT. Such workshops have led to the formation of new producer groups (e.g., a "Saxon Village Preserves" Slow Food network for traditional jam-makers) and even initiatives for community forestry certification, in which villages pursue FSC sustainable forest certification together. These examples underscore a shift towards inclusive governance: farmers, including smallholders and marginalized small producers, are actively involved in designing and implementing interventions, rather than being passive recipients of external instructions.

Youth and children are not left out. Both the MET and ADEPT have run environmental education and cultural heritage programs to seed the next generation's interest in sustaining their landscape. Schoolchildren in the Târnava Mare area have been given butterfly and wildflower identification guides, as well as farmers' almanacs adapted for HNV grasslands. Summer camps and "learning centers" in villages like Mălâncrav engage local and Roma youth in crafts, active citizenship workshops, and nature exploration. These informal interventions build local capacity and pride, ensuring the longevity of the more formal projects. Success here is often assessed through community feedback, for instance, increasing attendance in village meetings and Local Action Group forums.

d) Sustainable tourism and "High Nature Value" enterprise

Another cluster of interventions translates the region's niche innovations into sustainable business models, particularly in the tourism sector. The Transylvanian Bike Trails are a noteworthy example: with external grants and local cooperation, over 100 km of mountain biking and hiking trails have been created linking eight Saxon villages and the medieval town of Sighișoara. These trails traverse wildflower meadows, oak woods, and village

lanes, intentionally routing visitors through the most scenic natural and cultural spots. Every year, a "Transylvania Bike Trail Race" is held, drawing more than a thousand participants to experience these landscapes. The race (organized by a local sports club together with ADEPT) is explicitly aimed at raising awareness of the "unaltered beauty of the area" and demonstrating the potential of nature-based, low-impact tourism. It has also become an economic opportunity for local people: local bed-and-breakfasts fill up during the event, and many racers return later as regular agri-tourists. The trails themselves won a European Landscape Award for their integration of conservation with community benefits. Importantly, local villagers (including schoolchildren) use the trail network as well, and some have been trained as biking guides or hospitality providers, ensuring the benefits circulate locally. This social enterprise approach to tourism builds on the niche idea that HNV farmland can be more valuable as a tourist landscape than as an intensive monoculture. By investing in trails and events instead of large ski resorts or extractive industries, the Saschiz area has become a path that challenges mainstream rural tourism models. Success is measured in part by visitor numbers and media attention. Small family-run guesthouses, craft shops, and farm-to-table experiences have increased alongside these interventions. For example, some local entrepreneurs offer "Transylvanian brunches" and farm visits, blending sustainable tourism with agro-biodiversity education. One couple in Saschiz opened the "Tei Tea House" in a restored Saxon home, which doubles as a community hub for discussing new projects while serving herbal teas and syrups made from foraged linden flowers and elderflowers. Another family launched a farm produce "basket" delivery service (the "Peasant's Basket") via an EU-funded project, allowing urban consumers to order traditional pickles, cheeses and jams from Saschiz farms online. These initiatives demonstrate how traditional knowledge, whether for gathering wild herbs or creating pickling recipes, is being harnessed in new ways to give HNV farming an economic edge. One example is Pivnița Buncii ("Grandmother's Cellar"), a jam and syrup enterprise in Saschiz started by a local Scotsman, Jim Turnbull. He built a fruit processing center that now works with hundreds of villagers (many from poor families who seasonally pick elderflowers and berries) and employs several full-time staff to produce award-winning traditional preserves. By branding them as "like grandma used to make", this initiative connects culturally embedded skills (foraging, jam-making) with modern food markets. It challenges the conventional agri-business supply chain by keeping value addition local and ecologically gentle (e.g., wild elderflower instead of intensive crops). As an ADEPT director, Turnbull also insisted on training locals in hygiene and hospitality, enabling them to host tourists and offer tastings, which represents a holistic approach that links environment, culture, and business. The success of such social enterprises is often informal but tangible: Pivnița Buncii products are now sold internationally, and similar small businesses have sprouted in neighboring villages, indicating replication of the innovation.

The Saschiz community-led interventions provide how niche innovations can be scaled out or translated into mainstream practice. What began as local experiments (e.g., a farmers' market here, a heritage festival there) is now part of an integrated rural development approach. For instance, the Slow Food-inspired "Saxon Village Preserves" idea helped local women commercialize traditional jams, informing national policy discussions on short supply chains and Geographic Indication labels for local products. Likewise, the creation of grazing associations in Saschiz has been used as a case study by agricultural policymakers to promote commons-based pasture management in other regions. These interventions also underscore the importance of policy support: EU programs, such as Natura 2000 and agri-environment schemes, provided an enabling framework (e.g., paying farmers to maintain wildflower meadows), but it was the local actors' capacity to organize and innovate that ultimately determined success. The fact that six times more farmers joined eco-schemes in the Saschiz area than elsewhere suggests that policy mechanisms only reach their potential when coupled with local facilitation and trust-building.

Another lesson is the power of social innovation and inclusive governance in achieving conservation outcomes. Rather than treating biodiversity protection as a solely ecological or technical issue, the Saschiz case shows it is inherently social. Initiatives deliberately

built on cultural heritage (Saxon customs, Roma knowledge of the land) tend to gain local legitimacy and endurance. In fact, Saschiz and surrounding communes demonstrate a model of inclusive conservation where women's groups, farmers, and even youth clubs are stakeholders in biodiversity management. Policies aiming to replicate such success should therefore invest in local capacity (e.g., training rural animators and supporting micro-grants for community enterprises) and in mechanisms for participation (such as Local Action Groups or participatory budgeting for conservation initiatives).

Ultimately, these interventions challenge the conventional distinction between "development" and "conservation." In Saschiz, there are two sides of the same coin. High Nature Value farmlands are sustained not by fencing people out, but by drawing people in through livelihood projects, festivals, and education. The LIFE "Metamorphosis" project (2023–2029), now underway in the region, exemplifies this merged approach. It aims to reintroduce three threatened butterfly species and restore 45 hectares of meadow habitat, while indirectly protecting over 1,000 hectares by improving local incomes and working with farmers as partners. In other words, ecological experiments are not happening in isolation; they are entwined with social enterprise and participatory management. The Saschiz case study suggests that truly innovative interventions for biodiversity are those that embrace cultural context, empower communities (including marginalized Roma), and break the "business-as-usual" silo of conservation. By supporting festivals, local museums and centers, workshops, and inclusive campaigns, the region is actively redefining what biodiversity governance looks like on the ground, providing valuable insights for policymakers and researchers alike as they analyze interventions across Europe.

1.5 Discussion

Exclusionary practices in biodiversity governance

Biodiversity conservation is often shaped by exclusionary mechanisms that marginalize local knowledge, limit participation, and reinforce power hierarchies. These mechanisms manifest in various forms, from privileging scientific expertise over TEK to economic structures that disenfranchise small-scale farmers and local communities. Understanding these exclusionary practices is crucial for creating inclusive and effective biodiversity policies.

The role of values and social attitudes

Biodiversity governance is influenced by the values and attitudes that shape what is considered legitimate environmental knowledge. Historically, scientific frameworks have been prioritized over indigenous and local knowledge systems, systematically excluding traditional ecological practices. For example, conservation efforts in many rural areas often overlook the intricate understanding that local communities have of their ecosystems. Participants from Biertan illustrate this gap in perspectives. One workshop participant noted, "When I think about nature (...), it's a place where I don't see anything cultivated, just meadows or forests, without any kind of crops". This perception reflects the dominant conservation narrative, which views nature as separate from human influence. However, many local land users emphasize that biodiversity is a direct outcome of centuries of sustainable land management. "If we have biodiversity, it means that we have been quite sustainable so far" (workshop participant). Such statements highlight how exclusionary social attitudes can undermine the contributions of local communities to biodiversity conservation.

Furthermore, cultural identity is deeply intertwined with environmental practices. In Saschiz, a participant emphasized, "For me now, it means water. Water as a resource for food, drinking water, household water, water for animals" (workshop participant). The prioritization of scientific conservation over local knowledge overlooks these deeply

ingrained relationships with nature, thereby limiting the effectiveness of policy interventions.

Flows of knowledge and marginalization

Scientific research and policy-making processes often exclude or fail to engage local perspectives, further reinforcing power imbalances. Policies are usually formulated without consulting the individuals who are most directly affected, leading to ineffective implementation and community resistance. Knowledge asymmetries are also evident in the uneven distribution of resources and access to information. Rural communities frequently lack the means to engage in decision-making due to limited financial resources, restricted access to policy discussions, and barriers in navigating bureaucratic structures.

One participant noted: "Local communities are not well informed about legislation and do not comply with it. Everyone is minding their own business". This sentiment reveals the disconnect between policymakers and local populations. Similarly, the loss of traditional knowledge accelerates ecological degradation. A participant also reflected, "Thirty years ago, we used to bathe in the valley, but now there's barely any water flowing" (Participant_Saschiz). This highlights how environmental changes are exacerbated by the exclusion of TEK in biodiversity governance.

Economic practices and systemic exclusion

Economic structures play a significant role in biodiversity governance, often reinforcing exclusionary dynamics. Many small-scale farmers and pastoralists have historically maintained biodiversity through traditional practices, yet they are usually marginalized in broader economic policies. One participant from Biertan stated, "Small farmers... They have the most to lose. Overall, they have nowhere to sell their products because of our policies...". This economic exclusion leads to financial instability and weakens local resilience against environmental change. Moreover, economic incentives tend to favor large-scale conservation initiatives that cater to industrialized resource management or tourism rather than community-based conservation models. This displacement of traditional livelihoods disrupts existing human-nature relationships, forcing communities to conform to externally imposed conservation models. Industrialized farming further exacerbates ecological degradation. As one participant observed, "For twenty years, my father-in-law has only planted corn on the same plot" (This monoculture practice, driven by economic policies, contrasts sharply with traditional land-use strategies that promote biodiversity).

Power dynamics in decision-making

Biodiversity governance is often dominated by government agencies, NGOs, and scientific institutions, without providing a voice for local communities. This top-down approach imposes external conservation frameworks without considering local realities and contexts. A participant expressed frustration: "Our pastures used to be properly maintained, but now no one takes care of them". This highlights how traditional land management practices are being eroded due to power imbalances in conservation decision-making.

Inclusive mechanisms for biodiversity conservation

To counteract exclusionary practices, inclusive mechanisms must be strengthened to integrate diverse knowledge systems, empower marginalized groups, and promote participatory governance.

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- a) Strengthening participatory governance: Community-led conservation initiatives and co-management agreements are essential for fostering inclusion. These mechanisms help bridge the gap between scientific and local knowledge, ensuring that policies are co-created rather than imposed. One practical approach involves adapting conservation discourse to local understandings of nature. For instance, researchers substituted “biodiversity” with “nature” in interview guides to align with local perspectives. This simple linguistic shift facilitated more meaningful community engagement.
- b) Recognizing and valuing traditional knowledge: Policies should formally recognize TEK as a valid and valuable expertise. Legal frameworks can support this by protecting land rights, funding community-led research, and creating platforms for knowledge exchange. A participant emphasized the importance of traditional ecological knowledge, stating, “In our area, it was very important that almost all households had a well in the yard”. Biodiversity governance can benefit from centuries of accumulated wisdom by restoring and incorporating such practices.
- c) Supporting sustainable local livelihoods: Ensuring that biodiversity policies align with the economic needs of local communities is essential for their long-term viability. Many rural populations rely on traditional farming techniques that should be recognized within conservation frameworks. A participant noted, “Mowing is a bit mechanized now... because no one mows traditionally anymore”. Supporting sustainable land management techniques through financial incentives and policy recognition can help bridge this gap.
- d) Creating platforms for community engagement: Inclusive conservation requires spaces where local voices can be actively heard and involved in decision-making. Knowledge-sharing initiatives that integrate local perspectives into biodiversity governance foster a sense of ownership and long-term sustainability. A participant highlighted the cultural importance of local biodiversity knowledge: “Elderberry, for example, at grandma’s cellar, local elderberry...”. This demonstrates how biodiversity conservation must integrate both ecological and cultural dimensions to be effective.

The role of innovation and innovators

Innovation plays a crucial role in biodiversity conservation by introducing novel approaches that integrate traditional knowledge with modern sustainability strategies. Niche innovators, including local farmers, environmental activists, and citizen scientists, drive transformative changes by experimenting with new conservation techniques. Researchers introduced measures to protect the Albăstrelul Transilvan butterfly, engaging local farmers in habitat restoration. Similarly, community members have worked to preserve traditional vineyards, ensuring that these landscapes continue to support biodiversity. Recognizing and supporting these grassroots innovators is essential for fostering inclusive and sustainable biodiversity governance.

Exclusionary mechanisms in biodiversity governance marginalize traditional ecological knowledge, reinforce economic disparities, and limit participatory decision-making. However, inclusive approaches that recognize local knowledge and empower marginalized groups, fostering community-led conservation, can drive transformative change. By integrating traditional knowledge systems, supporting sustainable livelihoods, and strengthening participatory governance, biodiversity policies can become more equitable, effective, and resilient in the long term (Figure 1). Bridging the gap between scientific and local knowledge is essential to ensure that biodiversity conservation efforts are both socially just and ecologically sustainable.

Figure 2. Balancing exclusion and inclusion in biodiversity governance

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D2.2

Bottom-Up Forest Biodiversity

UGOT, Sweden

November 2025

Authors

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Summary

Summary of Deliverable

The study examines focusing on biodiversity dynamics among private forest owners in three Swedish parishes—Säve, Istorp, and Ambjörnarp.

Geographical and Historical Dimensions

Säve (near Gothenburg) features flat farmland and forested hills shaped by glaciation. Historically dominated by farming, deforestation peaked in the 19th century, followed by regrowth and spruce planting. Today, urban expansion pressures forests, with most residents working outside agriculture. Istorp is characterized by agricultural valleys and forested uplands, once communal grazing lands. Fires and 19th-century land reforms fragmented ownership, leading to conifer plantations. The population has declined since the 19th century, and current employment spans agriculture, construction, and services. Ambjörnarp is predominantly forested, with continuity since the 17th century. Poor soils constrained farming, fostering self-sufficient animal husbandry. Logging accelerated in the late 19th century, reducing deciduous cover. Population peaked around 1900 but later stabilized at low levels.

Key Actors and Worldviews

Swedish forestry debates pit industry (productive forestry) against conservationists (protection of old-growth forests). Private forest owners—diverse in background and rarely professional foresters—occupy a middle ground, valuing both ecology and practice. Local differences emerge: in Ambjörnarp, biodiversity is tied to forestry practices; in Istorp, to species variation and protection; and in Säve, to informed reasoning. Companies like Sveaskog, Derome, and Skanska integrate biodiversity unevenly, while associations such as Södra promote certification and voluntary conservation. Government actors (Swedish Forest Agency, Environmental Protection Agency, County Boards) enforce legislation and monitor biodiversity, with municipalities playing varying roles—minimal in Istorp/Ambjörnarp but significant in urbanizing Säve. Non-human “actants” such as capercaillie, trees, soils, and topography also shape forest use and conservation debates.

Drivers of Biodiversity Loss

Key direct drivers include reforestation (conversion of heathlands and open landscapes to conifers); even-aged silviculture (clear-cutting and monocultures, replacing diverse forest structures); and urban expansion (notably in Säve, where housing and logistics displace forests). Indirect drivers stem from industrialization, urbanization, and reinforcement of production forestry.

Cultural and Identity Dynamics

Forest owners emphasize relational values (recreation, heritage, stewardship) over economic returns. Conflicts arise with authorities and industry over management and aesthetics. Gender dynamics show women’s growing yet marginalized role, with networks like *Dryaderna* providing support. Age influences stewardship, especially succession planning.

Political/Institutional Dynamics

Swedish forestry is locked into even-aged silviculture due to long-standing policies, industrial interests, and infrastructure. This entrenched model shapes both national forestry culture and Sweden’s role in European policy, creating barriers to biodiversity-friendly alternatives.

Transformative biodiversity innovations (D2.2)

1.1 Analysis of Inclusion/Exclusion Mechanisms

Exclusionary practices

The exclusion of more diverse practices and perspectives in private forest ownership in western Sweden is shaped by several different dynamics: forest management norms, uneven knowledge access, current forestry regulations and economic structures. In combination, these serve to restrict possibilities for alternative practices and favours the adoption of industrial forestry.

Forest management norms

The ingrained practice of even-aged silviculture that has shaped Swedish forestry for more than 100 years contributes significantly to the marginalisation of alternative practices. Many of the interviewed forest owners, especially in Ambjörnarp and Istorp, express a feeling that they are already contributing to environmental values while practicing traditional certified forestry, often through actors such as Södra and Derome. In general, respondents express that private forest owners are primarily logging smaller areas, and compared to larger actors they are more considerate with their own forests:

O: *Do you think forestry could be changed in some way? How can biodiversity be improved or increased? [...]*

B: *That's the question. They've tried things like small clear-cuts and such. And we're already doing that. We don't do large clear-cuts. It's half a hectare. One hectare if it has to be done. And we leave a lot of seed trees and such. [...] No one around here is doing huge clear-cuts, actually. If it's larger forest owners, then maybe they do larger clear-cuts (Interview with 'Börje', September 2024).*

O: *How would you wish [the forestry debate] looked? What would you wish people did instead?*

B: *I think maybe those who have problems... Or who think that large clear-cuts and... that biodiversity isn't very good there. They should perhaps [more] focus on those who are doing things wrong, rather than making [a] general statement about how forestry in Sweden is. Because it's not like that in southern Sweden. Sure, the occasional forest might be mismanaged here too. But a forest farm down here is no more than 50 hectares. Then maybe you can harvest one hectare a year (Interview with 'Tommy', October 2024).*

No, but small forest owners [...] have a closer connection to their environment. They live nearby or own land nearby, so in some way they try to do the best they can, whereas larger state and private forest owners deal with much bigger volumes and have a greater need to make money (Interview with 'Annika', May 2024).

This implies that many private owners primarily perceive the environmental problems in traditional even-aged forestry to be an issue of scale rather than the practice. This is also a potential reason why many private forest owners interviewed perceive that the wider forestry debate does not concern them. However, interviews also revealed tendencies in private forest owners that may undermine biodiversity actions, such as the image of the 'clean' forest. A connected problem here concerns the reliance of forest owners on external advice, in our case study often from actors such as Södra or Derome. As described under chapter 3.2 of deliverable 2.5, these actors serve to entrench traditional forestry practices among private forest owners for the sake of providing resources to the forest industry.

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A specific historical dimension that hinders the adoption of alternative forestry practices is the early 20th-century debate in Sweden between selective logging (*blädning*) and clear-cut forestry (*trakthyggesbruk*). At that time, the discussion concluded with the view that selective logging had a clearly negative impact on long-term forest growth compared to clear-cutting. This perception still lingers among several forest owners and was brought up during both interviews and workshops, particularly in Ambjörnarp (e.g., interviews with 'Viktor' and 'Johan'). During the workshop in Ambjörnarp, it was suggested that the term "dimension cutting" (*dimensionshuggning*) be used instead, as "selective logging" carries historical baggage that makes it a sensitive concept

Uneven knowledge access

The interviews reveal differences in knowledge access among private forest owners in our case study, especially when it comes to alternative forestry practices and general knowledge of biodiversity. This is not the least related to how informed forest owners are on forest management in general and the degree to which they are active themselves. A previous background, for example growing up with family members involved in forestry, often leads to larger capacities for individual decision making. However, when such a background is lacking, management decisions are often delegated. For example, 'Eva', a rather recent widow in her mid-60s whose husband bought forest properties as a kind of investment, and who has worked in her husband's company, has little practical knowledge in forestry herself. She owns a forest property which she rarely visits as she lives c. 10 kilometres away. While she is currently striving to build up her own knowledge on forestry, but so far, she has delegated the forest management on this property almost entirely to Derome (Interview with 'Eva', October 2024).

In some cases, with new forest owners, the knowledge they build up over time increases their capacity to question the status quo in forestry which forestry consultants often default to:

O: *Right, then it's hard for you to know whether you'll get any income from the forest. Do you know anything? Do you have any thoughts?*

J: *Yeah, actually, we brought in Derome. [...]. And we didn't want to end up in a situation like with storm Gudrun... where everything ends up like a game of pick-up sticks. Because we wouldn't be able to deal with that. So, we actually want to collect that money. [...] [W]e doesn't know anything about forestry. But the guy from Derome said it would be a final harvest, and then the area would be defined. And then he'd arrange the harvesters. But then I read something in Land magazine about selling by the stump. Like, you go out beforehand and say: we'll take that tree, and that one. It paid better too. Maybe not for our small volume, but I don't care. I don't want it to look like a clear-cut. I want to take the trees that should be taken. Because that, to me, is forest care (Interview with 'Johanna', October 2024).*

It is somewhat of a struggle as a new forest owner to know how to navigate the complex knowledge arena connected to forestry issues, where there also may be conflicting information. Many new forest owners wish to do the right thing for environment and biodiversity but find it difficult to know exactly what to do and why since different actors give different advice.

What I feel is that I want a forest where you can occasionally harvest – I'm thinking more like thinning. I would like to have an actively managed forest where you thin out some trees and then let it regenerate. But as I said, this isn't something I've worked with, so I don't know if this is a realistic wish, but that's what I would want – to harvest selectively. Because I really hate clear-cuts, I think they're awful. I want the forest to remain, to really still be there (Interview with 'Helena', May 2024).

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A new forest owner attending our local workshop in Ambjörnarp, who wanted to have a forest management plan centred on conservation, expressed himself in this way:

At the same time, it's important that the forester you talk to – or someone in a similar role – understands what your intentions are. I wanted to adapt the forest management plan [...] to focus more on conservation. But in the end, it still turned out to be quite production oriented. So, you have to navigate that yourself. [...] I find that you really need to do a lot of research on your own, talk to many different people. I also get the sense that things are improving within Södra, but you can get different answers from different people, depending on their background and training. It's hard to know – do I have to do this, am I allowed to do that, and so on (Workshop in Ambjörnarp, March 2025).

At the same time, since knowledge production around forestry in a Swedish context is rather tied to the forest-industrial complex, there is a tendency for people with long practical experience, strong forestry educational backgrounds or strong connections to economic forestry to express themselves more negative towards alternative forestry practices:

O: *What's your view on continuous cover forestry?*

J: *A disaster.*

O: *In what way?*

J: *You get poorer stands, because you end up... we're going back to something that was once declared illegal.*

O: *You mean selective logging?*

J: *Yes, the selective logging that used to be illegal. That's the problem. But of course, we have to try to reinvent the wheel as many times as possible (Interview with 'Johan', September 2024).*

O: *Okay, what's your view on continuous cover forestry [...]?*

V: *Well, we've already tried that.*

O: *You're referring to the selective logging practices during the 20th century?*

V: *Exactly – or dimension cutting, or whatever they called it back then. So, we know exactly what a green lie looks like (Interview with 'Viktor', May 2024).*

Yes, if we're talking about selective cutting. I find it hard to believe in that. If I were to start doing selective cutting here, the harvesting costs would be high – that's probably the first thing that comes to mind. Then you get gaps, and the wind blows... If you're supposed to wait ten years, then you've got... It becomes really difficult to manage it in a sensible way. In an economically reasonable way (Interview with 'Andreas', September 2024).

The role that uneven knowledge access plays as an exclusionary mechanism is thus complex and context dependent. Limited knowledge leads to less capacity for independent decision-making and a larger reliance on forestry advisory services, but at the same time is often connected to knowledge seeking which may pave the way for interests in alternative practices. A larger knowledge base serves a foundation for being more independent in forest management, and while not always the case this does not seldom lead to stronger ties to even-aged silviculture.

Current forest regulations

Current Swedish Forest regulations play a significant role in shaping how private forest owners perceive and engage with biodiversity. Among many forest owners interviewed in the case study, biodiversity is often framed as something external, associated with the

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state agencies, EU policies or sometimes urban environmentalist agendas, rather than as a shared responsibility. This perception is enhanced through regulations that aim at environmental protection but frequently results in exclusion and disempowerment among landowners.

An often-recurring theme, not the least in the interviews, was that forest owners often associate biodiversity management with something imposed from above. The presence of certain species habitats – such as those of the capercaillie – can trigger legal restrictions on logging, with no automatic economic compensation for the affected landowners (e.g. Interview with 'Linda', May 2024; Interview with 'Jens', September 2024). Owners who have managed their forest to reach ecological continuity or high conservation values on their land may be faced with the fact that through promoting biodiversity they risk losing income or control over their land. To get any kind of compensation, they must typically initiate a legal process, which is time-consuming, uncertain and beyond the capacity of most individuals. This situation is largely perceived as unsustainable by a wide range of forestry actors, including environmental NGOs, which suggests that some kind of reform may not be far off.

Furthermore, the current regulatory system leads to practical geographical management decisions. Certification standards such as FSC or PEFC, which require a certain percentage of forest holding to be retention areas for conservation (typically 5-10%), are frequently met by setting aside unproductive, marginal or inaccessible forest land which in either case still would be less managed for forest production. This strategy allows owners to maintain productive forestry on the more economically valuable parts of their properties but distinctly limits the type of forest geographies that are typically set aside for conservation purposes, leading in turn to homogeneity of environmental values in the forest.

Economic structures

Economic structures in Swedish forestry create powerful exclusionary mechanisms that limit the adoption of biodiversity-enhancing practices among private forest owners. The prevailing market logic is strongly oriented toward standardized timber and pulp production, which marginalizes alternative forms of forestry such as long-rotation management, mixed-species stands, and continuous cover forestry.

Current market systems are structured around the demands of industrial actors who effectively set the terms for what qualifies as "marketable" forest products. Timber must conform to specific qualities and dimensions to be accepted by processing facilities, which means that overgrown or non-standard trees – often characteristic of more biodiverse or uneven-aged forests – are economically penalized. Forest owners who consider shifting toward biodiversity-oriented practices face structural disincentives, as their products may not find a viable market. This system reinforces production-oriented forestry and limits experimentation with alternative approaches.

The internal market also contributes to these constraints. Several respondents noted that trees exceeding standard dimensions are difficult or impossible to sell, as industrial processes are optimized for specific sizes. This technical limitation discourages forest owners from adopting longer rotation cycles that would allow forests to mature more naturally and increase biodiversity. The result is a system where forest management is shaped not only by ecological or ethical considerations but by what the market will accept – often to the detriment of biodiversity.

Inclusive mechanisms

The inclusive mechanisms active in the case study areas range from personal engagement to top-down initiatives and legal frameworks. In this sub-section, we divide these mechanisms into personal, horizontal and top-down.

Personal inclusive mechanisms

Many forest owners, especially those with close family ties or who live on or nearby their own forest land, exhibit strong place-based connections to their forests and the species in them. In the wider context of Swedish forestry, often defaulting to traditional even-aged practices, personal engagement is very important in challenging the status quo. In the context of our interviews and workshops, this is most clearly expressed when it comes to forests closer to residential areas, which are more often used for recreational purposes, and which serve more clear aesthetic functions. There is a larger tendency for forest owners to use alternative practices, less monoculture forest stands and focus more on deciduous trees closer to their areas of residence:

If you're looking for a return on investment, then it might be more difficult to use alternative harvesting methods. But in our case – I'm speaking more generally now – but in our case, it's more about... the areas we're currently considering are closer to where we live, and in those cases, I think we'll choose the method that makes the forest look nice afterward (Interview with 'Anders', May 2024).

The same is true in the case of forest owners owning several forest properties, where they tend to prioritize recreational and aesthetic values on properties with closer geographic or emotional proximity.

I might be talking more than you'd like now, but as I mentioned, the farm we have in Torsestorp – we manage it more emotionally than rationally, and because of that we try to do things a bit differently. We've planted beech on two hectares, even though everyone said it wouldn't work, that beech can't grow there, but it's doing just fine. So, on that farm, we're focusing on creating a more varied type of forestry, but elsewhere we manage things more rationally (Interview with 'Erik', October 2024).

O: What would you say the forest means to you personally?

E: Here, where I live in my house, it means a lot. I love walking in the forest – even though it's not that big here, I would never move to the city. But then the one over in Grimmed, I'd say that one doesn't mean as much. Not in my heart, so to speak (Interview with 'Eva', October 2024).

There is also a strong tendency for many forest owners to host negative feelings towards too large clear-cuts, and this serves as a mechanism for being more open to practices where such clear-cuts are avoided. However, this seldom means adopting alternative forest management across the entire forest property, but rather to create or use the forest in way that avoids larger areas of clear-cuts but is still managed traditionally.

Another mechanism here is connected to the forest owners who are hunters in Ambjörnarp and Istorp, who often care deeply for wild species, especially larger mammals such as the moose, on their land. This also serves as an arena of some conflict with larger forestry corporation, which opens up for a wider critique of the forest industry.

And ideally, we should eradicate calves, shoot all of them, it seems. And we don't want that. We want... It's actually really fun to go up into the forest and see a moose, but they don't want that. Well, it's the forestry companies that are saying no. We have Sveaskog. And it's just about shooting, period. They don't care if there's a moose next year, they don't care about that, because they're focused on their forest. Whether there's any browsing damage or not, they don't care, they'll shoot anyway. So they're the ones influencing the county administrative board (Interview with 'Jens', September 2024).

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What we were talking about earlier, a bit about moose hunting and such. In my world, it's entirely the fault of the large forestry companies that there are no moose. Because they've wrongly blamed the moose for browsing damage on pine trees and wanted to more or less eradicate the moose, forcing the tenants to hunt much more than they're actually interested in themselves (Interview with 'Simon', May 2024).

Horizontal inclusive mechanisms

There are some signs in the case study of cooperative mechanisms which may have potential in ensuring more biodiversity-friendly practices among forest owners. An apparent example here is that members within Södra have pushed the organisation to give advice on continuous cover forestry since autumn 2024. This shows the potential of horizontal organisation among forest owners to push for changes in the largely industrial actors which they continuously interact with.

The workshops also revealed ideas for horizontal organisation that would enhance the capacity for forest owners to pursue alternative practices. At the workshop in Ambjörnarp, the idea of establishing a shared machinery pool for local forest owners was raised, since investing in forestry machines individually is often very expensive. Challenges with this idea were also discussed, particularly that heavily used large machines would require costly repairs. Nevertheless, it was seen as an opportunity to support more small-scale forestry operations (Workshop in Ambjörnarp, March 2025). The same idea was also brought up at the workshop in Istorp, where participants discussed the possibility of locally organizing a machine station for smaller harvesters to facilitate dimension cutting (Workshop in Istorp, March 2025).

The focus group interview with Dryaderna also showed the potential in horizontal organisation among forest owners, with less formal ties to industrial forest production. While it is unclear in what ways specifically female forest owners practice different kinds of forest management from their male counterparts, a forum such as Dryaderna at least seems to serve as an inclusive environment which broadens the perspective on forestry:

It's interesting because... at the men's forestry days, it used to be – maybe it's not as much anymore – but it was very clear that everything revolved around forestry. And in our gatherings, you meet so many women who have completely different jobs. And that's actually quite nice. Even though they are very interested in their forests, they also have slightly different ways of thinking about life (Workshop with Dryaderna, March 2025).

The problems of existing member organisations such as Södra were also raised in both workshops and interviews, especially the industrial ties of this actor and that they do not accept specialty assortments of timber, focusing on a narrow range of products (Workshop in Istorp, March 2025). In one of the interviews, the potential of creating a branch organization for small forest owners was raised in contrast:

E: *We are always in the shadow of the large forest owners and forest companies. I don't know how we are supposed to make our voices heard – we should have our own industry association for small forest owners to speak up through. But as far as I know, we don't have one.*

O: *How do you feel about Södra then? Don't they represent you in any way?*

E: *I don't think so. Sure, it's member-owned, but somehow it feels like they have one foot in the big forest companies and one foot among the members. But to me, they feel more like a large forest company than true representatives.*

O: *Do you think it could make a difference if forest owners organized themselves independently?*

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E: *Yes, I actually do. Not least because forest companies often shape how people think forestry should be done. Things like thinning – when and how often. They push that everywhere because it benefits their industry (Interview with 'Erik', October 2024).*

Another example of horizontal organization is the hunting teams, in which many forest owners are involved. Within the hunting teams, landowners (and others, such as those who lease hunting rights) come together. Hunting teams often work with various types of wildlife management, such as improving habitats and providing supplementary feeding. In Ambjörnarp, an example was given of how the local hunting team defies the moose quotas assigned to them by the County Administrative Board, which several forest owners engaged in hunting believe are set too high:

O: *What's your impression of the moose population?*

K: *Very small, really far too small. The hunting team that operates on our land doesn't shoot as many animals as they are allocated.*

O: *So they're trying on their own to increase it?*

K: *Yes, and they're also very careful about which animals they shoot. They avoid shooting the males – the moose bulls – that are in their prime. Instead, they prefer to shoot older animals and calves. They want to keep the animals that will produce the next generation (Interview with 'Kristin', October 2024).*

These types of horizontal mechanisms certainly have the potential to be developed further through different bottom-up initiatives, and as shown here some of these types of organizational initiatives are already initiated locally and regionally.

Top-down mechanisms

Although not efficient in handling the contradictions between production and conservation interests the current Swedish forestry legislation serves as an important inclusive mechanism, especially in comparison to earlier legislations from the 70s and 80s. The current legislation allows a large amount of freedom for forest owners to choose their type of management and use according to their own interests, where previous legislations had more formal rules which served to enhance the production interests in the forests. This "freedom under responsibility" has become the lead word for Swedish forestry, meaning that as long as forest owners abide by certain legislation, primarily for environmental considerations, they are free to manage their forests for their own goals and purposes. However, there has also been calls for more active involvement of the government in setting more clear boundaries for Swedish forestry, both from actors with industrial interests (who wants to ensure that the forest remains in use) and from people or organisations interested in promoting biodiversity conservation and climate adaptation (e.g. more forest area under formal protection by the state). The Swedish Government is currently working with updating the forest legislation. A government-initiated public inquiry has proposed financial compensation at 125% of market value when environmental considerations prevent logging, simplifying the approval process for forestry operations and capping the cost of surveys for protected species (with excess costs covered by the state). If such legislation is finally put into practice, this would mean larger space for promoting environmental values in Swedish forests.

The government has also directed Skogsstyrelsen and Naturvårdsverket to develop strategies to increase the share of continuous-cover forestry in Swedish forests. A report from this work described increasing the share of continuous-cover practices in state-owned forest companies to 20-25% as an important step and giving financial incentives, targeted consultation and developing business models to promote the adoption of such practices among private forest owners (Naturvårdsverket & Skogsstyrelsen, 2023). Like the

suggested changes in the forest legislation, an adoption and development of such policies would likely increase the number of viable alternatives in forest management, paving the way for more nature-inclusive management types.

Public actors such as the Swedish Forestry Agency (Skogsstyrelsen) and SMHI (Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute) have also intensified efforts to promote climate adaptation and biodiversity in forestry. These agencies have developed educational campaigns, digital advisory tools, and reports that encourage forest owners to reduce dependence on Norway spruce monocultures, in favour of mixed-species stands better adapted to a warming climate. The Forestry Agency has, for instance, published recommendations for diversifying species composition and adjusting silvicultural practices to new climatic realities. SMHI has contributed with climate models and local projections, helping forest owners assess future risks related to drought, storms, and pest outbreaks – factors that directly affect forest management strategies. Although few of the forest owners we have interacted with are aware of these resources available to them, if promoted more efficiently they would not only increase climate adaptation in Swedish forestry, but also present pathways away from traditional conifer monocultures.

As mentioned under chapter 3.6 of deliverable 2.5, there are also various ongoing strategies within the forest industrial sector which largely serves the function to uphold industrial forest production under the pressures of environmental change. However, although part of a status quo movement, it should also be recognized that some of these have potential to transform material practices and make way for more nature-inclusive ways to manage at least parts of the forest. One example of this is the development of biodiversity credits, in Sweden under the platform Treebula, where companies can purchase credits to fund biodiversity-enhancing measures in private forests. Payments are made to forest owners who commit to promoting biodiversity and a continuous monitoring of these values aim to ensure accountability. The first such transaction in Sweden occurred in the autumn of 2024. If developed further, this type of business model may allow forest owners a financial incentive to promote biodiversity, although it can be questioned what types of biodiversity that will be promoted under such schemes and what effects it would have on forest management on a larger scale. Another example is Södra Skogsägarna's nature conservation premium, which incentivises members to voluntarily set aside a larger proportion of their forests for conservation. Forest owners who allocate up to 14% of their total forest area for conservation purposes receive a higher price per cubic meter of timber harvested from the remaining forest area. However, questions can also be raised here whether 14% is enough to preserve biodiversity, especially under the rather homogenous geographical strategies by which already unproductive land is chosen for conservation purposes.

1.2 Niche Innovators and Key Players

Since our case study analyses a case where there is no formal societal partner, and no coordinated action among the forest owners for biodiversity restoration/regeneration, we have not engaged in practical activities with the innovators that we have identified towards this goal, nor have they engaged us. Our case study has been focused on trying to understand the conditions for working with and engaging private forest owners in biodiversity efforts in their forests, and while doing so a few individuals have emerged as more innovative and experimental than others. Here, we focus on contextually analysing what makes these innovators unique and discuss the potential of upscaling their innovations. Innovators 1 and 2 were engaged in the local workshops that we organised, while innovator 3 did not have the opportunity to participate.

To maintain confidentiality while providing detailed information relevant to the study of innovation, certain details about the innovators have been generalised. Additionally, a gender-neutral description has been used to further protect the individuals' identities (they/them). We have also chosen not to disclose the month of the interview, since this may enable identification or connection to other quotes and individual information in this

report. Furthermore, while each innovator represents one of the study areas, we have chosen not to name these areas explicitly.

Innovator 1

This forest owner is in their seventies and deeply engaged in questions of biodiversity and climate change at both local and international levels. With a background as a journalist for Swedish national radio and as a former press officer at the European Parliament, they represent a generation politicised during the 1968 movement and the anti-nuclear campaigns of the 1980s. Today, they are still politically engaged and a member of national activist groups, participating in public climate demonstrations.

Although having spent much of their life elsewhere, they have strong ties to the local community, having grown up in the area. A few years ago, they returned to live on their family farm. They currently own c. 50 hectares of forest land divided between two properties inherited through their family and are committed to landscape stewardship that goes beyond personal benefit, aiming to provide ecosystem services for the wider society.

They hold a membership in Södra Skogsägarna by heritage but are rather critical of its standard forest management practices. To deepen their knowledge, they have pursued nature-oriented courses offered by adult education institutions, the Board of Forestry, and the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute.

Innovator 1 sees biodiversity loss and climate change as interconnected and equally serious threats, shaped by a background in professional work and political engagement. They oppose industrial forestry and monocultures, advocating for reduced consumption and more continuous-cover forestry to enhance resilience against climate change. They value ecological and aesthetic qualities of broadleaf forests, aiming for greater diversity instead of monocultures.

Innovations include planting oak and other broadleaf trees, restoring wetland areas to create carbon sinks and promote biodiversity, and developing a forest management plan focused on ecosystem services rather than personal profit. The plan, created in collaboration with a biologist, draws on historical maps to guide restoration efforts. Although full implementation is still pending, the owner's approach emphasizes long-term societal benefits in terms of climate and biodiversity.

Innovator 1 describe themselves as rather marginalised among the local private forest owners who primarily practice traditional forestry:

O: *Isn't there someone who comes and asks you how you do things, someone who's curious?*

M: *They naturally think they know much more than I do because they are farmers, and the closest neighbour down here has worked as a forest worker, and the one who leases land has really large forests and has bought up a lot. He didn't have very large forests to begin with. He does one good thing – he has a lot of horses that he uses for work in the forest. [...] Otherwise, it's completely traditional – clear-cuts and spruce plantations (Interview with Innovator 1, 2024).*

The same impression was given when Innovator 1 attended the local workshop where they raised the importance of a changed forestry legislation, with the forestry act incorporated under the Environmental Code, and called for Sweden to fulfil the international commitments it has signed. This was not taken up for further discussion by the other forest owners present; the sense was that the proposal either went over their heads or was actively ignored. Still, Innovator 1 with a background in journalism has managed to make their voice heard in other contexts such as regional media.

Innovator 2

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This forest owner is in their fifties with a background in public administration, they have experience working in both Swedish Government offices and municipal settings. About 15 years ago, they moved back to their family farm and transitioned into forestry, completing a foundational forestry program and additional distance studies at Växjö University.

Today, they divide their time between forestry work and running a small-scale agricultural business. They own approximately 30 hectares of forest land and manage the forest largely manually, gradually transitioning to alternative practices such as various forms of continuous-cover forestry. This approach is strongly inspired by their child, who works at a cultural heritage reserve and advocates for historical, low-impact forest management.

They are also working towards greater self-sufficiency in food and raw materials, aiming to reduce reliance on external inputs. Their role as a freelance forest planner has provided a broad network among local forest owners. While not generally perceived as radical, they are attentive to the individual goals of each landowner and tailor forest management plans accordingly. They maintain strong collaborative ties with neighbours, sharing access to forestry machinery and coordinating work, resulting in largely self-sufficient but locally cooperative forest management. Due to their forestry activities and work, they have a large network of forest owners in the local area.

For innovator 2, the forest is a place of reflection and restoration, but also a site for creative experimentation. The owner actively reshapes their forest with a strong focus on biodiversity, mixing tree species and structures even when this challenges rational forestry norms. They see biodiversity as essential for ecological functions and are critical of the pulpwood-oriented model within Södra, instead aiming to align ecological care with the production of high-quality timber for craft and construction.

Their approach is marked by curiosity and innovation: they test continuous-cover forestry, selective thinning, and natural regeneration in old pine stands. They increase the presence of broadleaved trees and undergrowth to support wildlife and climate resilience. They exchange wood and forestry services with neighbours and explore forest grazing and commercial blueberry production as new uses of the land. Much of this is done in dialogue with their child, and they are considering submitting motions to Södra to promote more diverse forms of forestry.

The large forestry network of innovator 2 is particularly useful when it comes to marketing products from their alternative forest management and ensuring a degree of self-sufficiency. For example, they have a designated area where they work with a so-called seed tree stand of old pines, intended to seed naturally and regenerate the forest underneath. These pines are of high quality and old age, and through their network they have the opportunity to sell this timber locally through selective logging:

Now we met someone who lives up here in the forest [...] he helps out with carpentry in the local heritage association, and he works with log construction nowadays since he moved up here to a small cottage. [...] He now buys standing timber, the good quality trees, and he wants to use local wood for the heritage association's buildings [...]. So he's interested in buying pine trees standing here, and he doesn't buy everything at once, but instead, if he needs five pines or whatever he might need, he just takes those instead of bringing in machinery. [...] As the crow flies, it's just like from the mast over there to here, [...] so he can just cross through the forest and our land to fetch them here, and that's how we sell the timber (Interview with Innovator 2, 2024).

Innovator 2 is largely careful in advocating their own views when interacting with other forest owners professionally, a setting which otherwise potentially could serve as an arena for transformative action. However, their closest neighbours are practicing a similar kind of forestry which gives Innovator 2 a certain local influence, especially since they are collaborating closely with each other. Their local setting constitutes a local pocket of alternative practices, which likely serves as an important facilitator for this which would be more difficult to pursue individually.

Innovator 3

This forest owner is in their sixties and has become increasingly engaged in forest management over the past few years. With a background in the construction industry, including running their own business and nearly three decades in product development at Volvo, they are self-taught in forestry. Their practical understanding of wood, developed through years in construction, strongly influences how they manage their land today. Although politically reserved, they are socially active through collaboration with a son-in-law who supports practical forest work and through participation in online groups for small-scale forestry.

The owner lives on a horse farm together with family members and holds a shared ownership of the property. Initially seeking land mainly for horse activities, they have gradually developed a deep interest in the forest, which covers about half the property. Forestry work is primarily directed towards personal use rather than commercial profit, with activities like small-scale logging, timber sawing, and firewood production. They have used timber from their own forest to build structures such as machine halls and stables, focusing on resource efficiency and self-sufficiency.

Innovator 2 connects forest management to active stewardship and personal craftsmanship. They emphasize removing storm-felled trees, maintaining a clean and accessible forest environment, and supporting biodiversity and ecosystem functions, particularly for pollinators. Regulations around biodiversity are generally accepted as they are not perceived to interfere significantly with the owner's management approach.

Innovations include using a personal sawmill to produce building materials, practicing selective logging and continuous-cover forestry to maintain an ongoing supply of older trees, and experimenting with an informal forest inventory to monitor tree numbers and ages. Their approach reflects a practical, resource-oriented creativity aimed at sustainable and self-reliant forest use.

Innovator 3 knows all the local forest owners but feels that these owners do not actively manage their forests. They say they do not want to complain about their neighbours, but for example, they feel that windfallen trees are left for too long, which can lead to infestations such as bark beetles. They also mention that several owners just hire a logging company when needed, and while some have done so, most are completely inactive in managing their forests. They do not seem to have any ambition to influence how others manage their land, and therefore his way of managing the forest has had little impact on local forest management.

1.3 Scalable Bottom-Up Innovations for Transformative Change

In our case study, a range of bottom-up innovations have emerged, primarily in contact with the key innovators listed above. These have primarily been assessed in the context of local workshops with private forest owners organised in March 2025, where we also explored further ideas and took top-down initiatives into consideration. The bottom-up innovations identified are listed below.

1. **Continuous Cover Forestry (CCF):** This is an alternative to clear-cutting, which maintains forest continuity and promotes/preserves biodiversity dependent on continuity (such as capercaillie), primarily through selective harvesting, or dimensional cutting. There are also alternatives such as gap harvesting or retained shelterwood, although selective harvesting of various forms was the primary management form put forward in both interviews and workshops. Although this is not a local innovation per se, since it is already practiced internationally and in other areas nationally, as already mentioned there is a clear bottom-up push from members within Södra to make this organisation provide advisory service for CCF, which has now been successful. Local innovators such as Innovators 2 and 3 also

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show how CCF can be applied to set goals and used in creative and innovative ways as part of a more self-sufficiently directed forest production.

2. **Use of Biologists for Forest Planning:** This innovation is distinctly tied to Innovator 1, where the goal was to develop forest management for a wider range of 'ecosystem services', a term used by the Innovator themselves. Such an approach deviates in many ways from usual forestry practices focused on wood and timber production, focusing on landscape restoration and a move away from previous monoculture and even-aged management systems.
3. **High-quality timber production:** This was primarily raised as an innovation by Innovator 2 in Istorp but plays into the management of Innovator 3 and was taken up as a point of discussion in all of the local workshops. The production of high-quality timber as a long-lasting material for building or handicraft fundamentally requires alternative forestry practices which deviates from even-aged silviculture. CCF is an important component of this, but it is also dependent on geographic context and adaptation to local conditions.
4. **Commercial Bilberry Production:** Innovator 2 also raised a personal innovation and the potential that they saw in commercialising bilberries as a way to promote multi-use forestry, which would make it possible to manage the forest in other ways than primarily for wood production.

Transformative potential and equity

Out of these innovations listed, the one with the most radical divergence from current forest management is the use of a biologist for forest planning. Adopting such innovations means moving away from valuing the forest primarily for personal gains (be they economic, material, recreational or other) towards a view where the local forests play an intricate role in a wider environmental context, serving larger societal purpose (for example as a carbon sink) but also being valued in itself. In turn, this means a large motion towards a 'nature-positive' forest management. Since the forest landscape today on a wide scale is strongly shaped by human intention as an economic resource, and also in relation to the fact that the aim of a biologically orientated forest management plan would be to restore the landscape to an earlier state also heavily influenced by human use, such a forest management would require a close interaction between human management and different non-human actants. What this means in practice is that landscape restoration is dependent on human intervention, observation and close consideration of species and environmental responses over time in order to reach a set restoration goal.

However, in a wider context, this innovation seems largely marginalised and it is questionable to what extent it could be upscaled in practice, especially in cases where forest uses serve personal and practical material purposes which also evolves over time. Innovator 1 themselves mention that this innovation was possible since they did not rely economically on an income from the forest, and the biologist employed for this purpose was a personal contact (Interview with Innovator 1, 2024). In cases where an income from the forest serves a reproductive purpose in a household, family or farm economy it is often more difficult to pursue alternative practices, not the least since forestry is dependent on long-term management with large uncertainties which means that long-term risks need careful evaluation. To a certain extent, this also aligns with ongoing research into how to widen the scope of current forest management plans by introducing a wider landscape perspective through regional plans for Green Infrastructure (Karlsson et al., 2024). However, as noted by Karlsson et al (2024), current forest legislation is largely built around voluntariness which means that implementation of such plans builds on personal interest and engagement. The same could be said of biologist forest management plans, which implementation builds both on material possibility and personal interests.

CCF and high-quality timber are two innovations that are highly connected to each other, and which has a transformative potential not the least when it comes to material practices and outcomes in the forest. It is widely recognised that CCF is superior to even-aged

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silviculture in supporting forest biodiversity, for example regarding deadwood retention, habitat heterogeneity and mycorrhizal development (Atlegrim & Sjöberg, 2004; Joelsson et al., 2018; Sterkenburg et al., 2019). In many cases, such as the case with the capercaillie hindering clear cuts mentioned under section 3.2, CCF is possible to practice in places where regular logging is restricted legally for environmental considerations (ATL, 2024). The relationship between CCF and high-quality timber is rather uncertain scientifically, since very few studies exist, but CCF generally produces denser tree rings although the quality of sawn goods generally is comparable to traditional retention forestry. A specific method mentioned for the production of high-grade timber is overstorey retention for pine (Piispanen et al., 2025), which was specifically practiced by Innovator 2.

While this emphasises CCF as a transformative material practice, it is less evident how such forest management would impact worldviews in a wider sense, or if the forest still is used primarily for instrumental purposes. As exemplified both by Innovator 2 and 3, the forest, while fundamentally an environment of enjoyment and recognised for its intrinsic environmental values (e.g. as a habitat), it is primarily discussed as a resource for personal goals and aims.

As shown by the member-driven development in the organisation Södra, these types of management practices are attractive enough to drive changes within large industrially oriented membership organisations. Upscaling of such practices are therefore already ongoing in a Swedish context, also encouraged by government authorities (Naturvårdsverket & Skogsstyrelsen, 2023). A major constraint to wider upscaling is constituted by the legacies of even-aged silviculture in Sweden, including industrial supply chains, forest politics and market access. Forests managed under CCF cannot meet current or future industrial demands for pulpwood and standardised assortments of timber (Stål et al., 2024).

At the local workshops organised, CCF and high-quality timber or at least alternative timber assortments than the usual was specifically taken up for discussion. In Ambjörnarp, restrictions related to sawmills and the industry was mentioned, where the industry primarily prioritises rapid growth and coniferous trees. This leads to less possibilities for developing slower growing forests with higher quality and also restricting the market for deciduous trees. A potential solution to this was to develop small-scale local sawmills which could take care of and market high quality timber (Workshop in Ambjörnarp, March 2025). In Istorp, there was a wider group of forest owners interested in or already practicing CCF in parts of their forests. However, important constraints were also raised such as transitioning existing spruce monocultures, the large-scale direction of industrial markets and the shifting national forest legislations which makes long-term planning difficult (Workshop in Istorp, March 2025). In Säve, where very few forest owners engaged in the workshop had practical knowledge or experience in forestry, high-quality timber production through dimensional and selective cutting seemed attractive. This was specifically raised in relation to a transition from a more resource intensive society to more long-term resource use, although local conditions for such timber were mentioned as rather unsuitable by more experienced participants (Workshop in Säve, March 2025).

In summary, our local workshops clearly illustrated that there is considerable interest in pursuing alternative practices such as CCF and high-quality timber, although there are many constraints to overcome ranging from industrial supply chains and markets to local geographic conditions and legacies of past even-aged silviculture. As also shown in the description of Innovators 2 and 3, the adoption of such practices depends on both local social networks, collaboration or individual practical capacities. The largest potential for upscaling such practices likely thus start in the development of local and regional markets for such products, including overcoming restrictions relating to machinery and logistics.

The last innovation mentioned here, commercial bilberry production, is deemed to carry the least potential for transformative upscaling, due to climate, social and equity reasons. This is not the least the case since there is already a Swedish bilberry industry intricately entwined in global commodity chains through its nutritional and medicinal character. The

Swedish bilberry industry has grown from small family businesses selling locally to mass global exportation dependent on the recruitment of cheap foreign labour, often from Asian countries (Hedberg, 2016). A large share of exported wild-picked bilberries are refined (increasing the value) and used in the global medical industry, with connected long-distance transportation and increased emissions. At the same time, bilberries and particularly blueberries are important to fill demands on the Swedish market (Lundgren, 2021). Thus, in order to commercialise and upscale Swedish bilberry production in socially/environmentally sustainable and equitable way the current market logics through which Swedish wild bilberries are globally valued needs to be changed, along with the dependence on cheap foreign labour.

If analysed as an alternative forest management, with the goal to increase bilberry cover and production amounts in the forest, simulations have shown that a combination of different management practices, including both traditional retention forestry and CCF etc., is the best alternative (Bergenheim, 2024). This means that innovations in this area may lead to increased possibilities for alternative practices in Swedish forestry, also pursuing values beyond wood production. However, as already mentioned, it is doubtful whether upscaling of such this innovation can be considered transformative in a wider social and environmental sense.

1.4 Initial Mapping of Interventions

In our case study, we regard the workshops we organized – particularly those held in Istorp, Ambjörnarp, and Säve – as the main interventions. This is based on the fact that private forest owners rarely meet to discuss forestry-related issues in settings that deviate from standard forestry contexts. Typically, such encounters take place during forestry days or courses organized by actors like Södra or the Swedish Forest Agency. These gatherings are often characterized by top-down information transfer between experts and forest owners. By contrast, our workshops were designed to foster peer-to-peer dialogue around alternative forest management practices and, more broadly, around pressing issues affecting forest biodiversity. We aimed to provide a platform for forest owners to articulate their needs and perspectives on forestry in a shared and reflective space.

A recent literature review on private forest owners and forest-related services (Matilainen et al., 2023) noted that most existing studies adopt a top-down approach, focusing on how to convince forest owners to adopt specific services or participate in centrally designed forestry programmes. The need to understand forest owners' perspectives and wishes is widely acknowledged, empirical research focusing on such a bottom-up perspective remains limited. Our qualitative case study, and especially the workshops, directly contribute to filling this gap. From this perspective, the workshops can be considered as interventions that aim to deepen the knowledge about the relationship between forest governance and the agency of forest owners. Our workshops, also supported by the interviews, demonstrate that the needs and interests of forest owners vary significantly depending on local geographic, economic, and social conditions. This should be of high significance for understanding how biodiversity-promoting practices interacts with the social, cultural and economic conditions underlying the management of forest owners in different contexts. In this sense, our approach also deviates from conventional approaches to understanding private forest owner perspectives.

The workshops also served as testing grounds for introducing and discussing various niche innovations in forest management. In particular, we raised discussions around Continuous Cover Forestry (CCF) and high-quality timber production, which allowed participants to critically evaluate these practices considering their own goals and local conditions. We also introduced other innovations not as prominent in the interview material, but common in other forestry contexts, such as landscape restoration, nature tourism and bio-credits. These were introduced along with the niche innovations listed above as a means to assess which ones sparked the most interest as a topic for discussion. Overall, these innovations were not technically evaluated but brought up in collective discussion, where participants

considered how such approaches might align or conflict with their own forest management goals.

Importantly, the workshops were designed to reflect specific characteristics of each area. In Istorp and Ambjörnarp, with a high level of active engagement in forestry, the workshops focused on the prospects for local implementation of alternative practices. Participants were also asked to identify their own needs and wishes concerning forest management, with the aim to bring these insights to a follow-up workshop with regional decision-makers. In contrast, in Säve few forest owners were actively managing their forests beyond harvesting of firewood or small-scale timber sales. The focus there shifted to the question of how to encourage more active management among forest owners in the area. This was particularly relevant because many Säve's historical biodiversity values are linked to open or semi-open habitats like former pastures and heathlands, which are increasingly threatened by reforestation due to abandonment.

The second thematic discussion in Säve addressed the future of the forest in light of urban expansion. Säve is located on Hisingen island, where the city of Gothenburg is growing rapidly. Participants expressed concern about the weak protection status of forests compared to agricultural land, and many felt that municipal growth strategies often were valued higher than preserving forest values.

At this point, we have no quantitative metrics to evaluate the success or impact of the workshops, and we are unable to tell whether any practical outcomes have resulted from our workshops. It is important to remember that our case study is situated in an early phase of where no organised biodiversity initiatives exist locally among the involved forest owners. Our workshops should thus be seen as exploratory interventions – first steps towards building dialogue and communication among forest owners who usually rarely interact with each other or interact primarily with their closest neighbours. We did this in a horizontal setting as compared to conventional primarily informational forestry settings. Our goal was to help forest owners recognise the existence of shared interests, and how those do not always align with the interests of industrial forestry, or in the case of Säve, with urban land expansion. We believe we succeeded in creating an open, reflective space where participants could explore both tensions and common ground.

From our perspective, the workshops fulfilled this purpose. The discussions were open-ended, allowing us to observe how discussions evolved around selected themes, deviated from them and revealing both agreements and disagreements. In both Ambjörnarp and Istorp, interest in Continuous Cover Forestry was strong, although some participants were highly critical – typically based on alternative management goals or prior practical forestry experiences. Still, even among those with differing views, some shared concerns were also made clear. For example, in Ambjörnarp, the idea of a shared machinery pool sparked interest across participant groups, although practical limitations were also mentioned. In Istorp, EU-level forest policy and its implications for Swedish forest owners served as a common point of debate and concern.

In Säve, CCF also sparked interest, particularly as a method for managing small or inaccessible forest plots with less effort. However, the discussion around urban development sparked the most interest and debate among the participants. Several participants expressed a municipal imbalance between protections for agricultural land and forest land, and that the municipality prioritised municipal expansion over forest values. The views on this were not only critical, since the municipality needed space to grow, but the geographical prioritisation of the municipality was a point of some negative views since development primarily focused on areas with existing infrastructure and leaving others less developed. Some forest owners who had participated in housing development projects pointed to the possibility of integrating green spaces with new housing, but past experiences were also mentioned where valued forest landscapes had been entirely cleared for development. A few participants reported legal conflicts with the municipality over land expropriation for development purposes. While no clear solution was formulated, the

discussion showed that geographic proximity to the city played a major role in how vulnerable owners felt to urban development pressure.

Overall, the workshops revealed many of the practical opportunities and obstacles tied to environmentally sustainable forest management. Through these interventions, we initiated local conversations that likely would not have taken place otherwise.

1.5 Discussion

Our case study illustrates a complex interplay between often structural constraints and local agency in the possibilities or barriers for biodiversity innovations among private forest owners in southwestern Sweden. Based on the analysis of inclusion/exclusion mechanisms (section 4.2), niche innovators and innovations (sections 4.3 and 4.4) and interventions (section 4.5), here we discuss how transformative change may be supported or hindered in the context of private forest ownership.

One of the key results here is that exclusionary mechanisms based in forestry norms, knowledge structures, regulations and markets serve as large constraints for transformative change and biodiversity innovations in Swedish forestry sector, and among private forest owners. Even-aged silviculture remains the dominant form of managing forests, and the interviews that we conducted revealed that private forest owners often perceive their management as already environmentally friendly. This is primarily related to a prominent view among many respondents that the main environmental problem in Swedish forestry is an issue of scale rather than the practice itself. Small-scale forestry, regardless of management form, is largely perceived as less problematic than large-scale forestry. Although there might be some truth to partly motivate such views, this serves to limit more fundamental engagement with alternative forest management such as CCF. Historical legacies also negatively impact the adoption of CCF, especially since similar practices were made illegal in Sweden during the 20th century.

Knowledge structures are another factor impacting the upscaling and adoption of practices such as CCF. Access to different knowledge is uneven and highly influenced by background, previous experience and the use of advisory services. Paradoxically, newer or less experienced owners are at the same time more prone for less individual decision making due to a reliance on external advice, yet at the same time more open to new information. This is especially true with individuals actively seeking out new knowledge on their own to inform their forest management, as opposed to individuals who primarily use advisory services to manage a land use where they have little to no knowledge or interest.

Current regulatory frameworks in forestry simultaneously allow for a wide range of practices (e.g. the current forest legislation) yet creates a strong sense of distrust and influence of external restrictions when forest owners are encountered with environmental forestry regulations, especially species protection laws. These are widely seen as something externally imposed, often connected to financial disincentives for species protection, contrasting a view of biodiversity as a goal shared among people and society at large. In turn this contradicts a valuation of nature in itself, since the presence of certain species in practice means an instrumental devaluation of the land, even in cases where non-human actants such as capercaillie are highly valued and enjoyed by the forest owners.

Economic structures also serve as fundamental structural barriers for transformative change, since the current forest industry is structured around standardised production of pulp and timber products which restricts the range of available options for marketing more diverse forest values, such as high-quality timber. Such structures within the wider sector puts constraints on local innovations, and both workshops and interviews (including with innovator 2 and 3) reveal how practicing CCF largely depends on local arenas of consumption or exchange or finding specific pockets of use for the products of such forest management.

Personal connection to forests is an inclusive mechanism that has a potential to allow for more innovative use of the forest among private forest owners. Owners with emotional or place-based ties to their forest are more likely to deviate from industrial norms and prioritise other values, ecological, aesthetic or recreational, although primarily in parts of their forests to which those connections are more prominent. Many forest owners describe a geographic prioritisation in their forests for different purposes. Another arena for alternative practices and a fundamental critique of industrial norms is apparent with those forest owners who are also hunters, with concern for game species (especially moose). Here, the impression is that the wider forest industry is largely incompatible with the sustainable management of species for hunting. This opens for some alternative practices and a larger openness for pursuing other values in the forest, also including non-human actants.

Our local workshop interventions, where we discussed innovations and explored the wishes and needs of the forest owners, created novel horizontal spaces for dialogue among forest owners who usually do not interact with each other in such settings. This revealed largely the wide interest in alternative forest management, but also many of the constraints that actively work against a wider upscaling of such practices. While it was clear that similar activities in the future would create horizontal spaces for discussion and exchange beyond usual top-down forms of interaction between forest owners and forestry organisations, most issues were left open and unresolved. No solution was presented on how to implement more biodiversity-friendly forest management in practice, nor how to combine urbanisation with forest preservation.

Importantly, this points to the constraints restricting transformative change for biodiversity in the Swedish forestry sector. While most innovations listed here, such as CCF, biologist forest management plans and commercial bilberry production have potential for upscaling, a broader upscaling largely depends on systemic change in markets, global value chains, advisory systems and forest legislation. Innovator 2 is especially interesting in this regard, since they show local pockets exhibiting a certain 'resistance' to status quo norms may be organised using local social networks and collaboration. It is likely such collective local initiatives that might be a way forward for forest owners who want to pursue alternative practices, which over time might serve to initiate a wider transformation of the sector. However, overcoming current constraints is a massive undertaking which likely will need a combination of bottom-up and top-down initiatives and which is also dependent on the wider development including the shifts and turns of global markets, regional/national labour capacity and the urgency of ongoing climate and environmental crises.

Understanding transformative innovation through the eyes of the capercaillie

It was dark in the forest where I moved. The dense rows of low spruces enclosed me as I walked across the barren ground, dry twigs crackling beneath my claws. Dry, tight branches scraped against my feathers. My former display site had been transformed – the trees were gone, the ground laid bare. I searched for a new place, a new stage for my display, but so far, my search had been in vain. The forest here smelled monotonous, the visibility was poor, and it spelled danger for me. Who knows what hides among the branches?

I crouched low as I moved forward, alert to approaching threats, shifting from cover to cover in the dense forest. A deep track in the ground stopped me temporarily, where bare soil and pooled water lay exposed. Something very large had passed here, tearing up the earth. Brushwood filled the hollows. I flew cautiously over and made it to the other side.

Then suddenly, the forest opened up, and I was met by new scents – damp earth, moss, and old leaves. Old trees mixed with young ones, and light filtered down through the shifting canopy.

I moved across the ground, over mushrooms pushing up through the moss beneath my claws, over fallen trees where food could be found. Berry shrubs spread out before me,

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with blooming bilberry shoots. Further ahead I saw low deciduous trees, their leaves beginning to burst – tender, nourishing leaves for me. Again, I crouched, searching for danger in the forest. No sounds stirred my fears. The birds sang their spring songs. I passed a few tracks of an animal and torn moss, as if a tree had recently been dragged by. Only the large stump of the tree remained, and I jumped up onto it. The visibility in the forest was good. I listened again. No danger. Still watchful, I filled my chest, and a low bubbling rose in my throat. My first display in this place, where I could find peace, food, and safety.

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D2.2

Simeto River Alliance for Biodiversity

UNICT, Italy

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The deliverable was produced through differentiated contributions within the research unit, covering overall coordination, field research, data collection, data analysis, text drafting, and final content revision.

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Summary

Summary of Deliverable

Located in inner eastern Sicily, the Simeto River and its Valley constitute a territory of high ecological, cultural, and historical value currently facing profound socio-ecological challenges. Extending over about 4,200 km² and including the fertile Plain of Catania, the valley is shaped by a dense interaction between natural and human systems. Its riverine corridor – fragmented by dams, weirs, and extensive irrigation infrastructure – reveals how biodiversity loss interlaces with industrial agriculture, energy production, and governance fragmentation. This makes the Simeto Valley an exemplary case for studying how local actors understand and address biodiversity decline through innovative, participatory and transformative practices.

Three interdependent pressures define the crisis: (1) the fragmentation of aquatic ecosystems caused by heavy engineering, which disrupts ecological corridors and habitats; (2) the persistence of intensive monoculture farming reliant on agrochemicals and mechanisation, leading to soil depletion and pollution aggravated by drought and wildfires; (3) and the conversion of farmland into industrial-scale photovoltaic fields enabled by the collapse of citrus monoculture and declining land values. Together, these processes reveal a socio-ecological system dominated by extractive dynamics but also animated by civic mobilisation and experimentation.

The case study, grounded in Participatory Action Research, was conducted by the University of Catania in close collaboration with the Participatory Praesidium of the Simeto River Agreement a long-standing civic network uniting municipalities, communities, and associations across the basin. This partnership ensured inclusiveness, co-design, and the translation of research findings into collective action. The study engaged a diverse set of actors, such as farmers (both conventional and alternative), livestock breeders, water authorities and infrastructure managers, multinational energy companies, civil-society organisations, and local institutions. Their interactions shape the ecological and governance dynamics of the Simeto system.

Research activities developed along three interlinked strands:

1. Re-inhabiting the river through historical and ethnographic analysis of dwelling and agroecological practices.
2. Investigating irrigation governance and farmer cooperation around water infrastructures.
3. Mapping the socio-ecological and spatial impacts of industrial photovoltaic expansion through collaborative GIS.

The process fostered sustained co-learning between researchers and local actors, deepening mutual understanding of biodiversity-related challenges and enabling the co-production of actionable knowledge. Participatory outcomes – such as a permanent exhibition and a two-week territorial festival in 2025 – contributed to public debate and institutional dialogue.

Overall, the Simeto Valley case highlights how place-based alliances, civic participation, and plural knowledge systems can sustain more just, democratic, and biodiversity-oriented forms of territorial governance, aligning with BIOTraCes Theory of Transformative Change.

Transformative biodiversity innovations (D2.2)

1.1 Analysis of Inclusion/Exclusion Mechanisms

Exclusionary practices and inclusive mechanisms materialise deeper socio-ecological relations, registers of meaning, and cultural representations. Within capitalist dynamics, human–nature relations are framed through the logics of commodification, profit extraction, and capital accumulation (Smith & Harvey 2008). Consequently, exclusionary practices often emerge through the privatisation of ecosystem components destined for incorporation into business schemes, while simultaneously excluding other beings—human and non-human—from using these as life worlds. Conversely, mechanisms capable of including diverse perspectives on biodiversity typically develop externally to or at the margins of dominant economic practices, which remain embedded in the logic of endless accumulation.

The exclusion of alternative and marginal perspectives on biodiversity in the Simeto Valley stems from a dominant understanding of the ecosystem as a reservoir of resources and, therefore, of exchange value to be extracted and accumulated (Buscher et al., 2012). This worldview, central to the capitalist mode of production, is underpinned by values of opportunism, competition, and productivism—social attitudes oriented toward profit maximisation and indifferent to elements of the ecosystem that cannot be monetised.

These values and attitudes are embodied in the agro-industrial model of both citrus and wheat monoculture, which during the 1900s has transformed socio-ecological relations and reshaped the cultural, ecological, and social landscape in the image of intensive agriculture. The monocultural system has not only generated vast orange groves that continue to define the valley’s landscape but has also altered its micro-scale composition, including relationships between plants, humans, and other species.

Ethnographic conversations conducted during the first research strand reveal the depth of the transformations imposed on citrus trees to meet production requirements. A key example is the continuous development of pruning techniques designed to produce shorter trees for easier harvests and optimise row arrangements to maximise productivity per unit of land. Although effective from a business standpoint, these practices profoundly alter ecosystem equilibria, reinforcing competitive hierarchies among species rather than cooperation. These different ways of relating to the territory and to cultivated species are a point of generational conflict and mark the distinction between ways of life, dwelling styles, and cultivation practices. As Sandro (a pseudonym), one of the valley’s inhabitants who practices agroecology, explains, the choice to move to the countryside made a fracture visible for him:

“Transforming a part of the olive grove... let’s say that my goal when I bought this place was the desire to reconnect with the land. My father worked in the countryside, so I’ve always had that connection, even if there’s always a generational clash, right? So, with that generational clash, you distance yourself a bit because of the older generation’s approach which—let’s say—reflects how conventional agriculture developed over time. Obviously, it affected the previous generation, so when you talk to older people, they use synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, a more industrial kind of agriculture. I’ve always... let’s say, from my point of view, that way of doing things never really resonated with me” (Interview, 29.11.2024)

Moreover, elders and those accustomed to monocultural agro-industry frequently view spontaneous plant species or secondary crops as “competitors” to orange trees and their profit potential. This illustrates how values, attitudes, flows of knowledge, and economic practices intertwine to marginalise diverse understandings of biodiversity.

This capitalist logic perpetuates the notion that the valley is not a space for coexistence but rather an extraction site, where monoculture farming enables accumulation while

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producing residual toxicity from fertilisers and pesticides. The productivity of this model is leveraged to discredit alternative agricultural approaches as economically unviable. As fieldwork indicates, permaculture and organic farmers often feel perceived as eccentric or unserious by conventional producers, who equate “proper agriculture” with industrial efficiency and output.

The same extractive rationale has expanded into the energy sector. Since the 1960s, natural gas extraction, followed by hydropower and more recently industrial-scale photovoltaic energy, has consolidated the region’s dependence on extractive development. The Simeto River has been heavily engineered, with two major dams and six hydropower plants permanently altering its flow, fragmenting habitat corridors, and excluding conservation practices compatible with a free-flowing river.

The ongoing expansion of agro-photovoltaic plants reproduces this logic. Approximately 6000 hectares are projected to be covered with solar panels in the coming years, much of it converted from abandoned citrus lands. This process, driven by the chronic crisis of the agricultural sector, leads farmers to rent their land for long-term contracts with energy companies. Carlo (farmer - pseudonym) explains that “For many decades, these lands were farmed intensively to produce citrus and grain, which are now being replaced with panels. From a citrus monoculture, we are transitioning to a silicon monoculture” (Interview, 15 11 2024). As a result, a new industrial landscape is emerging, signalling, at a deeper level, that the inclusion of alternative biodiversity perspectives is further constrained.

Regulatory frameworks exacerbate exclusion by limiting community participation in zoning and permitting processes. Local actors have minimal influence over where and how new plants are installed, leaving alternative territorial visions with little chance to emerge.

Conversely, through participatory research within BIOTraCes, inclusive approaches to human–nature relations are advanced in the Simeto Valley, particularly through the Simeto Ecomuseum, which represents an innovative model for engaging communities with the river and non-human entities. The Ecomuseum aims to empower marginalised groups by recognising their agency in shaping the landscape. It does so by promoting walking itineraries and a permanent exhibition that integrates archival data and ethnographic materials to historicise and revitalise the community’s relationship with the river. This model fosters a deeper awareness of ecological interdependence and opens pathways for the collective stewardship of biodiversity.

Similarly, alternative and permaculture-inspired agricultural practices offer inclusive mechanisms that restore disrupted relationships between humans and other life forms. These approaches reduce dependence on water, pesticides, and herbicides while reintroducing species diversity. Building upon local micro-practices, they provide a foundation for long-term biodiversity resilience and more equitable socio-ecological relations.

Finally, the collaborative and critical mapping of agro-photovoltaic plants, developed through cooperation between the UNICT BIOTraCes team and the Presidio, constitutes both a scientific and democratic innovation. By compiling georeferenced data from archives, surveys, and interviews, the mapping project will produce a publicly accessible cartography showing how energy infrastructures intersect with biodiversity and cultural heritage. This instrument will strengthen evidence-based policymaking, empower civil society with strategic knowledge, and enhance the inclusivity of territorial planning. The establishment of a joint management collective between the university and the Presidio will ensure the map’s long-term sustainability as a collaborative tool for pluralising biodiversity governance.

Concluding remarks

Exclusionary practices in the Simeto Valley derive from an extractive worldview that treats ecosystems as resources for accumulation, marginalising alternative ways of relating to nature. Intensive agriculture and industrial-scale energy production reproduce this logic, excluding local actors and biodiversity perspectives. Inclusive mechanisms—such as the Simeto Ecomuseum, permaculture practices, and collaborative mapping—counter this exclusion by promoting participatory engagement, ecological care, and plural knowledge systems. These initiatives demonstrate that transformative biodiversity governance requires not only technical innovation but also social inclusion and cultural recognition, embedding local voices at the heart of ecological restoration.

1.2 Niche Innovators and Key Players

The Participatory Praesidium as a Driver of Innovation

In the case study Simeto River Alliance for Biodiversity, grassroots organisations and movements that have gathered over the years around the Participatory Praesidium of the Simeto River Agreement (Presidio Partecipativo)—the Societal Partner of the BIOTraCes project for the University of Catania—play a crucial role as innovators in the research area. However, to fully understand their influence and contribution to biodiversity restoration, it is important to clarify how the notion of “innovation” has evolved within this context over time.

Between the early 2000s and 2015, the group of activists in the Simeto River Valley, which had not yet taken the form of the Presidio, gradually developed a new approach to social innovation, focusing on how changes in practices or institutions could trigger deeper transformations in values, culture, and participatory paradigms, generating broader policy and regulatory effects (Moore et al., 2015). Realising that individual or emergency-driven initiatives—such as Orti di Pace G. Rosano and Reforestation in Contrada Niccolò—lacked the strength to achieve lasting change, the group decided to consolidate institutional relationships by promoting open innovation within public–private relations (Saija, 2016).

Supported by the expertise of the University of Catania, particularly the Department of Civil Engineering and Architecture (DiCAR), the group co-designed the Simeto River Agreement, a framework intended to create a permanent debate forum that was not only consultative but also deliberative. This approach was deeply innovative compared to standard Italian river agreements (contratti di fiume), which are primarily consultative community tools. The Presidio aimed to influence territorial policies; however, the way the River Agreement was signed—amid strong media and political pressure and in the absence of regulatory backing—quickly led to the failure of this experience during its first three years (2015–2018). As several members of societal partner later reflected, one of the core challenges of that phase was the push toward innovation as a goal, which often stretched the organisational capacity of the Presidium. As a participant noted during FG2, *“The pursuit of innovation for its own sake, as in other processes, became a limitation for the Presidio, as it absorbed a great deal of energy while at the same time leaving behind many micro-practices and concrete actions that we are only now carrying forward [...]”* (15/03/2025 – Participant, FG2). The attempt to innovate too rapidly suffered from the same weaknesses that had characterised earlier activism: a strong drive for change that lacked stable institutional foundations.

Pragmatic Reorientation and Incremental Change

This experience led the Presidio, now an umbrella association whose horizontally diffused model was being replicated by other initiatives, to deeply rethink its role and mission. It adopted a more pragmatic approach to innovation, centred on targeted project-based initiatives that, unlike past efforts, involved local administrators and built upon the experience of the River Agreement. This evolution ideally brought the Presidium back to

its origins, with what may appear as pilot initiatives (e.g., Break Free, Science Trip), yet these differ significantly from earlier efforts as they are integrated into a broader and more coherent framework. While maintaining its strong orientation toward innovation, between 2018 and 2024 the Praesidium shifted its strategy from immediate, deep innovation toward incremental and context-sensitive change, recognising the complexity of the socio-ecological system.

Today, the Presidio can be defined as an open social innovator pursuing a process-based model of transformative change. However, it cannot be considered a niche innovator in the strict sense (Geels & Schot, 2007), since it no longer operates from a marginal position but has become a central actor in local and regional policymaking.

Institutionalisation, Identity, and Participatory Governance

Over two decades, this group has introduced new languages and approaches to thinking and acting in the Simeto River Valley. From this process, the very identity of the “Simetini” has emerged, fostering a sense of unity within a historically fragmented context. This evolution has transformed both external perceptions—how the Valley’s municipalities are viewed from outside—and internal ones—how local communities perceive themselves in relation to neighbouring territories such as Catania, Enna, and the Nebrodi area. Activists within the Presidio have progressively developed new forms of social interaction and participatory democracy, positioning this collective as a key innovator at both regional and national levels.

Over the years, the Presidio’s practices have also focused on mitigating harmful environmental processes. At the macro level, activists initially opposed the construction of an incinerator in Contrada Cannizzola near the Simeto River, later halting plans for another landfill in Contrada Muglia and supporting the closure and remediation of the landfill in Contrada Valanghe d’Inverno in Motta S. Anastasia. Beyond these conflicts, the Presidio has promoted various initiatives to reconnect urban areas with the river, particularly through the Simeto Ecomuseum (EcoSI) launched in 2019. Over six years, the Ecomuseum has developed multiple projects, including a network of organic farmers through the Simeto Biodistrict (established in 2015).

Project-Based Innovation and Environmental Action

Alongside these broader interventions, several specific initiatives have increased ecological awareness, promoting local environmental stewardship and biodiversity protection. Notable examples include:

- ✓ LIFE Simeto Res (2015–2018), aimed at regulating water cycles in peri-urban areas, reducing soil sealing and uncontrolled cementification, and creating green zones for runoff management.
- ✓ PO FESR Ponte Barca (2017–2020), which focused on the Ponte Barca SIC area, establishing a civic monitoring network and designing nesting islands (not yet implemented).
- ✓ EcoSI Itineraries (2020–ongoing), a participatory monitoring tool promoted by the Simeto Ecomuseum.
- ✓ Open Science (2023–2025), which engages school-aged children in citizen science and river monitoring.
- ✓ Coltiviamo Bellezza (2024–ongoing), creating a biodiversity-rich urban garden in Paternò and promoting community participation in green space care.

These projects illustrate the Praesidium’s long-standing commitment to sustainable practices, directly addressing the Valley’s environmental challenges. Over time, this social collective has gained legitimacy, shifting from a peripheral role in local governance to a central position, particularly in municipalities that are part of the River Agreement.

However, this newfound centrality also risks alienating its grassroots base—a challenge that remains central to the Presidio’s current transformation.

Structural Gaps and Peripheral Networks

The BIOTraCes research has identified two interrelated phenomena within this evolution. First, the Presidio’s efforts have concentrated primarily on urban areas, while remote rural zones—often key to biodiversity regeneration—remain more difficult to engage. Second, the Presidio has not yet fully connected with the existing informal rural networks that sustain local socio-ecological knowledge. Addressing these limitations is essential for strengthening its transformative reach.

From this collaboration, the UNICT research team expanded its inquiry to include other niche innovators operating outside or at the periphery of the Presidio’s core network.

New Farmers and Dwellers as Niche Innovators

Among niche innovators operating outside or at the periphery of the Presidio’s core network, the new farmers and dwellers of the Simeto Valley stand out. Many are young, educated adults—often without family ties to the region—who have chosen to live in rural areas and pursue organic, permaculture-inspired farming. Rejecting monoculture and agro-industrial models, they experiment with regenerative practices aimed at restoring soil fertility and biodiversity. Beyond their technical methods, they also build networks of solidarity and mutual learning, creating social-ecological infrastructures that allow newcomers to settle and collaborate despite limited economic means.

Their relationships with traditional farmers are marked by both proximity and distance. While sharing the same territory, they often operate in parallel social worlds, though the potential for exchange remains. Conventional farmers nonetheless preserve valuable knowledge on hybrid irrigation systems—combining earthen channels (*saje*) and storage tanks (*gebbie*)—that can inspire future retro-innovation (Zagata et al., 2020).

Low-Impact Dwelling and Retro-Innovation

Another dimension of innovation lies in low-impact dwelling practices (*abitare leggero*) and new relationships with water. These approaches involve the removal of buried plastic piping and the creation of small ponds and open irrigation channels that restore permeability between soil and water. Through processes of lithification (Luisetti, 2023), these structures mimic the river’s own ecological dynamics, fostering biodiversity and reconfiguring human–non-human relations. These forms of retro-innovation (Zagata et al., 2020) do not simply imitate traditional techniques but refunctionalise them in the face of contemporary climate challenges.

Despite their significance, these niche innovators remain largely invisible within political and institutional arenas. Their marginality limits their capacity for influence but also allows greater autonomy in experimentation. Conversely, conventional farmers—while not typically innovative—maintain fundamental techniques and knowledge that could support transitions toward more sustainable practices.

Renewable Energy Communities (RECs)

Another emerging group of niche innovators consisted of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) established in collaboration with the Presidio. These initiatives, developed through a process of dialogue and co-design between citizens, local associations, small producers, and researchers, sought to democratise energy production by promoting local ownership, collective investment, and fair redistribution of benefits. Grounded in the principles of energy justice, solidarity, and participatory governance, the RECs redefined the ecological

transition as a social process rather than a purely technical one. Their cooperative structures aligned decarbonisation with community welfare and biodiversity protection, reducing land consumption while revitalising existing infrastructures and built environments.

Collaborative Mapping Networks

Equally significant were the grassroots organisations that participated in the collaborative mapping of agro-photovoltaic plants, developed through the cooperation between BIOTraCes researchers and the Praesidium. Specifically, the Praesidium played a crucial facilitative role, connecting local associations such as Sciara Viva (Belpasso) and Legambiente Ancipa (Troina) and coordinating collective field activities. Together, these actors combined local ecological knowledge, GIS-based data collection, and community-based monitoring to create an open, critical cartography linking energy infrastructures to biodiversity and cultural heritage. Beyond its technical output, this collaborative process strengthened participatory governance by empowering citizens to analyse land-use transformations, challenge exclusionary planning, and co-design more just and biodiversity-oriented territorial futures, embedding research within local networks of care and environmental stewardship. As Francesca (activist – pseudonym) pointed out :

“when you talk to some local officer enthusiast for these large photovoltaic plants, they often say «what’s wrong with putting panels on such empty lands...?», sometimes they even say «on these deserts»...because they just imply that the lands they target are empty, void of any life or story, uninhabited. That is why the map is important...because it shows exactly the contrary, it puts the plants into a context that is full of life, story and inhabitants!!” (Interview, 23/09/2025).

Concluding Remarks

The Simeto Valley hosts a rich network of innovators operating across civic, agricultural, and energy domains. The Participatory Praesidium anchors long-term participatory governance, while new farmers, RECs, and collaborative mapping networks experiment with novel forms of collective agency linking biodiversity, justice, and sustainability. Together, they embody the BIOTraCes principles of pluralising knowledge, empowering local actors, politicising structural inequalities, and embedding transformative practices in governance. Despite limitations of scale and visibility, these actors provide tangible pathways for transformative change, reconfiguring human–nature relations within the Simeto socio-ecological system.

1.3 Scalable Bottom-Up Innovations for Transformative Change

Several bottom-up innovations have emerged in the case study: new practices of the Simeto Ecomuseum focused on rediscovering the landscape and fostering multispecies agency; young farmers/dwellers who break with agro-industrial traditions and build associative and mutual-aid networks; civil-society actors and municipalities advocating alternative energy production while critically opposing the uncontrolled expansion of agro-photovoltaic plants presented as a “green,” impact-free solution; and conventional farmers who possess, share, and apply practical knowledge in water management, farming, and animal husbandry in synergy with the more-than-human world—knowledges that could become niche innovations if scaled to shift prevailing production patterns.

The Simeto Ecomuseum

The Simeto Ecomuseum can be considered a locally scalable bottom-up innovation. Linked to the activism of the Presidio, it was launched in 2019 after a participatory mapping process involving residents and territorial actors. It creates “[...] an agreement through which a community commits to taking care of a territory, implemented by means of a shared and integrated project for the protection, enhancement, maintenance, and cultural production of a geographically, socially, and economically homogeneous area, characterized by distinctive historical, cultural, tangible and intangible, landscape, and environmental features¹.” Though currently challenged by an unsustainable reliance on volunteer labour, the Ecomuseum aims to innovate methods, expand relationships, and consolidate its role as a territorial actor in dialogue with associations, the municipality, and economic stakeholders. Drawing on research materials, archival data, and the support of BIOTraCes researchers and professionals, it laid the groundwork for a permanent exhibition in Paternò, at the Presidio’s premises.

With a deeply place-based approach and sensitivity to territorial transformations, the Ecomuseum departs from business-as-usual policies that struggle to envisage any coherent strategy for territorial enhancement. Operating in a marginalised socio-cultural and environmental context, it promotes local knowledge and economies to address drivers of marginalisation—such as limited knowledge of the valley’s history, which fuels emotional and physical detachment. Within BIOTraCes, the Simeto Ecomuseum has focused on biodiversity, initiating a participatory action research process that valorises present-day marginal practices (e.g., livestock raising, fishing) as integral components of historical ecological systems. By interpreting these practices as ways of inhabiting the river and as elements of a complex ecological fabric, it adopts a holistic, historically grounded view of biodiversity (beyond quantitative indicators).

Through school initiatives and youth engagement, the Simeto Ecomuseum’s innovation is cross-cutting and inclusive. With its community base and experience in territorial micro-economies, it has the potential to scale by framing biodiversity as the outcome of relational, productive, and historical ties. This trajectory is strengthened by exchanges with other ecomuseums (e.g., the May 25–June 8, 2025 festival) and by establishing the permanent exhibition with BIOTraCes support.

Grounded in environmental history, multispecies agency, and biodiversity, the permanent centre holds long-term transformative potential. If adequately supported, the Simeto Ecomuseum could become a reference actor and interlocutor for local administrations on river issues and transformations—functioning as a platform for dialogue among diverse actors and territories. It represents a scalable bottom-up innovation because it builds a territorial narrative that includes diverse ways of inhabiting the land. While aligned with conservation and nature protection, it addresses biodiversity place-specifically, valuing history, practices, and marginalised voices.

Agricultural and Water Management Innovations by farmers/dwellers

Farmers and residents inspired by permaculture are introducing small-scale biodiversity innovations in water management and cultivation. To make water visible and functional to ecological processes, they create micro-wetlands on their plots, countering the dominant, buried-pipe model. By constructing small basins and designing earthen irrigation channels (emulating traditional saje without cement), they retain soil moisture and support diverse plant and insect species. Some are removing legacy plastic piping, painstakingly unearthing networks installed decades ago that have become an invisible toxic infrastructure of the valley.

¹ Regional Law of Sicily No. 16/2014, Article 2

Agronomically, while continuing oranges and olives for economic viability, they experiment with additional crops and species to enrich soils and foster biodiversity—often selecting nitrogen-fixing plants. Combined with a rejection of pesticides, these practices enable gradual soil regeneration and significant gains in biodiversity. It is important to emphasize that these innovations related to agriculture and water management are closely connected to the choice to practice a way of dwelling that is alternative to the agro-industrial citrus system. One example comes from the interview with Clara (a pseudonym), who, although she has always lived in a town in the valley, chose to move to the countryside. In recalling her family's history, Clara tries to trace these transformations:

"I don't know whether these lands, when they were only oranges' orchards, were actually inhabited. I think they were inhabited only for the amount of time the farmer spent cultivating them — that is, the time spent working the land. At least, this is what I believe was traditionally done: you stayed on the land to do the work and then, of course, you went back home. [...] And today, in this sense, things are changing a bit, perhaps also in the way people perceive the countryside. There is a return to a different kind of relationship — one that is not only focused on obtaining basic necessities, but also on experiencing the countryside as something connected to the home, you know? Seeing the countryside also, in a way, as a home" (Interview, 23.11.2024)

This potential emerges precisely as climate impacts and water-management failures intensify, making alternative agriculture a viable path for those wishing to remain connected to the land.

The innovations show early scalability: from one advanced permaculture initiative started in 2012, at least four additional farmers in the same area now manage ~2-hectare plots with ecological practices. If water innovations (micro-wetlands, pipe removal) were diffused through broader networks, they could catalyse transformative interest among conventional farmers still adhering to business-as-usual practices.

Economic sustainability remains a core challenge. Consequently, innovations are low-cost and best suited to those willing to forgo the productivity levels and standardised outputs of chemically intensive agriculture. Many conventional farmers perceive wetland creation as a waste of water rather than a biodiversity and resilience strategy. By restoring species typical of the traditional "Sicilian Garden," new farmers seek to revive pre-monoculture practices, aligning—at the level of values—with older knowledge. However, such exchanges are rare, as dominant "conventional" knowledge is now tied to citrus monoculture rather than the self-sufficiency landscapes largely absent for decades.

Ultimately, the transformative potential lies not only in techniques but in the social, relational, and affective infrastructure that enables these inhabitants to live differently in the valley. These informal networks, which support biodiversity-positive practices, show periods of disintegration and reassembly, reflecting the economic and existential precarity underpinning them.

Bottom-up innovations in the energy sector

Scalable bottom-up energy innovations take multiple forms. First, the emergence of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) carries transformative potential by democratising decision-making and information-sharing, reducing consumption, raising awareness, and gradually shifting away from high-energy consumption models. Their significance lies not only in material outcomes but in their inclusive constitution, bringing together individuals, associations, businesses, and institutions to form networks of knowledge and support. Originating in participatory processes with BIOTraCes involvement, RECs introduce participation into an otherwise highly technical domain, breaking with business-as-usual.

A second innovation is the participatory mapping of large-scale agro-photovoltaic plants. Launched by BIOTraCes, it engages local actors and municipalities in a participatory

process that is methodologically relevant in a context largely lacking such tools. Beyond method, the innovation lies in building a knowledge base from which mobilisation and advocacy can emerge—clarifying how large-scale agro-photovoltaics reshape landscape and economy. The mapping responds to the wave of large-scale investments in agro-photovoltaic energy impacting the Valley.

Findings suggest that the siting and proliferation of infrastructures frequently escape both residents' and institutions' control. The mapping can help municipalities and citizens have a stronger voice amid rapid land appropriation. By highlighting desertification risks—economic, social, and agricultural—this innovation can ultimately support biodiversity. While agro photovoltaics may allow some under-panel crops, these do not contribute meaningfully to biodiversity or farmer livelihoods, who increasingly rely on land rental rather than production.

Innovations in “conventional” agriculture

There are also bottom-up innovations to enhance or revive within “conventional” agriculture—especially synergies between production and the more-than-human. Although traditional farmers and livestock breeders have applied monoculture with an extractive approach, they also maintain micro-management practices that enable biodiversity to persist and even improve.

For example, *sulla coronaria*² cultivation for fodder supports pollinators, and the valley's artificial reservoirs sustain migratory birds through fish–bird trophic relations. As a sheep breeder explained, recalling past practices, “*Bees are dying because in the Plain we used to grow a lot of sulla. Practically every household, every farmhouse had a flock of sheep, and sulla was one of the best and most important feeds for dairy animals and for fattening. Bees once relied on sulla, which was a rich and nourishing plant; now they die because they no longer have that resource. I remember that when bees found sulla flowers, they would swarm, they would leave the hives in great numbers. They don't do that anymore because this plant is no longer there.*” (Sheep breeder³ – 20/05/2024) Though overshadowed by destructive production methods, such practices are niches to leverage. Building on deep farmer–land–water relations, they could become innovations if scaled, progressively tempering harmful monoculture logics and the broader production mindset now in economic crisis.

The same applies to water management. Farmers and breeders share informal micro-management rooted in neighbourly relations and sociality. In contrast to the centralised consortium model, these practices could render water management more rational and sustainable, while empowering farmers and breeders as inhabitants and guardians of the valley's waters.

Concluding remarks

Bottom-up innovations in the Simeto Valley include the Simeto Ecomuseum, permaculture-inspired farming and water practices, RECs, participatory mapping of agro-photovoltaics, and biodiversity-supporting micro-practices in traditional agriculture. Their transformative

² The *sulla coronaria* is a leguminous fodder plant that produces a striking red flower. Commonly found throughout the Mediterranean basin, it is known in Sicilian as *sudda*.

³ The interlocutor is a livestock breeder from a seven-generation family tradition, who fears that he will be the last to continue this line of work. His farm has always been in the lower part of the river, near the Simeto Oasis, where the family operates both a livestock farm and a dairy. His concern is palpable, as is his constant reference to deeply empirical observations regarding the presence and disappearance of plants and animals in his surroundings.

potential of these initiatives depends on scaling low-cost techniques, strengthening social networks, and embedding participatory tools in governance. Early effects include soil regeneration, biodiversity gains, and greater civic oversight of energy siting. Equitable access remains a challenge, but these innovations collectively pluralise knowledge, support cultural recognition, and diversify local socio-ecological strategies.

1.4 Initial Mapping of Interventions

The interventions for transformative change identified in the BIOTraCes Italian case study of the Simeto valley build on niche innovators' actions and practices, which are actively shaping pathways toward socio-ecological transformation. Across the three interlinked research strands, we examine how farmers, cultural practitioners, and environmental stewards mobilise knowledge, practices, and infrastructures in ways that challenge dominant models and lay groundwork for systemic change. These interventions are not only responses to existing conditions; they are prefigurative practices that anticipate and prototype alternative futures for biodiversity, energy, and territorial governance.

Before detailing the initial interventions, it is useful to summarise initiatives enacted by niche innovators. Fieldwork shows that local cultural actors and environmental advocates are reclaiming the river as a multispecies ecosystem and multispecies homescape (Schuumarn 2024), narrating its history through extinction, ecological memory, and more-than-human agency. Since April 2024, regular meetings have supported a collaborative inquiry into the ecological and symbolic marginalisation of the river and its species. By recentring the river as a political and ecological actor, these innovators contest anthropocentric and extractivist paradigms—documenting loss while reclaiming space for the river within future visions of the valley.

Fieldwork also highlights the role of young farmers/dwellers —many of them niche innovators rejecting monoculture—in shaping biodiversity-supportive agricultural practices and reconfiguring water infrastructure governance. From May to December 2024, multiple encounters enabled close engagement with these farmers and their support networks. Their actions—rooted in agroecology, ecological repair, and collaborative experimentation—constitute a clear departure from dominant agricultural regimes while opening new spaces of community-making, care, and stewardship. A co-designed workshop at the June 2025 Simeto Festival will further refine these innovations and situate them within a broader territorial strategy.

Niche innovators are also active in energy, co-conducting with the UNICT research team a participatory mapping process. Members of two grassroots organisations (Troina and Belpasso) were involved from the earliest conceptual stages—co-shaping tools, categories, and modes of analysis. Through iterative workshops, the mapping has enabled cycles of reflection, imagination, and strategic planning. Beyond diagnosis, it functions as an infrastructure supporting territorial actors in contesting speculative land deals, visualising spatial inequalities, and advancing situated visions for a just energy transition.

Intervention 1 — Permanent Interpretation Center (Simeto Ecomuseum)

Together with the Participatory Presidium, we organised a permanent exhibition for the Simeto Ecomuseum. It will display archival documents (1889–1940s) on life of and along the river before heavy regimentation (weirs and dams), revealing interactions among human and more-than-human communities that are now invisible or lost. The core message— “there is and there has been a river”—responds to current seasonal disappearance due to droughts and withdrawals.

The centre includes fieldwork materials from the three research stands (photos, video, interview excerpts) to integrate and return research results to the Societal Partner and community. The Presidio enriched the exhibition with images and documents on the

struggles that have enlivened the Valley and are part of a common political and social heritage (e.g., the 2002 protest against the waste-to-energy plant).

The exhibition aims to consolidate a place-based narrative, strengthen collective memory, and embed biodiversity awareness within a publicly accessible, permanent space.

Intervention 2 – Interactive Web Cartography (Agro-Photovoltaic Plants)

We are translating the collaborative mapping of industrial-scale agro-photovoltaics into an interactive online cartography. Designed as a public digital tool, it provides georeferenced information on the ecological transition in the Simeto Valley—specifically, data directly and indirectly related to agro-photovoltaic plants.

The map is intended to generate impact across three fronts:

- Research: consolidated evidence base.
- Local policymaking: support for territorial planning.
- Democratic participation: public oversight of land-cover changes linked to photovoltaic production.

Two access modes will be available: consultation and data entry. Registered/verified users will be able to report energy and non-energy objects, promoting active participation in monitoring processes.

Intervention 3 – Two-Week Festival (May 25 – June 8, 2025)

A two-week Festival connected themes emerging from research through the following programme:

- A debate on Ecomuseums as instruments to counter biodiversity and cultural-heritage degradation in the Simeto Valley.
- A multispecies Itinerary along the river's middle course (Santa Domenica ENEL's intake and agroecological farm) narrating more-than-human histories of co-habitation in and with the river. The itinerary connected socioecological relations to landscape transformations (agriculture, infrastructuring) by highlighting the complex and often conflictual relations with the river.
- A workshop on regenerative farming techniques (syntropic agriculture) focusing on historical/geographical specificities, and climate change impacts. Its goals were to strengthen solidarity networks among farmers, connect with experts on regenerative agriculture, share local knowledge supporting biodiversity, and link biodiversity to ways of inhabiting land.
- A day dedicated to Micro and Macro Water Infrastructure that explored the complex material and symbolic dimensions of water in the Simeto Valley. In the morning, participants engaged in a deep mapping session at an organic farm in Contrada Nicolò, led by a local activist. This activity focused on tracing the journey of water through its multiple infrastructures—both materials, such as canals and pipes, and immaterial, such as communication networks and local knowledge systems—revealing how these layers shaped ecological and social relations. In the afternoon, attention shifted to the macro-infrastructures of the Simeto River, examining their historical and contemporary impacts on biodiversity and socio-ecological interactions. Through discussions with experts, researchers, activists, and local authorities, the session outlined a political ecology of water in the Simeto Valley and presented the Passo Martino weir as a case study of potential dismantling, aimed at partially restoring the river's ecological continuity and re-establishing its role as a living, interconnected ecosystem.
- A day dedicated to the theme of energy as a space for reflection, debate, and planning on the relationship between energy production and the shaping of territory. In this context, the event wove together two key topics: large-scale agro-

agro-photovoltaic plants and Renewable Energy Communities (RECs), using as a common thread the materiality, politics, meaning, and imagination of the ecological transition in Simeto and Sicily.

Concluding Remarks

These initial interventions translate niche innovations into tangible actions: a permanent interpretation centre anchors multispecies histories in a public space; an interactive cartography supports research, policymaking, and democratic oversight; and a territorial festival activates shared learning on biodiversity, water, agriculture, and energy. Collectively, they challenge business-as-usual approaches by centring participation, memory, and situated knowledge. Their contribution lies in restoring relations between communities and ecosystems, re-politicising decisions on land and energy, and enabling equitable management of biodiversity. These interventions provide a practical springboard for the actions foreseen in Task 2.4, aligning experimentation with transformative governance.

Discussion

The analysis conducted in the Simeto Valley highlights a socio-ecological context deeply marked by tensions and discontinuities, yet also by opportunities for transformative innovation. The river and its basin constitute a space where contrasting agricultural practices, divergent visions of the human–nature relationship, and experiments in community governance intersect. These efforts seek to balance the pressures of intensive production models while resisting new forms of extractive exploitation of the territory. Within this framework, biodiversity emerges not merely as a threatened resource but as a field of political and cultural negotiation.

One of the most significant findings concerns the persistence of intensive agriculture, which continues to dominate large areas of the territory. This model produces a dual effect: on the one hand, it sustains segments of the local economy and maintains connections to national and global markets, thereby perpetuating logics of exploitation, marginality, and inequality—both economic and representational. On the other hand, it contributes to biodiversity loss, soil depletion, and aquifer reduction, while entering into a problematic dialogue with older landscape-care practices (Calcaterra, 1986; Lupo, 1990). While some farmers still retain synergistic relations with nature and local knowledge, the increasing mechanisation of agriculture has substantially eroded such traditional practices of care. The persistence of intensive farming should not be read merely as resistance to change, but as the outcome of an economic and political system that rewards high yields and global integration, making alternative paths costly and risky for most farmers.

Alongside this scenario, heterogeneous experiences of alternative farmers have emerged, introducing practices inspired by agroecology, permaculture, and rural multifunctionality. These actors—often returning migrants, urban dwellers, or individuals seeking to reconnect with the land—do not represent a purely marginal phenomenon. They experiment with models grounded in crop diversification, short supply chains, and direct relationships with consumer communities. Their presence carries transformative potential yet also generates tensions with traditional farmers. This friction manifests in multiple ways: while traditional producers may view “new” inhabitants as pursuing economically unrealistic practices, the latter often criticise established farms for their inertia and dependence on global market logics.

Such dialectics, far from being merely conflictual, also create opportunities for collective learning, enabling new forms of hybridisation and mutual contamination. Informal exchange networks, farmers’ markets, and community festivals demonstrate the possibility

of alliances across different actor groups, even if these attempts have yet to consolidate into systemic change.

A further layer of complexity arises from the spread of agro-photovoltaic energy. While framed as a green innovation promising emissions reduction, in the Simeto Valley it often functions as a form of socioecological dispossession. Large-scale installations on agricultural land intensify pressure on biodiversity, transform landscapes, and reinforce extractive logics of resource appropriation. Community perspectives on such projects remain ambivalent: for some, they offer economic opportunities; for others, they embody a development model that sacrifices ecological and cultural values. The much-publicised coexistence of solar panels and crops is, in practice, minimal—given the industrial scale of these plants, the lack of community participation in decision-making, and the negligible agricultural role they allow. What emerges is not a linear transition toward sustainability but a landscape of transformative frictions: intensive agriculture and agro-photovoltaic energy reproducing extractive logics on one side, and community-based and agroecological experiments seeking to rearticulate human–nature relations on the other.

Within this scenario, governance capacity becomes crucial. The Presidio stands as a key example of community-based institutional innovation, creating spaces for collective deliberation and recognising the political value of biodiversity and local knowledge (Saija, 2011). Its activities include concrete actions—supporting ecological restoration, resisting the expansion of energy infrastructures, and promoting educational and laboratory pathways involving schools, associations, and local communities. Yet these efforts remain constrained by limited resources and the constant need to mediate between divergent interests, often in tension with public institutions themselves.

An equally important role is played by the Simeto Ecomuseum, which operates as both an institutional and cultural innovation capable of expanding collective imaginaries around the river and rural landscapes (Pappalardo, 2021; Lambert-Pennington & Pappalardo, 2025). The Ecomuseum does more than valorise material and immaterial heritage—it acts as a cultural infrastructure linking memory, identity, and community experimentation, giving legitimacy to alternative ways of relating to biodiversity. Its contribution is twofold: it strengthens alliances among diverse actors (schools, associations, small producers, researchers), and it provides a narrative counterweight to the rhetoric of extractive development.

The mapped interventions—from experimental agroecological practices to environmental education, from energy-critical networks to community laboratories—demonstrate a plurality of local initiatives seeking to open spaces for transformation. Yet these initiatives often remain fragmented, lacking an overarching institutional framework capable of connecting them within a coherent strategic vision. This fragmentation limits their ability to challenge the economic and political structures sustaining intensive agriculture and extractive energy models.

From both a theoretical and practical perspective, the results suggest that transformative innovation cannot be understood as the mere introduction of new technologies or practices. It entails the construction of new social, institutional, and ecological relations. Biodiversity thus emerges not only as an object of protection but as a terrain of conflict and negotiation, where collective identities, political legitimacy, and development trajectories are redefined. Recognising the limits of this scenario is equally essential: alternative practices remain marginal in spatial and economic terms; public policies oscillate between support for industrial chains and fragmented funding for local projects. Moreover, internal fragmentation among community actors and difficulties competing with external capital risk are undermining the transformative potential of the most innovative experiences.

Nonetheless, the research identifies several key levers for future action: the cultural embeddedness of the river landscape; the growing awareness of the need for less destructive agricultural and energy models; and the capacity of community networks to bridge local practices with broader political claims. These elements provide the foundation

for a genuinely transformative trajectory—one that moves beyond mitigation toward an alternative vision of ecological and social justice.

Ultimately, the Simeto Valley functions as a complex laboratory where tensions among agricultural models, energy pressures, and community initiatives delineate the concrete contours of socio-ecological transformation. The future of biodiversity in this territory will depend on the ability to turn these tensions into opportunities for convergence, rather than persistent division.

Concluding Remarks

The discussion underscores that biodiversity transformation in the Simeto Valley is inseparable from broader political, cultural, and economic negotiations. Intensive agriculture and agrivoltaics perpetuate extractive dynamics, while agroecological practices, community governance, and cultural innovations—such as the Simeto Ecomuseum—offer relational and restorative alternatives. Yet fragmentation and resource scarcity limit their reach. Future interventions must therefore integrate dispersed efforts into coherent frameworks linking knowledge, governance, and ecological care. The valley's challenge, and potential, lies in turning friction into collaboration, embedding justice and biodiversity within the same transformative horizon.

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Transformative biodiversity innovation

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D2.2

Foodpark against industry

UT, The Netherlands

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Summary

Summary of Deliverable

Foodpark Amsterdam is a grassroots organisation that aims to protect an area in the city of Amsterdam (the Lutkemeerpolder) from industrialization. Their approach consists of three interrelated strategies. The first strategy is protest. The movement protests against the plans to develop the area and build warehouses on them through banners and flyers and by using public consultation. The second strategy is to frame a broader narrative. In this narrative, they present the development plans as representing an unsustainable economic worldview that is based a separation between people and nature, overconsumption, and property, and they contrast this with an alternative worldview that conceives of land not as property but as commons and that considers humans as entangled with nature. The third strategy is prefiguring and building an alternative. Specifically, they aim to create a foodpark that will be governed as a commons and that will foster enhanced human nature relationships, and they also prefigure this model of the commons in the inner workings of the grassroots organisation. The case study demonstrates how these different strategies work together to not only protect a specific area, but also build an alternative, commons based, society.

Transformative biodiversity innovations (D2.2)

1.1 Analysis of Inclusion/Exclusion Mechanisms

In the Amsterdam case, we note a structural dominance of a modernist worldview resulting in the exclusion of the relational worldview that is at the core of Foodpark Amsterdam. Urban agriculture farms, such as for example CSA (Community Supported Agriculture) Pluk and the Stadsgoenteboer, advance relational perspectives on biodiversity and have considerable popular support and scientific endorsement. Nevertheless, they remain marginalized in practice. This marginalization happens not only vis-à-vis economic plans and actors, but also in relation to green policies and actors.

Foodpark Amsterdam's vision of an agroecological commons offers a radically different worldview to the modernist one. The latter either follows a standard economic perspective centered on financial value that depends on economic growth on a finite planet, or follows a standard green perspective based on a separation between humans and nature. This green perspective deems the agricultural nature of Lutkemeer not 'natural' and valuable enough to be protected for ecological reasons.

To counter this dual marginalization, Foodpark Amsterdam has worked on developing and applying the idea of broad wellbeing [*brede welvaart*]. In doing so, it aims to respond to the focus areas of the National Program Together Nieuw West [*in Dutch Nationaal Programma Samen Nieuw-West*] that was designed to address various social challenges in the Amsterdam Nieuw-West neighbourhood.¹ Specifically, Foodpark Amsterdam aims to respond to the topics of "living environment, opportunities for the youth, job and social security, community wealth building, sustainability, culture, and education".² This notion of broad wellbeing [*welvaart*] encompasses diverse values. In a document from 2024 titled "Sociale paragraaf" that was also shared with the municipality, Lucie Snoeker, one of the Foodpark volunteers details how Foodpark Amsterdam contributes to creating eight values which include 1) subjective wellbeing, 2) health, 3) consumption and income, 4) education and professional training, 5) Spatial cohesion and quality, 6) economic capital, 7) natural capital, and 8) social capital.³ In contrast to the metric of GDP (Gross Domestic Product), broad wellbeing [*brede welvaart*] offers the opportunity to think about place-based co-production processes that recognize the specific needs, desires, and potentials of diverse social-ecological communities, in this case the neighbourhood of Nieuw West. This alternative logic of valuation places an emphasis on material and embodied values that are meaningful to specific places / people / communities rather than on universal standards and metrics. However, some of these values are hardly quantifiable in financial terms, and thus they lose out against standard value assessments. Nevertheless, after Foodpark Amsterdam presented these eight values at the municipality, they were asked to participate in a workshop organized by the municipality in connection to the National Program Together Nieuw West.

It should be noted that FPA is an initiative with very scarce resources. It is mostly volunteer-run and community building typically requires a lot of time and dedication. They organize several activities that aim to engage with the municipality, promote FPA, and connect with the neighbourhood. These include guided walks, events at local libraries, film screenings in local cinema, participating in (festive) markets, offerereng workshops in the neighbourhood, joining and organizing campaigns and protests, joining other ongoing cultural activities in the neighbourhood, organizing cultural activities, joining local political

¹ See *Nationaal Programma Samen Nieuw-West*. Samen Nieuw-West. Retrieved November 20, 2025, from <https://www.samennieuw-west.nl/>.

² Translation from Lucie Snoeker's "Sociale paragraaf: wat kan Voedselpark Amsterdam betekenen voor Nieuw-West?" (2024). For more information, see [Sociale paragraaf - Wat kan Voedselpark Amsterdam betekenen voor Nieuw-West](#).

³ See [Sociale paragraaf - Wat kan Voedselpark Amsterdam betekenen voor Nieuw-West](#).

conversations, and collaborating with local social initiatives, like the free supermarket for people with low incomes and the foodbank. The volunteer character of FPA restricts their capacity to engage with actors that are fully paid for their time, for example the municipality and economic actors. It also restricts their capacity to build relations with inhabitants of the neighbourhood and has, so far, not resulted in neighbourhood inhabitants joining the core team of Foodpark Amsterdam for extended periods. For Foodpark this is an issue that is often brought up during meetings.

Despite the limitations of being a volunteer run organization, Foodpark Amsterdam makes great effort to reach out and build relations with diverse people and actors. Moreover, it offers a space and community that empowers its members to do work that is meaningful to them. This can have positive effects on their lives by providing a sense of community, a sense of expertise on a topic, experience, etc. The organizational structure of Foodpark Amsterdam provides a 'workplace experience' that to some extent prefigures the bottom-up and commons-based democratic decision-making processes that they are advocating for. Within Foodpark Amsterdam, anybody who has an idea for doing something can in principle go ahead, but they are expected to consult others before execution. This gives everybody a sense of ownership of their own work, freedom and creativity. At the same time, the community consultation ensures broad support and improvement of plans, which can help smaller initiatives. While there are specific people that are in charge of the budget (in terms of organizing payments and applying for funds), the budget is transparent and everybody who would like to initiate a project can put forward a proposal.

A further way in which inclusion is promoted, we can mention the PAR approach itself. Being part of a research project (BIOTraCes) has enabled Foodpark to expand their already extensive relations. This creates visibility for the initiative and for the knowledges and experience of small-scale farmers and activists. More specifically, in the case of Foodpark, such a research approach supports knowledge generation around commoning activities, which is still regarded as a marginal economic practice. The post-growth cities symposium (2024), a research symposium dedicated fully to Foodpark Amsterdam, was a moment in which this academic support was publicly showcased. During this symposium, 10 well-established and successful academic researchers from various disciplines spoke in front of an audience of around 100 mostly other academic researchers (although policy makers and urban farmers were also invited). The symposium was a strong signal of mutual solidarity between the academic community and Foodpark, highlighting the power of the ideas and movement around their commons-based vision.

1.2 Niche Innovators and Key Players

Many members of Foodpark Amsterdam are connected to other movements, which links them to wider networks and initiatives that search for radical alternatives to the current modernist worldview and political economic system. However, we do not think that the term innovator is appropriate in our context, and we prefer not to use it for two reasons. Firstly, the term's prevalent interpretations related to new solutions. Such understandings promote a progress narrative that lies at the heart of the modernist worldview and associated ideas of economic growth and technological expansion, both of which have been identified as underlying causes and indirect drivers of biodiversity loss. By placing an emphasis on the 'new', the mainstream understandings of "innovation" place it in opposition to what may be perceived as old and traditional, even implying "a lack of imagination" (Bollier and Helfrich 2019). Second, the terminology of "niche innovators" risks to depoliticize projects, as they are not understood to engage with structural issues and pre-existing power relations. Niche innovations are part of a wider trend to organize policy and governance in terms of pilots, or experiments. While this has advantages because such pilots and experiments are bounded, this boundedness also means that they

are depolitized and detached from wider institutional and power dynamics (Turnhout et al. 2020).⁴

Both reasons show why FPA does not fit well with mainstream interpretations of innovation. FPA's focus on commoning is not new. Commoning and commons have a very long history, and they are the backbone of vibrant social-ecological communities across the world. Claiming 'commoning' as an innovation would be inappropriate and would not only dismiss this history but also ignore the ongoing commoning practices that are going on in many parts of the world. Second, commoning is explicitly political. It challenges existing institutions of land use and ownership and proposes an alternative institutional form, the community land trust. Moreover, FPA engages in diverse networks related to alternative economies, food and art. These are outlined below.

Economic Initiatives

Foodpark Amsterdam is aligned to other initiatives and movements interested in themes like commons, alternative economies, and degrowth. This includes the Stichting Grond van Bestaan, Schumacher center for new economics, Waag Futurelab, And the People, the Commons Network, the MeentCoop, etc. What ties these themes together is a shared understanding that the accumulation of capital, financialization, and profit maximalization ultimately undermine relational values, and social-ecological justice and flourishing. The underlying logic regarding biodiversity is that if you take away the financial incentives of profit maximizing, other values are given a chance to flourish, including ecological values, such as biodiversity.

Also, within the municipality of Amsterdam there is an increasing recognition of FPA' ideas. The municipality now even has its own commons program. Nonetheless, it seems to be the case that the municipality is mostly enthusiastic about cooperative modes of organization, while putting land that is in the property of the municipality into a trust is not yet on the agenda.

Food Initiatives

Second, Foodpark Amsterdam is connected to initiatives and movements that aim to change our food system in the way food is produced and processed. This includes the Slowfood movement, 'Futurefarmers' [*in Dutch Toekomstboeren*], the Foundation for urban agriculture [*in Dutch Stichting Stadslandbouw Amsterdam*]. All of these initiatives understand the close relationship between biodiversity, food, and culture. While they differ largely in their geographical reach (from international to local) they remain very much at the margins of the Dutch food system.

Arts Initiatives

Third, Foodpark Amsterdam is connected to arts movements that also challenge the way art has been traditionally thought and practiced. This includes most relevantly the artistic residence with Waag Futurelab (2024), the Lumbung Curatorial Program (2024-2025), de Appel Curatorial Programme (2024), and the International Architecture Biennale Rotterdam (2024). For these different artistic initiatives, FPA serves a place of using natural materials of the polder, most significantly the clay, a place for learning and dialogue. Perhaps, most interestingly, it also serves as a place to rethink the meaning and purpose of art and artistic practice.

⁴ Turnhout, E., Metze, T.A.P., Wyborn, C., Klenk, N. & Louder, E. (2020). The politics of co-production: participation, power, and transformation. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 42, 15–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2019.11.009>.

This becomes most explicit in the Lumbung Curatorial Program that aims to understand art and curation as lumbung – which is a kind of commoning. To them “The lumbung practice enables an alternative economy of collectivity, shared resource building, and equitable distribution. Lumbung is anchored in the local and based on values such as humor, generosity, independence, transparency, sufficiency, and regeneration.”⁵ This was developed in during documenta 15 and now is offered as a 2-year master program and training and thus has also received significant institutional recognition. The impact of Lumbung on biodiversity conservation is not necessarily linear, as not all artistic collectives are dealing with issues that are directly about biodiversity. Yet, in a more general sense it provides another entry into practicing and imagining an alternative economy, which can make space for biodiversity to flourish.

The International Architecture Biennale Rotterdam (IABR) *Nature of Hope* (2024)⁶ involved Foodpark Amsterdam to show how architecture and its practice need to be rethought. Instead of thinking of architecture in terms of new built environment, there needs to be more focus on the relation between building and the environment.

1.3 Scalable Bottom-Up Innovations for Transformative Change

For the same reasons as explained above (e.g., connection to notions of progress and development of ‘new’ technologies or products associated with a modernist worldview detrimental to biodiversity), also within this section we will refrain from using the terminology of ‘innovation’. Moreover, the notion of ‘scaling’ itself has been met with some critique, seen to reflect the modernist project, and promote certain problem framings and visions of the future that benefit some powerful actors while sidelining others (Pfothenhauer et al, 2021).⁷ Scaling also tends to point to solutionism (i.e. ‘scalable solutions’) which does not appreciate the time needed for forming relationships, learning and co-creation in bottom-up experimentation, and especially for the broader narrative and societal shifts that FPA is working towards.

Instead of developing testable and scalable solutions, the strategies and activities of FPA can better be characterized as a continuous process and struggle. This includes spreading their commons-based vision and economic alternatives and connecting with other people, networks, organizations and movements. Instead of the notion of scaling up as is used in common understandings of innovation, where local initiatives can scale up to the policy or regime level, this approach aligns better with ideas of scaling out and scaling deep (Moore at al., 2015).⁸ Scaling out because the focus is not necessary on governmental actors but on connecting with comparable initiatives and organizations. Scaling deep because the focus is not only on protecting a specific place and changing a specific plan but on challenging the dominant paradigm and narrative that underlies the plan to develop the Lutkemeerpolder and current regulations and policies that enable the financialization and private ownership of land, and that is the underlying root cause of biodiversity loss more generally.

Within the case of Foodpark Amsterdam, scaling deep could be seen through artistic collaborations which are also part of some of the workshops, including *Listening to the Soil*

⁵ Lumbung. *Documenta Fifteen*. Retrieved November 20, 2025, from <https://documenta-fifteen.de/en/lumbung/>.

⁶ *Nature of Hope 2024*. IABR. Retrieved November 20, 2025, from <https://content.iabr.nl/en/biennales/nature-of-hope>.

⁷ Pfothenhauer, S., Laurent, B., Papageorgiou, K., & Stilgoe, and J. (2021). The politics of scaling. *Social Studies of Science*, 52(1), 3-34. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03063127211048945>.

⁸ Moore, M.-L., Riddell, D., & Vocisano, D. (2015). Scaling Out, Scaling Up, Scaling Deep: Strategies of Non-profits in Advancing Systemic Social Innovation. *The Journal of Corporate Citizenship*, 58, 67–84. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/jcorpciti.58.67>.

(W02), *Ceramics Workshops* (W06), *Rurban Toolmaking* (W07), and *Speculative Monitoring* (W09). But also the collaboration around the International Architecture Biennale Rotterdam (2024) provides an example of a deeper transformative learning.

1.4 Initial Mapping of Interventions

An overview of the different activities and collaborations undertaken by Foodpark Amsterdam in the context of this project can be found in table 1.

Table 1: Overview of Workshops			
Number, Name & Date	Organizers	Participants	Description
<p>W01: <i>Social Ecological Systems mapping with Foodpark Amsterdam</i> 28 June 2023, at de Waag Future lab</p>	UT researcher	6 FPA members	During this workshop, in a three-step procedure, we mapped with our societal partner the Social Ecological System around Foodpark Amsterdam. Starting from the individual network and connections, we were further circling into issues of conflict, power, synergies and open questions and concluded with a formulation of challenges and potentials. During this workshop the key themes were identified, which included problematizing real estate development and its financial logic, community building and creating an appealing narrative for Foodpark Amsterdam.
<p>W02: <i>Listening to the Soil</i>, June 2023, at the Boterbloem in the Lutkemeerpolder</p>	UT researcher & external artist with some assistance of Foodpark.	Around 40 15–16-year-old students from local (public) international school	The aim of the workshop was to stimulate deeper engagement with nature and imagination around alternative human-nature relationships through making speculative listening tools. For this purpose, we used white canvases and coloured pens for brainstorming; discarded and leftover crafting materials and electronics for making the tools. With this the pupils made speculative listening tools capturing more-than human needs in ways that could be experienced through human senses. Analysis of the workshop may be found in Baibarac-Duignan, C., & van den Eijnden, T. (2025). Designing for Transitions Through Co-created Artistic Methods: Gluing Affective “Rurban” Encounters. <i>World Futures Review</i> , 0(0). https://doi.org/10.1177/19467567251330153 .
<p>W03: <i>Land Lease and Food Initiatives</i>, 27 Oktober, 2023, Urban farm Noord-Oogst</p>	Foodpark member & Foundation for Urban Agriculture, UT researcher involved as report maker	15 participants, including civic servants, urban farmers, artists, etc.	The starting point of the conversation was a widely shared feeling that there is much motivation for urban agriculture, exemplified by still unrealized projects such as Foodpark Amsterdam. However, there are structural financial, legal and fiscal barriers that prevent such projects from being realized with difficulty, if at all. The goal of the workshop was to better identify these barriers, but also to gather strategies and courses of action for

			how we can collectively deal with these barriers and what the possibilities are for rearranging land ownership.
<p>W04: <i>Postgrowth Cities workshop on collaboration,</i> 9th February 2024, at the Boterbloem in the Lutekemeerpolder</p>	<p>UT researcher, external researcher and FPA</p>	<p>2 X 25 participants, mostly researchers, 1 FPA member</p>	<p>During the <u>Postgrowth Cities Symposium</u> (see chapter 4.2), we also conducted a workshop with the aim of the workshop was to bring policymakers, researchers, commoners and urban agriculture practitioners together to reflect on the relations and collaborations between researchers, civic organisations, and the municipality. These questions do not just bring us together around Foodpark Amsterdam but also resonate more widely with the broader field of urban agriculture. While generally, there is a lot of enthusiasm for these collaborations, it is also worthwhile examining how they take shape, what are good practices and where we need to improve our ways of working together to make them more equitable, impactful and generative. The aim of the workshop was twofold: to formulate general principles that can help us to make collaboration agreements and strategize about concrete actions we could take in the present.</p>
<p>W05: <i>Spatial planning for Food within Urban Development,</i> 21 June, 2024, urban farm NoordOogst</p>	<p>Foundation for urban agriculture, municipality of Amsterdam, UT researcher</p>	<p>Around 15 participants including architects, planners, civic servants, researchers</p>	<p>For a healthy, sustainable and resilient city, it is crucial that the food cycle is given space in new neighbourhoods. How can this be organized in the planning process? And what does this require from residents (networks) in adopting gardens and other communal outdoor spaces? We take the case of the area development for Havenstad and NoordOogst as an example.</p>
<p>W06: <i>Ceramic Workshops,</i> March-July 2024, at New metropolis, Bouwput, & de Boterbloem</p>	<p>External artist, Waag Futurelab, FPA, UT researcher</p>	<p>About 5-25 participants per workshop, mostly residents and clay lovers of Amsterdam</p>	<p>There were 8 clay workshops taking place between March and July 2024 in different locations in Nieuw West, including the Lutkemeerpolder. This happened as part of an artistic residency between FPA and Waag Futurelab. All workshops involved clay from the Lutkemeerpolder. In some workshops the focus was on harvesting the wild clay and cleansing it in others the focus was on making objects. Different artistic exercises were employed for this and inspiration was taken from ancient ceramic art from the Asia Minor region. This also provoked reflections on how ceramic art and clay connects us to the land, plants, and food. Results include an artistic catalogue, a short documentary on "The Gold of Amsterdam" and an open-air exhibition.</p>
<p>W07: <i>Toolmaking to Reimagine Food</i></p>	<p>UT Researchers, Rurba</p>	<p>10 participants</p>	<p>In this workshop, we aimed to explore and reimagine 'rurban' food futures for the neighbourhood of Nieuw West through</p>

<p><i>Futures</i>, 14 June 2024, at de Boterbloem</p>	<p>nFutures Collective, FPA</p>		<p>toolmaking at the present site of FoodparkAmsterdam. The workshop was an experimental format, conceived as a low-threshold mode of engagement with the site at Lutkemeerpolder by making it accessible to participants from groups outside the academic or artistic realms. Tools allow us to work the land, harvest and prepare food. They connect soil and seeds, skills and knowledge, humans and nature.</p>
<p>W08: <i>Bioblitz</i>, June 2024, in de Lutkemeerpolder, cancelled due to lack of available volunteer ecologists</p>	<p>UT Researchers & FPA</p>	<p>n.a.</p>	<p>Through biologically surveying the site where the Foodpark is presently located, we will make visible the biodiversity value of the land and explore potential futures where various species thrive. The aim of the workshop was to bring to the fore the biodiversity specific to this land and to explore potential tensions between how biodiversity is normally conceived (e.g., as unique and/or protected species) and everyday / mundane illustrations of biodiversity of a land under threat of redevelopment for lack of biodiversity significance. While in the end we had sufficient citizen participants that were eager to participate, we did not manage to find enough ecological experts that would have been able to instruct the citizens and bring the tools for proper examination.</p>
<p>W09: <i>Speculative Monitoring Workshop</i>, 24 July 2024 at de Boterbloem</p>	<p>UT researcher, FPA Amsterdam, External curators</p>	<p>20 artists, curators, and activists from Open Call: de Appel Curatorial Programme Summer School - de Appel Amsterdam</p>	<p>In this workshop, we speculatively monitored the life of the polder above and below the surface of soil, water, and empirical reality. We did this by imaging what the polder smells, feels, and looks like for different moments in time that slip through current monitoring practices. In doing so, we wanted to expand our attention to biodiversity beyond limiting notions of biodiversity that dominate in the present and think about other ways of conceiving the richness of the living world. By bringing together different speculative accounts on what biodiversity might be, we wanted to open up a conversation about what biodiversity would mean if we conceived of it as a potentiality rather than a reality. And lastly, what are the implications in terms of landownership, if we look at land as potentialities for life rather than a measurable reality?</p>
<p>W10: <i>Toward a desirable land policy: Visions and routes for collaboration</i>, 4 December 2024,</p>	<p>UT researcher, FPA, Foundation for urban agriculture</p>	<p>25 participants, including urban farmers and municipal employees</p>	<p>The workshop was conducted during the Day of Urban Agriculture in Amsterdam organized by the Association of urban agriculture in Amsterdam. Approximately 25 people were anticipating in the workshop, among which two core members of Foodpark Amsterdam, and one researcher, one student who are also</p>

<p>at urban farm NoordOogst</p>		<p>involved in the case. Among their participants were urban farmers (among which at least one who is currently collaborating with Foodpark Amsterdam): Leading questions were: What are the desirable visions for the future of land policy? Is land a resource, or should it be considered a commons, meaning that the land is unsellable? What are the challenges and opportunities from the perspective of officials and council members as we move toward desirable land policy? And how can we collaborate effectively at the interface of research, policy and civic engagement? This workshop is "hands-on": we started with big ideas and then worked toward concrete proposals for collaboration. The workshop provided different insights on vision on land and principles of collaboration.</p>
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The activities can be grouped into three approaches:

1. Problem mapping
2. New perspectives on biodiversity
3. New tools for collaboration

Problem Mapping

Two workshops have been mostly concerned with mapping a salient problem within the field of biodiversity loss. This concerns firstly the Social Ecological Systems workshop (W01). During this workshop, we used three-step procedure. First, we mapped our individual network and connections. Second, we collectively mapped common issues of conflict, power, synergy, third we developed main questions challenges, and potentials. During this workshop the key themes were identified, which included problematizing real estate development and its financial logic, community building and creating an appealing narrative for Foodpark Amsterdam. Another example of problem mapping was a workshop on *Land Lease and Food Initiatives* (W03) that was led by a FPA member and documented by a UT researcher during the first day of urban agriculture in Amsterdam. The aim of the workshop was to map barriers to urban agriculture but also strategies and action roots to address the barriers collectively. The main barrier in question was the way land ownership is currently handled. What both workshops on problem mapping have in common is that they do not address biodiversity directly but help identify an environment that allows biodiversity to flourish by addressing underlying causes of biodiversity loss.

New perspectives on biodiversity

This involved workshops that aimed to provoke alternative perspectives and imaginaries on biodiversity. For instance, for the *Listening to the Soil* workshop (W02), the aim was drawing attention to the invisible soil life and imagine knowledge could be exchanged between humans and soil. For the *Speculative Monitoring* workshop (W09), the aim was to open up perspectives on biodiversity beyond the biodiversity that can be currently measured to what it was and what it could be. Finally, for the *Ceramic Workshop* (W06), it was more generally a way of relating to nature through the medium of clay and also archetypical subject matters of clay, such as flora and fauna, fertility, and nourishment-related artefacts like bowls, cups, and plates for food.

These alternative perspectives on biodiversity are important for several reasons. They counter biodiversity as a purely 'natural science' issue and how this is also something that comes alive in cultural imaginaries. Moreover, they help to challenge the modernist

worldview and associated technocratic visions of nature that are also entangled with dynamics of extraction and mechanization. For instance, understanding the soil as something that can be listened to and communicated with allows to see soil as full of life rather than non-specific matter (i.e. mud).

The *Speculative Monitoring* workshop (W09) helped to historicize biodiversity, as something that came into being through specific land uses and decisions rather than having been naturally like this forever. This, at the same time, also opened up diverse perspectives on biodiversity for the future. Instead of assessing landscapes merely in what kind of species they are hosting now, they could be viewed in terms of their potential for future life.

New tools for collaboration

Other workshops were around the topic of collaboration, which is an essential strategy for small scale initiatives to survive within a system that privileges collaborations with powerful actors and organizations. During the *Toolmaking to Reimagine Food Futures* workshop (W07), led by a member of the Toekomstboeren network together with a UT researcher, collaboration was about peer-to-peer knowledge-sharing between different farmers and gardeners. It focused on exchange of knowledge around tools, what can be done with them, and how they can be repaired or adjusted to specific purposes. For other workshops, the focus was on collaborations between different urban agriculture advocates that brings together activists, researchers and municipal employees. Collaboration that goes beyond tokenistic consultation would be an impactful intervention into how many spatial planning processes take place, particularly around issues of urban agriculture. Here, collaboration is also about finding common goals despite differences in values or perspectives, and ways to work towards them. Examples for this are the *Postgrowth Cities* workshops on collaborations (W04) and the workshop *Spatial planning for Food within Urban Development* (W05).

1.5 Discussion

In this report, we have reflected on different dynamics that drive or block transformation in various ways. We discussed the dominance of the modernist worldview as one of the main barriers for more relational ideas on wider prosperity to be taken serious at a policy level but also how volunteer run initiatives struggle to find volunteer support when basic needs are not yet fulfilled (section 2). Nonetheless, we also noted, that precisely here it is of great importance to build community relations and alliances. Researchers that take a PAR approach can actively support this, not least by recognizing and emphasizing its importance (section 2).

We also discussed the significance of the commoning focus on Foodpark Amsterdam for the larger project of transformation, and how this spans a network that involves alternative economies initiatives, food initiatives and artistic initiatives (section 3). Our research is then precisely located at the intersection of these three domains where we participated actively. We also discussed the issue of scalability and highlighted the importance of making horizontal connections to related initiatives (section 4) like those mapped in section 3. Finally, we provided a brief overview of the most important workshops that we conducted in the past two years and discussed how they contribute to either mapping the problem, offering new perspectives on biodiversity or offering new tools for collaboration (section 5).

To conclude, this report has shown that transformative approaches to biodiversity require a shift in worldviews. This has very practical implications, including what are important domains for biodiversity, how to make impact and how we as researchers can contribute with transformative interventions.

D2.2

Nature-Inclusive building

WR, The Netherlands

November 2025

Authors

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Summary

Summary of Deliverable

The planning, design and construction of new houses and neighbourhoods has a significant impact on nature. Over the past decade, approximately 280 square kilometres have been converted into human habitats, coinciding with a corresponding decline in agricultural and natural areas. The sector is rightly considered high-impact. In response to its problematic relationship with nature, efforts have been made to incorporate more nature into human living environments. These innovation programmes are referred to as part of the “nature-inclusive agenda”.

The system tasked with building around one million homes in the coming decade is highly complex, involving a multitude of actors, legislation and political disputes. As a result, it is difficult to change. The power to initiate or resist change is distributed across a vast public-private network. The aim of this case study is to uncover the structures and mechanisms that either block or enable innovations that could improve the sector’s relationship with nature.

This case study focuses on one such nature-inclusive innovation programme, Nature for Each Other, hosted by the Province of Overijssel. In parallel, it examines an innovative citizens’ initiative called De Beuk, which aims to establish an ecovillage and eco-community on the outskirts of Wageningen. The research methods applied are rooted in action research. By engaging directly with the bio-innovative enterprise and collaborating with the citizens of De Beuk and provincial officers, researchers encountered the challenging path of marginalisation, blockage and leverage.

Biodiversity loss is indirectly driven by a narrow view of nature—as merely species and habitats—whose decline is assumed to be compensable by converting agricultural land into new nature reserves. This approach backfires in politics and public opinion, as the public tends to sympathise with farmers. Nature is often blamed for the sector’s current stagnation. The deterioration of nature is countered by an increasingly strict set of regulations. Ironically, these same regulations now hinder the success of bio-innovations. Innovations emerging from new human-nature relationships are seen as potentially harmful to the forms of nature that existing protection frameworks recognise and safeguard. The regulatory and permitting system is unyielding.

The case study reveals that innovation within the sector is primarily driven by goals of efficiency and the adoption of biomaterials. Ideological and moral innovations, however, do not fit within the sector’s systemic boundaries. Although nature-inclusive building is broadly recognised, it remains difficult to realise and is often more rhetoric than practice.

Transformative Biodiversity Innovations (D2.2)

1.1 Analysis of Inclusion/Exclusion Mechanisms

Exclusion mechanisms and practices in relation to eco-community De Beuk

The values of De Beuk (environmental care, reduced car use, tackling loneliness, greater autonomy in terms of energy, food and materials, and close contact between children and nature) are not acknowledged in the mainstream procedures and processes of creating a new neighbourhood. Their values are not capitalised, as they do not fit within the systemic and social standards of this high-impact sector. All members of De Beuk are motivated by a strong desire for a sustainable and holistic community—sustainable in an environmental sense, but also in a social sense (caring for one another when needed), and at times in a spiritual sense.

In the process of establishing this community, however, members of De Beuk are continually confronted with housing standardisation that prioritises individual or narrowly family-oriented interests and short-term policies. Within mainstream Dutch culture, there is little physical space to cultivate a connection with nature, let alone a spiritual relationship with it, as most of the interviewees confirmed.

For example, one of the interviewees, B2, feels very energetically connected to the Dorschkamp but often holds back in making that explicit. According to B2:

"Other people sometimes find this strange, which can make people feel ashamed when they make contact with a tree. B2 does not care about that so much but can also adapt without difficulty. B2 sees the way indigenous peoples live with nature as an example. In the Netherlands it is difficult to live up to that way, also in terms of spirituality." (B2 interview, April 2024).

Short-term policy and planning reinforce more materialistic behaviour (construction), running counter to eco-friendly values and practices. De Beuk is confronted with a planning process they are obliged to engage with, which has neither a clear beginning nor end, nor a defined goal, owing to political indecisiveness. During the research period, the political arena supported policymaking that prioritised economic efficiency in building practices over approaches that could also contribute to restoring biodiversity. This is linked to a housing shortage that has driven up property prices and has particularly excluded first-time buyers from the housing market, as illustrated by a younger member of De Beuk:

"Everyone in our subgroup is between 30 and 40 years old and has a desire to buy/build a house. Renting feels like a black hole where your money disappears" (B5 interview, June 2024).

Because adding positive conditions for biodiversity restoration is politically perceived and framed as more expensive, 'living with nature' becomes associated with elitism, for it is only accessible for the few who can afford it. Ecovillages are proving this frame to be false but are not, or barely institutionally recognized. So far, there is no formal category of 'ecovillage' foreseen in the allotment plan procedure (this however is possible, as proved by Het Land van Aine). The formal moment to make an offer for the land in combination with the plan that is part of the outsource, is postponed many times over many years now, and the members of De Beuk are getting exhausted due the lack of tangible outcome.

"Politicians only govern for 4 years. In four years, it is almost impossible to implement major changes. Dutch society as it is currently structured, steers towards ego-driven behavior. Capitalism is an expression of that" (B6 interview, June 2024).

B6's remark about capitalism does not come out of the blue. De Beuk is forced to compete with regular project developers because of what is called the Didam Arrest (the obligation for a governmental institution to organize open procedures for selling land), whereas there are good and legal solid arguments to organize a one-to-one contract that lays down the obligations by which De Beuk helps to realize the biodiversity aims in the management

plan of the surrounding N2000 area. Another problem is that the finance sector rules out De Beuk because it is very hard to obtain a collective mortgage in the Netherlands. Almost no Dutch bank has any experience with collective mortgages, therefore collective initiatives have to look for alternative finance schemes or go to foreign banks (bank in Germany for example, are much more advanced in this). For the Beuk, the acquisition of land is perceived as a 'make or break moment'. They are entirely relying on the willingness of the current landowners to sell their land to them, possibly at a lower price than a mainstream project developer can offer. Though the local municipality supports the Beuk, they are unable to provide them any real guarantees:

"A shortcoming that the municipality faces are that they manage little land. For projects, you often have to go to private landowners" (Interview B2, April 2024).

Several core members have mentioned they are trapped in an economic power lock-in. More specifically, especially younger people (≤ 40) and elderly (≥ 67) are in a vulnerable position, due they limited access to financial means. Young people without parents that can offer them financial relieve, are confronted with unbearable high mortgages:

"B5 would like to realize a house for a reasonable price. Reasonable in the sense that you don't have to bend over backwards to pay a mortgage. In the current housing market, they would have to do that if they wanted to buy a family home with a garden. Such a mortgage feels like a 'noose around your neck for a pile of bricks.' That is crooked. (B5 interview, June 2024)."

Elderly people on the other hand, are often not eligible for a mortgage at all due to their shorter life expectancy. Without any private financial capital, elderly people are constrained to renting a home that does not always provide them the security they need, as is illustrated by the following conversation between a researcher and an aspiring future resident of the Beuk:

'Before the walk I speak to a woman. I estimate her age to be somewhere in the mid-60s. The woman tells me that she currently lives alone in a social housing unit in Renkum where she is very lonely. She has no contact with her neighbours and even quarrels with a neighbour. Due to the lack of contact she regularly feels unsafe. In the Beuk she is mainly looking for like-minded people. She is concerned about the earth. According to her, companies and people are greedy, and we consume too much. She would like to see a sustainable, holistic society. She reads a lot about holism and knows of various ecovillage initiatives.' (Note from a future residents walk, September 2023)

Finally, it was mentioned that knowledge on planning procedures and technical aspects of the plan works out exclusionary, because it takes years of study to get to the same level or to surpass the level of big project development bureaus. On several occasions, the Beuk was confronted by what could be considered (a fear of) institutional complexity that excludes people internally as well as externally. Internally some people had trouble following institutional language:

"The past two years have been tough for several reasons. On the one hand because of the loneliness, on the other hand because starting a residential community also requires a lot of knowledge of terms. It took time to learn these terms" (interview B3, April 2024).

Becoming familiar with institutional language can take its toll, especially for people who also have high demanding jobs besides the initiative. This means especially younger people struggle with finding the energy to keep up:

"B5 sometimes find it difficult to continue to actively participate in all the activities around the Beuk. Their jobs require a lot of energy from them and the uncertainties around the Beuk do too. Sometimes it is not clear what exactly is expected of them, what can they say yes or no to? Some people in the subgroup have already dropped out with a burnout. People have to go beyond their limits. Those who are now active are also already wavering. At a certain point, the

uncertainty can break you. Age also sometimes plays a role in the uncertainties. The older members often know a lot. Sometimes it seems as if meetings are held for the sake of meetings. At the same time, you do not want to fall behind, and you try to participate as best you can. At times such as during the workshop (power and strength) you sometimes start to doubt: what do I really know? Insecurities are also addressed at such moments. You do not want to repeat things or be inefficient. During some meetings, that feeling creeps up on you. For example, when we recently had another meeting about what we call ourselves. The outcome is an ecological neighbourhood. Whether it has become more concrete is questionable. Some things drag on, such as how are we going to divide the costs? That is an issue that we all have to deal with, but nobody really wants to burn their fingers on it" (Interview B5, June 2024).

Inclusion mechanisms and practices in relation to eco-community De Beuk

Amidst the various exclusion practices, some inclusion mechanisms have also been identified. One helpful instrument for *De Beuk* is the recently adopted CPO policy [Collective Private Commissioning Policy] of the Municipality of Wageningen. This policy recognises collective initiatives and can even favour them in certain locations. It enabled *De Beuk* to apply for a subsidy to cover their feasibility study. However, the CPO policy does not override the consequences of the *Didam Arrest*. More concretely, in the case of *De Beuk*, the Municipality can express its support for CPOs but cannot enforce CPO on land that it does not own.

Another inclusive mechanism was activated when *De Beuk* reached an agreement with the social housing cooperative. The cooperative has declared its intention to contribute to some of the financial requirements for building public social housing, and in return *De Beuk* has committed to allocate 10% of households for public social housing purposes (meaning that the housing cooperative provides the residents, although they must be approved by *De Beuk*).

An innovative mechanism pioneered by *De Beuk* is the establishment of a landscape cooperative [gebiedscoöperatie], which operates as a separate legal entity from the association. The distinction between the landscape cooperative and the association is that the cooperative has an economic purpose, while the association functions as a social, non-profit organisation. The cooperative can, for example, acquire land and generate profit from it, whereas the association cannot. The intention of the landscape cooperative—also run by core members of *De Beuk*—is to acquire the land needed to build *De Beuk*. Once this has been achieved and *De Beuk* realised, the cooperative also aims to invite neighbouring enterprises to join. The plan is to manage the land—or landscape—coherently and within environmental limits.

Finally, *De Beuk* themselves are highly determined to be as inclusive as possible. This is reflected in the way they manage their finances (through an equitable contribution system) and in their envisioned housing design. Houses within *De Beuk* will ideally be able to accommodate the needs of younger people (e.g. space for children) and older people (e.g. ground-level access), while safeguarding a healthy environment for local biodiversity. This vision was achieved through co-creation. During a vision-gathering session, the two age groups most marginalised by the mainstream housing market were notably represented:

'The initiators split up without any premeditated intention into two age groups sitting opposite each other. The young initiators (all in their early thirties) sit on the floor. Opposite them, the older ones sit on a chair or bench (all around sixty). Although this arrangement was created for practical reasons (more comfort for the older ones), it suddenly becomes clear that an (age) group is missing; among the initiators present, there are no 40-somethings, nor are there any family households.' (Observation from a *Beuk* vision gathering, June 2023)

To safeguard collective and equal interests, *De Beuk* follows a sociocratic governance system that allows every member to voice their opinion. No decision is taken without the

agreement of all. If someone does not agree, all arguments are considered until full consensus is reached. A drawback of this system is that reaching a decision can therefore take a considerable amount of time.

Exclusion and Inclusion mechanisms in relation to the province of Overijssel

Like De Beuk, the Province of Overijssel operates within a broader system that does not always align with its goals. This system is shaped by prevailing political values which—at the time of research—tended to frame nature more as a barrier than a benefit. For example, excess nitrogen was commonly portrayed as an impediment to housing development. In contrast, the province seeks to reinterpret such limitations not as obstacles, but as boundaries that can guide sustainable development. A key strategy in this effort is to reframe nature's role, emphasising its benefits rather than its constraints.

One way the province promotes inclusivity is by linking nature to public health. As one interviewee explained: *"How can we involve people in nature inclusivity? I'm not talking about building new houses, but about existing ones, where gardens have become paved and lifeless. We're asking: how can we inspire and motivate residents to enhance biodiversity in their gardens? We also approach it from a health perspective, because not everyone is naturally drawn to plants. So, it's interesting to connect nature-inclusive building more explicitly with nature-inclusive living."*

The Nature for Each Other programme also includes mechanisms to engage younger generations. For instance, the province has hosted informal "pizza nights" to attract young people and spark conversations about their visions for a nature-inclusive future. In addition, they collaborate with a provincial youth board, which contributes ideas and feedback to shape the programme's direction.

1.2 Niche Innovators and Key Players

In the context of nature-positive building, the primary niche innovators are the societal partners themselves, most notably, the members of De Beuk. Over time, they have cultivated a sustained process of social learning focused on integrating nature into their envisioned living environment.

Originally conceived as a knowledge hub for biobased residential construction, the initiative gradually evolved into a private effort to develop a multifaceted eco-community. This includes an ecovillage, a complex of tiny houses, and other forms of collective, nature-integrated living. Located in Wageningen, De Beuk has benefited significantly from its proximity to Wageningen University, tapping into academic expertise and student-led research. In addition, the group has built a robust network of professionals and institutions with deep knowledge of nature-inclusive design and construction.

Through this journey, De Beuk has developed a distinct concept they refer to as "human-inclusive nature", a vision in which nature is not merely preserved or observed, but actively intertwined with daily life, habitat, and livelihood.

At the heart of De Beuk is a core group of six members, each representing a specific subgroup within the community. This core team meets biweekly, occasionally joined by other subgroup members to share leadership responsibilities. Each core member brings a unique relationship with nature and faces personal challenges in shaping a lifestyle that aligns with their ecological values.

The following section provides brief profiles of these core members, the subgroups they represent, and their individual motivations for joining De Beuk.

Individual key players of De Beuk

B1

B1 describes herself as a connector. She likes to bring people together to start processes. Finishing is less her thing. Formally, B1 is the secretary of the board of De Beuk. Because of her former jobs (she is now retired) she knows how to navigate a role a secretary, but she does not necessarily like it. She understands the necessity of the role and therefore felt she should fill in the gap (no one else wanted to take up the role). Ever since she started studying when she was younger, sustainable and healthy food has been an area of interest of B1. Since corona, she no longer uses supermarkets. Corona was a period of reflection for her; a moment to stand still and think about life. Consumption behaviour was something she thought about for a longer time. She gets fresh produce locally, mainly from harvest garden initiatives that she is a member of. After her studies in domestic science in Wageningen, B1 lived in Africa for a while in an Anthroposophical community. She initially came there for a project on social participation and improving drinking water supplies. In Africa, the seasons were experienced much more consciously than in the Netherlands. This was partly due to the anthroposophical philosophy of life, which often refers to the transition of seasons. In Africa, B1 first met biodynamic agriculture. Community is an important value that B1 seeks, among others at the Beuk. Community for her, means looking after each other. Community does not mean controlling each other. People with an enormous missionary zeal are often an annoyance to B1. Previously, B1 experienced that in some communities there are expectations. Activities were always undertaken together and if you did not participate in certain things, you were addressed about it. Those experiences were not always positive. Now she seeks community in a way without too many expectations, in which cordiality and compassion are central without being dogmatically imposed. There is a balance in giving and taking and saying no is also possible.

B2

B2 is involved in several sustainability initiatives. She is a member of the Beuk and Platform Duurzaam Wageningen and also involved in the Community Vitaal Voedsel and has set up her own foundation: Gaia Sira [earth nest]. B2 is an active citizen and can work well with the municipality. She has regular contact with municipal council members and aldermen and often goes to council meetings to speak. B2 feels involved in the CPO policy that the municipality makes and is also active in the fields of sustainable food production and air quality. Other people sometimes call B2 business oriented. She feels like she is just good at achieving goals. In Wageningen, partly thanks to B2, there are now 80 people actively measuring air quality. That is the same as the citizen network of Paris that is committed to air quality.

B2 considers people as part of nature. She cherishes a need to experience nature, to be aware of everything that blooms. After high school, B2 started studying nutrition. She had developed an interest in this from home. Her motivation was initially to live as healthy and vitally as possible. During her studies, she learned nothing about the importance of healthy soil, while healthy soil and healthy intestines seem to have a lot in common. Sustainable supply chain cycles and obtaining good soil have now become an important goal for B2 about nutrition (food production). Fortunately, this is also being recognized by more people, organizations and institutions. B2 has a great intrinsic motivation for sustainability. She it is our responsibility to pass on a healthy earth to children. Nature fits in with that. She has also been able to pass on appreciating nature, among other things, to her own children. Her youngest daughter is now a draftsman and designer of green playgrounds for children. What motivates B2 in relation to the Beuk? A bit of idealism and yet also a bit of business orientation. B2 doesn't earn as much money as she used to. Sometimes it's really a bit like scraping the pieces together. Fortunately, she doesn't need much. What is important to her is that there are no more things that must be done. She doesn't have the energy for that anymore. B2 worked for a while as an office manager and director at Stichting Agromisa. This foundation mainly supports small farmers with knowledge exchange and financing. After Agromisa, B2 worked at De Kleine Aarde and then at Kraaybeekerhof in Driebergen; an anthroposophical centre for natural food. B2 however, does not identify as anthroposophical. B2's assignment was to bring the activities of

Kraaybeekerhof more into the present day. At the same time, she also became a single mother and had a difficult relationship with her ex. B2 ended up with a burn-out. However, sitting still for long was not possible. B2 quit her job at Kraaybeekerhof and set up her own foundation: Gaia Sira. Now, besides the Beuk, she guides family constellations and gives courses on vital agriculture. In the meantime, she is a core group member and leader of the Working Group Financing.

B3

B3 sees himself as a front runner. That means he must convince other people to come and live at the Beuk. B3 experiences this as a big and tiring task, but at the same time he gets energy from telling the story and recruiting people. That is also his talent: to inspire people. At the same time, B3 also wants to be able to understand what is going on to be able to translate matters to the vision group: the subgroup formed by part of the current squatters. He then functions as a kind of filter and translator; for example, when it comes to the plans of the urban planners. Living amongst the squatters has made B3 'conservative/right-wing', according to himself. By that, he means that he has started to live more principled. This is expressed, for example, in his view on smoking: you simply don't do it. Not only because it is bad for nature (filters that remain), but also because it is bad for your body: why would you consciously poison your own body? B3 tries to deal with his body very consciously. He himself also suffers from asthma. Amongst the squatters, people sometimes dealt very loosely with principles, for example regarding smoking, and that can be called somewhat hypocritical. B3 became increasingly annoyed by this hypocrisy the longer he lived amongst the squatters. There was not always honesty. Another example is the Slow Worm. Since chickens have been roaming around on the squatter's premises, there have been fewer slow worms on the Dorschkamp. That is a shame, B3 thinks. Especially because the slow worm is a vulnerable and rare native species and chickens are not. Standing up for the future generation doesn't really appeal to B3. That will be fine. What he is looking for is experience. Sensation encourages action. Nature is sensational. Nature can also move B3. For example, it can remind him of his mortality. B3 lived in the Amazon for a year. There he had several near-death experiences (including Dengue). The Netherlands and Belgium are like 'the shire' to B3. Nature is not dangerous here. Agriculture is the new nature here. Perhaps an expression of our desire for more control. In general, B3 is a fan of wonder. Let nature come to you. It's okay if it's a bit messy. B3 has been chairman of the Beuk for a while now. It is not entirely clear what that role entails. In practical terms, he is present at all AGM and Core Group meetings. There is also an administrative task attached to the role of chairman (including signing things, being the point of contact for the municipality). B3 is also the driving force behind the ecology working group and a project at the Science Shop.

"As chairman, it is my job to ensure that the association goes towards its goal and does not stray too much from its goal. So, to stay on course a bit, give direction. That is the function of a chairman. And he listens to everything that comes in and so on. What makes me so special in all of this, and what I think is also necessary as an ingredient for the Beuk, and what makes me so successful is, I am actually really not at home with all those crazy difficult complex terms. Certainly not to the extent of B4 and B6 for example who know how to express that very well, really the business, boring and so on, and what I realize is: even though I am not at home with that, I feel very compelled to understand it, but I do my best to translate that into my own language and that is a bit more basic than that of B6 and B4 for example. Because I succeed in making that translation, into a slightly easier language, it is so much easier to communicate with the supporters, and with the rest of the board and with the core group and externals, and I think that is precisely where my strength lies. Keeping everyone up-to-date and informed and letting them sail along in this project, which creates a feeling of 'we are all running this spaceship'." (Voice note, send by B3 on the 20th of June 2024)

B4

B4 was raised with Christian values, but he and his family are not practicing. In addition to living in the green, 'decluttering' is also an important reason for B4 to move into a Tiny House. With everything you have, you start asking yourself: do I really need it? If not, it goes away. B4 experiences having less stuff as a relief. At the Beuk, B4 finds people who share an interest in sustainability. B4 considers himself an entrepreneur and likes to tackle things. What they (Tiny house group - THG) have in common is the desire to live smaller in a green environment. A Tiny House may not be larger than 50 square meters. B4 considers the versatility of the group as a strength. Of all the subgroups of the Beuk, being together is perhaps the least important in the THG. Members want to live sustainably and reasonably off the grid, but also independently. For B4, living in a Tiny House symbolizes less materialism and fewer worries. Less stuff means less stress. Living smaller can simplify your life. B4 is now also developing a food forest in his neighbourhood in Ede. This initiative originated from a neighbourhood network. He himself helps with, among other things, applying for subsidies and realising and organising the initiative. B4 considers nature-inclusive construction as something in which nature is part of the design. As an architect, B4 wants to further develop what that looks like. This also ties in with his efforts in the development of the plan for the Beuk. Nature-inclusive construction must go further than just biobased construction. B4 prefers to be a bit reserved when it comes to decisions. His participation in the Beuk is more of a voyage of discovery. He has no problem with others occasionally determining the course. B4 considers himself an entrepreneur and likes to tackle things. Unconsciously, boundaries may also be pushed in the Beuk. That appeals to B4. B4 is chairman of the Tiny House Group and in that capacity is involved in all administrative tasks. He has been doing this for 5 years now. The core team of the THG consists of about 12 people, 4 of whom are board members. There are now 40 people on the waiting list. B4 sees himself as an initiative developer within the THG. He starts initiatives and connects people/members to the initiative and promotes initiatives externally. Design workshops are also organized and lectures in the library about small living.

B5

B5 are a young couple. B5 know their friends and subgroup 'Between the Trees' [Tussen de Bomen] from juggling and festivals. What connects everyone from Between the Trees is the importance that everyone attaches to sustainability and the desire to live in a community. Many now also live in a student house or housing group. Property-wise there are different wishes within the group. B5 would like to buy their house and piece of land. They have a need that their house is really theirs, including their own piece of land. B5 do not necessarily identify as spiritual, but they do experience a superhuman connection. This connection is also nature; it is our position and role in a greater whole, our soul. The young man first says that he does not feel called upon to convince others. The young woman sees it a little differently. They agree that appreciation for and experience of nature cannot be enforced. People simply prefer to be with other people. Sometimes you are also just in a completely different phase of life. Teenagers, for example, are extremely focused on each other. That is a phase that almost all of us go through at that age. There is also a difference in how people experience and prioritize 'nature' in Between the Trees. For some, living in nature is very important and for others, living in a community is especially important. For B5, both are important, but especially nature. They like the fact that they can cook together, for example, but also that it is not an obligation to cook together. Ideally, nothing is required, and a lot is possible. For festive occasions, it is very nice that there is a communal space to come together for a feast. B5 are inspired by Buddhism. They once followed a training with Matthijs Schouten [Dutch Nature philosopher] and have followed meditation courses. Buddhism teaches you, among other things, to have respect for all life. You no longer kill something so quickly. You even try to accept the snails that eat everything in your vegetable garden. Meditation mainly influences the relationship with yourself. Meditation helps you to let go of a piece of ego. Buddhism considers everything in essence as pure. This purity is shared with nature and the universe but can be

overshadowed by pieces of ego in the course of your life. Meditation helps you to think about what really belongs to you. It brings peace because you can peel off pieces of ego until you are in balance again: in connection with life. B5 are not so involved in all institutional matters. Others simply know much more about that. A visualization and the design of the forest rooms is something they would like to be involved in. For example, when thinking about green play areas for children. The members of Between the Trees are all at the age that they think about children. Raising children in a community appeals to them all. They also all want their children to grow up with each other and in a green environment. It must feel safe and nice to ring the neighbours' doorbell. Formal matters such as setting up an area cooperative, on the other hand, are more remote from them. B5 are intrigued by the concept of 'effective altruism'. Peeling off ego is part of it but is only effective if you don't get destroyed by it yourself. You can't carry the weight of the world on your own.

B6

B6 has lost a good friend during his studies. This event affected him deeply. They once had the ambition to save the world together. However, the problems in the world weighed too heavily on his friend. B6 promised him to continue. He keeps his friend in honour through his idealism. B6 meets his wife during folk dancing in '84. They complement each other. She is more of the 'social side.' He is more concerned with the earth. This is reflected in their housing wishes: she is especially looking forward to living in a community (neighbourhood), he is especially looking forward to sustainable living. A book that influenced B6 is greening the dessert. This book describes a project of a man who brought a seemingly dead place back to life with plants in seven years. B6 tells that all civilizations have once perished due to an environmental disaster. For our civilization, ryegrass is perhaps the disaster.

B6 knows how to tell a story, both to governments and to businesses. He regularly attends events about sustainable living. That's how he met BIOTraCes: on sustainable Tuesday [Dutch Sustainability event]. He also works in his own neighbourhood to teach people who are open to it about sustainability and nature. He thinks it's a shame that a lot of greenery in his neighbourhood has disappeared: people would rather have a shed with a bar in their garden. He also prefers to show things. For example, he once planted a potato with children from the neighbourhood to show that a few months later 12 potatoes suddenly appeared. B6 also used to have his own vegetable garden. When he heard about the substances that Chemours released [neighbouring chemical plant], he gave up his vegetable garden. B6 first met ecovillages through Ad Vlems, initiator of ecovillage Boekel. In 2009, Ad placed an advertisement in which he was looking for people who wanted to think differently. That appealed to B6, and with him 300 others. 300 people is too many to build a community. Ecovillage Boekel was eventually realized for 100 households. According to B6, you can build a community with at most 27 people. A vision is often more powerful if fewer people participate. The more people, the more hollow and less concrete a vision often becomes. With the experience that B6 had gained in the civil service world, came the logical responsibility to explore the civil service part of the realization of Ecodorp Boekel. B6 knows all the government terms and could therefore advise governments on how to deal with eco-village inactives. A good first step is always to write a letter to the alderman about your plans. After that, an alderman is obliged to invite you for a conversation. B6 calls himself someone who does not let himself be led. He does not want to be a leader himself but rather inspire others.

Discussion on innovative characteristics of key members of the Beuk

De Beuk deliberately calls itself an ecological hamlet. That feels like something between a district and a community. The subgroups, and their core group representatives are quite diverse in their wishes (hence no community). A concrete example is the desire for ownership of various participants/subgroups. Some absolutely want to own their piece of

land/house, others do not have that desire or have less of it. No consent has yet been reached on how to deal with this. There is, however, consent on the fact that the houses may not be used as speculative objects. The consequence of this is that the price of owner-occupied houses cannot rise. Compared to the dominant building regime that is very much driven by financial revenue, this is a bold and very social decision.

Social and ecological values are at the heart of every key player. Each core member of the Beuk has a strong desire to be surrounded by people that share similar values. Most members have developed these values at a relatively young age. Some are inspired by their experiences abroad, living in communities in Africa and the Amazon. Others were influenced by spiritual philosophies like Anthroposophy and Buddhism. One also mentioned Christian Values. A factor that has reinforced social ecological values for some, were traumatic experiences. One core member lost his best friend and swore to honour him by advocating ecological living. Other members experienced disease and burn out and were able to regain energy by reconnecting with nature. These core members are familiar with social and ecological resilience. They skilfully work together in ways that allow people to activate their individual strengths and tactfully use individual networks. For all members, working towards sustainable goals gives energy and purpose. This is also in contrast to a majority of mainstream project developers.

The Province of Overijssel as niche innovator (and system innovator)

The Province of Overijssel has the ambition to reach people 'outside of their bubble' with its policy programme. They are seeking to spread their message on the importance of nature-inclusive building and biodiversity to a broader audience. As they described it, until now they have mainly reached 'dark green' people, those already interested in or concerned with nature and biodiversity. Now, they want to reach 'lighter green citizens', whom they hope to inspire to become more involved in nature and biodiversity activities.

Their approach is to create practical toolboxes to support citizens and organisations in making nature-inclusive building accessible and manageable. To achieve this, they are focusing on nature-inclusive building projects in social housing, which are generally located in lower-income areas. These areas also tend to be less green, so investing in green surroundings will improve climate adaptation. Greener areas will also support public health. Health has therefore been adopted as an additional objective in their policy programme, as this is more likely to gain approval and support in the current political climate, whereas nature as a goal in itself is not widely supported.

They are also making efforts to involve young people, to include their perspectives on nature and their vision for the future. The province pursues several strategies to ensure that the ideas and values of nature-inclusive building reach others:

- They make things practical, local and achievable. For example, they ensure toolboxes are developed for communities, citizens, municipalities and other actors to use in implementing nature-inclusive building.
- They actively frame their language. At present, 'nature' is not a word they use directly; instead, they find alternative terms and integrate nature in other ways, for example, by using the health angle.
- They integrate nature into other domains.
- They seek to challenge mainstream ideas.
- They actively connect the provincial level with the national level on nature-inclusive building, taking a leading role in involving and influencing national policy.

The general impression is that they are successfully engaging with 'low-hanging fruit' and involving them actively, but the challenge now lies in reaching the 'medium' and 'high-hanging fruit' and ensuring those actors are also actively engaged.

Key players within the Province of Overijssel

Program Strategist

The civil servants involved in developing and implementing the policy program Nature for Each Other are working in a notably innovative and collaborative manner. They actively engage a wide range of organizations during the design phase, fostering a participatory approach to policy-making.

At the center of this initiative is the program strategist; a dynamic, extroverted, and highly energizing person. Their network building style is based on connection and collaboration. They are excellent in linking individuals, organizations, and projects in meaningful ways. Their personal relationship with nature is holistic and spiritual; they view nature not as something separate from humanity, but as an integral part of our existence. This perspective often leads them to seek immersive experiences in natural environments, reinforcing their belief in nature's intrinsic value and interconnectedness.

Policy Makers

The policy makers interviewed as part of this research tend to approach nature from a more analytical and rational standpoint. Their understanding of nature is largely shaped by the concept of ecosystem services, which are the tangible benefits that natural systems provide to society, such as clean air, water, and climate regulation, beneficial to human health.

Their motivation for engaging in nature-inclusive building practices stems from a sense of stewardship. They see themselves as responsible caretakers, working to preserve and protect these services for current and future generations. This pragmatic view influences their policy decisions and underpins their commitment to sustainable development.

(Landscape) Architects:

Several architects and landscape architects are actively contributing to nature-inclusive building solutions. In collaboration with Nature for Each Other, they have developed innovative approaches to integrate nature into the built environment, helping to make such practices more mainstream.

While biodiversity remains a key consideration in their work, they also place a high value on creativity and design freedom.

Exploring the transformative power of the Beuk and the Province of Overijssel

De Beuk and the Province of Overijssel both operate in power arenas where they are regarded as niche innovations and minorities in their views and practices. Both De Beuk and the Province of Overijssel aspire to amplify their views, practices and structures, and to contribute to building a new regime in which building and living with nature is considered normal. To help explore how De Beuk and the province might achieve this, the research team offered to organise a workshop, designed on the basis of the academic review on power (Deliverable 1.7).

During these two workshops, key players from De Beuk and the Province of Overijssel were presented with academic interpretations of power derived from multiple publications (Avelino & Wittmayer, 2016; Avelino, 2021; de Geus et al., 2023). This enabled participants to recognise their position within a power field alongside other actors. Placing themselves in this field helped them to negotiate potential strategies to amplify their values, structures and practices.

The outcomes of these workshops can inform how De Beuk and the Province position themselves outside, in opposition to certain societal domains, and interact with actors representing or working within those domains.

Power workshop with De Beuk

On 19 April 2024, researchers from WR organised a workshop to explicitly discuss the power field around De Beuk. De Beuk identified actors and power relations within and around them. When asked about their transformative potential, the following response was given: *"Nobody knows the rules of the game that belong to different fields, nobody knows which goal to shoot at. We are sitting on a chessboard."* (Core member of De Beuk during the power workshop, April 2024).

At that time, De Beuk was practising prefigurative power (the power to innovate, bringing new ideas and practices into the mainstream) through joining GEN-NL, a global ecovillage network of private entrepreneurial cooperatives that seek to realise multiple government ambitions through their network. These ambitions include social security and care, energy efficiency and sustainability, and nature restoration goals. De Beuk also aims to implement an anti-speculative financing system to secure long-term affordability.

De Beuk practises countervailing power (the power to challenge mainstream practice) by adopting a lower parking standard than that prescribed by building policy. They also joined a fund designed and owned by previously established eco-communities to create opportunities for other eco-community initiatives. *De Beuk* identified themselves as less active in practising reinforcing power (the power to embed new ideas and practices). They acknowledge that living in an eco-community "is not for everyone" and therefore do not wish to enforce it on anyone. However, they do share the view that governments should make it easier for eco-communities to establish themselves.

An important actor contributing to De Beuk's transformative potential is Cooplink, which can also be identified as a significant niche innovator. Cooplink is a support organisation for housing cooperatives:

- It presents initiatives to one another for inspiration.
- It organises knowledge meetings, open to members and non-members alike.
- It offers a space where experiences can be exchanged.
- It consolidates knowledge in a shared knowledge base.
- It represents the interests of housing cooperatives with politicians, financiers and other parties.
- It monitors trends and developments.

In the WR case, Cooplink plays an important role in advising on how to finance the eco-community initiative. This is transformative, as it is generally impossible to obtain a mortgage for an initiative that refrains from dividing the land into private lots. Working literally on common ground is what the eco-community strives for. Cooplink also advises on how to create a contract for the flourishing of nature in the wider area of the residential site. De Beuk will organise a workshop on "living as nature" during Cooplink Day on the 3rd of October 2025. In this way, De Beuk interacts with and potentially influences other cooperative living initiatives to organise themselves in closer integration with nature.

Power workshop with the Province of Overijssel

On 28 May 2024, researchers from WR organised a workshop to explicitly discuss the power field around the nature-inclusive building domain with representatives of *Nature for Each Other*. The representatives identified actors and power relations within and around them. There are many different forms of power at play; below are some examples.

There is a contradiction within the group regarding how to overcome certain powers in play, and whether this should be done by transforming the system itself or by operating within the system while creating their own rules. For example, one participant noted that including nature-inclusive measures in the national building code could serve as a regulatory lever during project outsourcing, since the party issuing the tender holds the power. Others emphasised that while regulations help, internal motivation is equally

important, as they believe intrinsic drive is needed to truly embed nature-inclusive principles.

When discussing the power that exists with others, participants stressed that this is a key form of power within *Nature for Each Other*. Power in this context is less about rules and more about collaboration. It is about collective action. They spoke of valuable “hotspots” where stakeholders with both power and motivation come together.

Participants also reported feeling powerless in the building domain. They expressed: *"There's a lack of professionals who can influence procurement processes. Buyers and tender issuers often prioritise development speed over sustainability."* They also mentioned feeling powerless because change takes so much time, and traditional thinking in the building sector still dominates, which runs counter to nature-inclusive building approaches.

To overcome this sense of powerlessness, transformative power was discussed at the end of the workshop. Two key elements emerged:

- **Storytelling** in many different forms by a wide range of actors is crucial. Professionals, ecologists, landscape architects and the province should share their positive examples, and spaces for dialogue must be sustained.
- **Governmental role** should be strengthened, either by setting conditions for new housing developments or by introducing taxes that reflect societal impact.

1.3 Scalable Bottom-Up Innovations for Transformative Change

De Beuk

De Beuk is an innovation both within and external to the building sector itself. To explain how De Beuk works in an innovative way, we first need to understand the governance context:

The Building Decree 2012 (and its subsequent amendments) is the regulation that sets the technical requirements for the safety, health, usability, energy efficiency and environmental aspects of building. The Building Decree therefore regulates the technical aspects of construction but does not contain any specific or detailed rules on the protection of nature, such as nature reserves or biodiversity on construction sites. However, the influence of nature is addressed indirectly, in particular through requirements relating to environmental aspects and sustainability. Although the Building Decree itself is not directly aimed at nature conservation, there are some relevant rules and references concerning the surrounding area and the environment, including nature. These rules often have to be combined with other laws and regulations, such as the Nature Conservation Act and the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA). Normally, when effects on protected species and habitats have been assessed, a mechanism of compensation is triggered. Compensation is sought through additional financing for the management of nature reserves, enlargement of reserves, or the conversion of agricultural land into natural habitats.

This practice contrasts with the way De Beuk develops its plans for an ecovillage/eco community. They strive to realise the best possible solutions for bio based building materials, energy efficiency, minimising non natural substrates and so forth. This places them ahead of regulatory frameworks. In their efforts, they challenge the usual assumption that sustainable building in close harmony with nature is more expensive than using mainstream materials and procedures.

The greatest drawback here is the enormous amount of time they must dedicate to acquiring and developing knowledge, in order to build their praxis and convince actors with regulatory power in their environment that their ideas are feasible. Together with many

other initiatives, they hold the promise of changing the mainstream culture in project development in the sense that:

- Building with and in harmony with nature is not more costly than building according to the regulations of the Building Decree.
- Building with and in harmony with nature creates an environment in which people can innovate their relationship with nature and adjust their lifestyle accordingly.
- People are enabled to build their dream living environment instead of having to adapt their wishes to what an architect has designed for a category or target group.

Despite this promise, they remain too insignificant to change the mainstream of the building sector, because the return on investment is considered much lower. The significant effects on the wellbeing of new residents, and a testing ground for innovative nature positive lifestyles, is not recognised in the sector, nor in political discourse. Most difficult is that nature positivity collides with the prevailing view in public administration and nature management institutes that creating new areas for living will by definition harm nature. This places De Beuk partly outside the system. However, working outside the system also contributes to De Beuk's transformative potential, because they create space for others who want to live alternatively, whether nature positive or otherwise. This space not only entails the freedom to think and bring alternative ideas into practice, but also allows others to build on the knowledge and experience they have gathered regarding regulation and the establishment of eco communities, thereby creating space for other values in governance systems.

De Beuk has also articulated how they envision increasing their transformative power in the future. They want to remain an important prefigurative force by serving as an area for experimentation—particularly in the field of sustainability and nature inclusive building (e.g. offering a testing ground for innovative energy solutions and water retention, compostable toilets, collaboration with sustainable start ups, and designing 'living houses' that are modular and can 'breathe'). They also consider starting a children's care facility focused on building early connections with nature. To increase their countervailing power, De Beuk is considering making a film about their journey towards realising their dream. In general, they see themselves as an example that ambitions can become reality. They plan to organise excursions and to become a hotspot for students and researchers on innovative, sustainable and circular lifestyles. They also want to contribute to evidence building, for example in relation to close to nature food forest cultivation. De Beuk also intends to offer space for mindfulness and spiritual connections.

All this also feeds into De Beuk's reinforcing ambitions. By providing evidence and showing that it can be done, they hope to inspire local government (e.g. province and municipality) in their conceptualisation of nature inclusive living. More concretely, De Beuk wants to contribute to food forest cultivation standards and circular building techniques. They also aim to form an energy cooperative and are currently organising themselves as a landscape cooperative (landschapscoöperatie). In the longer term, De Beuk also intends to provide (micro) funding to other eco community initiatives.

The province of Overijssel

The province is innovative in the way it creates policy programmes for biodiversity. Their aim is to establish a broad network of people who both have a say in the programme and help to implement it. They have set up a community in which bottom-up innovations are included. Within this community, small amounts of funding are allocated to support these innovations. The province strives to bring nature closer to people and people closer to nature by providing easily applicable tools. This includes, for example, a step-by-step programme for municipalities to make the edges of their territory greener ('Recipe for Edges'), or support for greening social housing. The policy programme genuinely considers how to achieve change, and a number of key players involved in these biodiversity innovations are highlighted below:

Straatboer: An organisation that regreens the gardens of social housing and supports residents in maintaining them. They organise activities to regreen entire streets or neighbourhoods. In this way, this innovator fulfils both an ecological and a social function. They are supported by the policy programme through subsidies and the network of the Province of Overijssel.

Oversticht: A foundation involved in greening (monumental) houses and neighbourhoods, advising on nature-inclusive building and the policies surrounding it. They also aim to inspire others in the dominant building sector to improve their sustainability practices. They are part of the Community of Practice on nature-inclusive building established by the province. We interviewed them and invited them to our workshop on power.

Architect: An architect is involved who is a pioneer in nature-inclusive building. He has strong ideas about what needs to change to raise the standard for nature-inclusive building. He expresses these views in several meetings and is regularly invited to do so.

Nature for Each Other: The civil servants designing and implementing the policy programme Nature for Each Other work in an innovative way. They involve many organisations in the design of their programme. The lead person is highly connecting, extrovert and energising.

Placing transformative biodiversity innovation next to the high impact sector as a system

In the figure below the high impact sector is illustrated and described as a system of practices, structures, and worldviews that is generating innovations or being confronted with challenging novelties. The left column represents the status quo: the dominant ways in which the building sector works, is organised and thinks. The middle column represents innovations that occur within the system but are often incremental and not effective enough to bend the curve of biodiversity loss. De Beuk and the Province both (also) partake in these innovations. However, in addition, they experiment, or (intent to) offer space for experimentation that also fosters practices, structures and worldviews that align with the right column that represents a state of nature positive transformation.

Figure 1: Overview how the transformative biodiversity innovation relates to the high impact sector as a system

1.4 Initial Mapping of Interventions

The case study is aimed at engaging the local community and niche innovators. It is mainly carried out by *De Beuk* and the province themselves, with researchers only playing a modest and consultative role to ensure that we do not interfere in their strategic activities. Our supportive role has been formalised in a cooperation agreement.

Interventions by De Beuk

All decisions concerning *De Beuk* are taken through sociocratic governance, which requires enormous patience and perseverance. This way of decision-making perfectly fits the process of social learning about how to live with nature. A further step in this evolution is the creation of an area management agreement, in which their efforts to help nature flourish around their neighbourhood are formalised in a contract. This is an interesting empowerment strategy because:

- Their future neighbour is the Forest Management Agency, responsible for managing the surrounding Natura 2000 area.
- This may provide a legally valid reason for the agency to set aside the *Didam Arrest* and initiate a one-to-one procurement process.

This evolution can serve as a reliable basis for the creation of new and unprecedented biodiversity innovations that could grow into inspiring examples influencing the mainstream construction sector. However, the municipality, through policy agreements, imposes several regulations on the character of the population that is to live in the new residential area. *De Beuk* is not comfortable with this: they certainly do not welcome the idea of neighbours keeping automobiles next to their houses. They would prefer only nature lovers to join their community. One way they aim to achieve this is by establishing a landscape cooperative. The landscape cooperative will function as the formal property management entity of *De Beuk*. This means the cooperative can also impose rules (or rather agreements) on how residents must manage their environment.

A major barrier for *De Beuk* (on paper) is nitrogen restrictions. In 2024, the Province of Gelderland (distinct from the Province of Overijssel) decided that all development plans within 500 metres of Natura 2000 areas would be suspended until further instructions from the national government. In June 2025, the Dutch Cabinet (Schoof I) collapsed. This postponed all prospects for *De Beuk* and caused major demotivation across all subgroups. *De Beuk* has written a detailed plan outlining how they intend to achieve emission-neutral building and reduce current environmental pressures through sustainable techniques and lifestyle adjustments. They aim to apply for pilot status that would allow them to bypass the decision of the Province of Gelderland. At present, they have engaged a group of Master's students at Wageningen University to assess the feasibility of their plans.

Interventions by the Province of Overijssel

The Province of Overijssel actively contributes to the accessibility of nature by focusing on nature-inclusive building projects in social housing, which are generally located in lower-income areas. These areas also tend to be less green, so investing in green surroundings will improve their climate adaptation. Greener areas will also support public health. Health has been adopted as an additional objective in their policy programme, as this is more likely to be approved and supported in the current political climate, whereas nature as a goal in itself is not widely supported.

They are also making efforts to involve young people, in order to include their perspectives on nature and their vision for the future.

The province pursues several strategies to ensure that the ideas and values of nature-inclusive building reach others:

- They make things practical, local and achievable. For example, they ensure toolboxes are developed for communities, citizens, municipalities and other actors to use in implementing nature-inclusive building.
- They actively frame their language. At present, 'nature' is not a word they use directly; instead, they find alternative terms and integrate nature in other ways. For example, they use the health angle to integrate nature.
- They integrate nature into other domains.
- They seek to challenge mainstream ideas.
- They actively connect the provincial level with the national level on nature-inclusive building, taking a leading role in involving and influencing national policy.

The general impression is that they are successfully engaging with the 'low-hanging fruit' and involving them actively, but the challenge now lies in reaching the 'medium' and 'high-hanging fruit' and ensuring those actors are also actively engaged.

Interventions by the research team

Although the interventions made by research time, should be seen from the perspective of going through a process together, and relate to several forms of actions, such as connecting to other actors via WR, information and knowledge input. We established for example new contacts for De Beuk, such as platforms on housing innovations (e.g. Anders Wonen Maand), policy innovators in the Ministry of the Interior, and technical innovators in building techniques. Some of these new contacts are the result of student research commissioned by De Beuk. The WR research team also organised modest interventions, which are meetings with various objectives and various character fitting the situation of De Beuk and the province. Below a few of those meetings will be illustrated.

One intervention was organised to discuss the issue of climate change through the eyes of ethnic wisdom holders. On Thursday 25 January 2024, the conversation session "*Ecological Crises, Indigenous Knowledge and Your Personal Story*" took place within the scope of the [BIOTraCes](#) project. Together we watched a [recorded conversation](#) between Bayo Akomolafe (author, speaker and teacher), Eriel Tchekwie Deranger (Indigenous Climate Action, Global Indigenous Youth Caucus) and Angaangaq Angakkorsuaq (elder, traditional healer, spiritual teacher and shaman from Greenland). In the conversation, the speakers shared the impact of climate change from their perspective and what we can learn from traditional wisdom. After showing this recording, we shared our impressions and ideas in smaller groups. Members of De Beuk were able to establish contact with innovative and academic knowledge brokers on human–nature relationships.

Another intervention was a strategic workshop in January 2025. We brought together nature protection and nature management organisations, organisations from the building sector, innovation organisations, the ministry, and an organisation for ecovillages, to reflect on the mismatch between how a growing number of citizens wish to live with or in nature and what the building sector as a system delivers. This mismatch was introduced through a survey of 5,000 inhabitants who expressed a desire to live alternatively. The results of this survey, together with other research on alternative ways of living, were presented by one of its directors. A philosopher specialising in nature–human relationships stretched the comfort zone of the participants by reviewing alternative relationships with nature. A director of a network of ecovillages presented both the advantages and drawbacks of ecovillages, alongside the challenges. We also addressed the tension between nature protection and nature positivity. These elements were used to discuss barriers and opportunities, and to assess how the system could perform better and become more inclusive. The outcome was compiled into a fact sheet and policy brief, which was disseminated by the participants.

A workshop was initiated by a member of De Beuk on 'Living as Nature' at the Cooplinc-dag (3 October 2025). This is an annual event organised by Cooplinc, aimed at anyone involved

in, or wishing to become involved in, cooperative living initiatives in the Netherlands. The workshop was co-hosted by a member of *De Beuk*, a member of eco-village Boekel, and a researcher from BIOTraCes. During the workshop, the researcher presented the results from our social-ecological systems analysis (see Chapter 5). The two other co-hosts presented practical examples of nature-positive systems from their (envisioned) ecovillages. The majority of the workshop was devoted to inviting participants to adopt a more-than-human perspective and to discuss how to coexist with humans. A set of cards, developed by Jay Marisca Gietzelt (2024) and adapted by Zoe van Eldik (2025), was used to introduce and guide participants into a more-than-human perspective.

This discussion led to nine concrete recommendations, which will be taken up by GEN-NL, the Dutch national ecovillage network:

1. Recognising the rights of nature
2. Living by the narrative of 'human-inclusive nature'
3. Limiting artificial lights and sounds
4. Including the voices of nature in decisions (e.g. nature as a board member)
5. Monitoring ecological wellbeing via 'icon species' (species identified by local nature networks as fundamental to local landscapes)
6. Learning from examples in other parts of the world. The Netherlands could be inspired by the concept of urban national parks (e.g. London). Within this concept, ecovillages could serve as excellent urban–nature connectors.
7. Promoting nature in education: teaching children that we are part of nature
8. Ecovillage residents taking care of nature, so this no longer has to be the sole responsibility of nature management organisations or the state
9. Building with nature also includes infrastructure

1.5 Discussion

The transformative nature of the Wageningen case remains open to debate. While its potential has been thoroughly analysed, the tangible impact achieved by our societal partners is difficult to measure. This, however, is not due to any lack of effort or commitment on their part.

The key innovators within De Beuk distinguish themselves from the mainstream in several ways. Their values and lifestyles challenge conventional norms, particularly those upheld by the traditional housing market. Young people and the elderly, in particular, often find themselves excluded from this system, forced into living arrangements that disconnect them from both nature and community. De Beuk's vision actively counters these dominant mechanisms. Yet complete detachment from the prevailing system is not feasible. To effect change, members of De Beuk recognise the need to understand and engage with the mainstream. Remaining entirely outside the system would undermine their ability to negotiate and influence outcomes.

As a result, De Beuk members invest significant personal time in learning formal regulations, mastering technical knowledge, and building relationships with local authorities and landscape stakeholders. Despite these efforts, their ability to secure land for development remains uncertain.

In contrast, the Province of Overijssel operates from within the system, seeking to drive change through institutional channels. Civil servants must navigate the shifting landscape of provincial councils and national directives, both of which reflect the broader political climate. Their "transformative arena" is subject to change every four years, or sooner, in the event of a cabinet collapse. While working within the system can be restrictive, the civil servants involved in this case have demonstrated remarkable creativity and

resilience in pursuing biodiversity goals. Their work requires courage, endurance, and a strong belief in the value of nature-inclusive development, even when the system temporarily resists change.

The limitations to transformative impact in this case appear to stem more from challenges of scalability than from a lack of innovation. Scalability could be enhanced if the Environment Act were amended to include a formal designation for eco-villages. Additionally, integrating knowledge-sharing and alternative financing mechanisms into the CPO (Collective Private Commissioning) policy, or even beyond it, it could support broader adoption.

A truly scalable solution would involve adapting residential permitting processes to accommodate specific lifestyle choices, such as electric-only vehicles, prohibition of fireplaces, and pesticide-free gardening. If residents were willing to comply with such conditions, they could be permitted to live closer to protected natural areas. These fundamental shifts can be initiated by grassroots efforts like De Beuk and supported by local governments such as the Province of Overijssel, but ultimately they require top-down enforcement to become systemic.

The situation of De Beuk shows that the sector is not prepared to deal with innovations emerging from outside the public-private partnership. The De Beuk innovation is directly based on fundamental values and can be seen as ideological, moral, and even epistemic in its relationship to nature. As an innovation, it seeks recognition and space to become reality. Neither of these is currently happening. The polysystem of planning, designing, regulating and constructing new houses has become self-referential and resists attempts to reach the canon of good practices.

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Conclusion

The deliverable “*Transformative Biodiversity Innovations Analysis*” demonstrates that transformative innovation in the field of biodiversity cannot be reduced to a set of technologies, managerial tools, or institutional top-down schemes. The case studies make clear that the transformative potential of innovations does not follow a defined “recipe,” but is instead inseparable from the local contexts in which it emerges, through collective work and shared actions. Biodiversity innovation appears as a complex and non-linear territorial process, produced through the interaction of local actors’ efforts, shifting ecological configurations, diverse political regimes, and emerging cultural imaginaries. In this sense, a common thread across all the contexts analysed—from the Simeto Valley to the Mértola reserve, from Swedish forests to Basque schools, from Romanian rural landscapes to the traditional knowledge of Hungarian shepherds—is the presence of structural fractures within existing governance systems: centralized decision-making models, a widespread logic that conceives “nature” as a homogeneous entity separate from humans, and institutions often unable to value local or relational forms of knowledge. At the same time, the case studies show that transformative forms of innovation emerge where communities, associations, educational groups, small farmers, or civic networks manage to initiate participatory processes and articulate counter-imaginaries of place, redefining the very meanings of biodiversity and care, and especially forging a connection between these two elements. These experiences, however, face numerous challenges: they often operate under conditions of marginality, resource scarcity, and power asymmetries that limit their effectiveness and duration, as well as their capacity to influence governance structures directly. Innovation and transformation therefore require confronting the politics of inclusion and exclusion. In each case study—albeit in different ways—local actors face structural forms of exclusion rooted in agricultural, forestry, urban, or other policies shaped by ecological and productive simplification. These institutional forms of exclusion coexist with non-institutionalized mechanisms grounded in cultural norms or historically sedimented socio-ecological relations.

As the Romanian case illustrates, there is often a prevailing perception that rural communities’ environmental knowledge is outdated and inadequate for contemporary conservation practices. Such a view contributes to the marginalisation of communities that have co-evolved with their environments over centuries. This dynamic is also evident in the Italian case: in Sicily, intensive orchard systems and the growing pressure of agro-photovoltaic installations produce a landscape oriented toward the maximisation of economic yield, thereby reducing the socio-ecological complexity of the valley and intensifying the marginalisation of certain forms of knowledge and of the communities that hold them. This process is supported not only by policy frameworks, but also by a deepening disconnection from the river ecosystem and a progressive loss and devaluation of pre-monoculture agricultural knowledge. In Mértola as well, the socio-economic fragility of local communities and the risk of marginalizing traditional knowledge complicate the construction of inclusive transformative pathways; similarly, in the Basque Country, biodiversity-oriented innovation encounters barriers to participation for the most vulnerable groups within a highly segregated school system. Alongside mechanisms of exclusion, the case studies shed light on the forms of inclusion and the conditions that enable them. In the contexts analysed, inclusion emerges when the plural value of ecological and social relations is recognized, and when shared spaces of experimentation take shape: community laboratories, regenerative agriculture networks, participatory processes, and arenas for open discussion in which different perspectives can meaningfully interact. These spaces—often self-organized—not only foster new environmental practices (and thus potential innovations), but also generate forms of belonging, care, and mutual recognition that constitute the social infrastructure of transformative change. This is the case, for instance, in Lithuania, where, in a context marked by the absence of participatory spaces and dialogue, action research laid the groundwork for creating arenas of debate and encounter among often conflicting parties. It is precisely the reflective and intentional practice of action research that enables the expansion of the relational fabric already present in local territories, thereby contributing to processes of inclusion. This is what

occurred, for example, in the research carried out by the University of Twente, which supported the co-production of knowledge regarding the commoning practices of Foodpark Amsterdam and created arenas for exchange with an expanded academic community. Supporting these inclusive mechanisms are often the innovators or changemakers themselves. Although they differ widely across contexts, these actors share certain key characteristics: they can weave relationships, facilitate dialogue across different knowledge systems, sustain the ecological memory-scape of a territory, promote collective resource management, and connect humans with other forms of life. It is important to emphasize that they are not “innovators” in a strictly technical sense, nor are the innovations they bring to the territory “groundbreaking discoveries.” Both innovators and innovations are inextricably linked to place-making practices, to long-term historical processes, to specific institutional frameworks, and to specific socio-ecological conditions. Their significance does not lie in the “novelty” of their solutions, but in their ability to generate political imagination and activate locally based transformative processes that reshape relationships between communities and their life environments. In this sense, the core of transformation is understood and practiced as a relational and territorial process rather than a technical event or technological solution. Because they are deeply embedded in context, one of the major challenges these innovations face concerns their scalability. The cases analysed suggest that scalability does not consist in mechanically replicating local practices, but in creating systemic conditions that allow such practices to flourish—also by intervening at the level of governance and institutions. Indeed, bottom-up innovations face significant challenges in achieving broader recognition and scalability due to existing systemic structures, policy frameworks, or a lack of integration with mainstream approaches. For example, the Wageningen case specifically details the systemic resistance encountered by bottom-up initiatives, such as eco-villages, in achieving scalability, highlighting the necessity of top-down policy changes (e.g., amending environmental acts, adapting permitting processes) and engagement with mainstream systems for broader adoption. The Hungarian case similarly reflects on the need for bottom-up scalable innovation, aiming to build collective advocacy capable of influencing policy despite the current limited decision-making authority of marginalized communities. Within this landscape, a decisive role is played by the interventions that animate territories and introduce discontinuities into established routines. The interventions observed across the case studies take diverse forms: outdoor school laboratories, artistic practices, participatory mapping, community gardens, consultation processes, civic initiatives, ecological walks, festivals, protests, educational projects, and environmental regeneration activities. Despite their heterogeneity, these moments share a common effect: they break the linearity of dominant practices and allow communities to experiment with different ways of inhabiting places and multispecies relations. Interventions function as political devices capable of redistributing visibility and power, giving voice to groups often excluded from decision-making processes—such as children, small farmers, marginalized residents, or non-human species—and rendering visible ecological conflicts that would otherwise remain hidden. In the Swedish case, the interventions took the form of workshops and tailored discussion sessions designed specifically for the communities involved, their interests, and their particular needs. The aim was to deepen knowledge about the relationship between forest governance and the agency of forest owners, and to create testing grounds for introducing and discussing various niche innovations in forest management. Even when they do not leave permanent material infrastructures, interventions generate lasting effects: their importance lies in their ability to plant the seeds for building territorial alliances and to set in motion transformational processes that extend beyond the temporality of the event.

In conclusion, the analysis of transformative biodiversity innovations across the nine case studies shows that innovation and biodiversity are connected through the practice of care as a transformative agent. In the territorial contexts examined, the possibility of inhabiting places with care manifests as a form of daily attention to relations between humans, non-humans, and socio-ecological settings. It is the care of Sicilian farmers who maintain diversified small plots; the care of teachers who transform schoolyards into more-than-human environments; the care of Mértola’s inhabitants who preserve local seeds and ecological knowledge; the care of Dutch activists who imagine new forms of collective land

use; the care of forest inhabitants in Sweden who promote management practices that respect biodiversity. This material, affective, and multispecies attention is not a secondary or romantic element of transformation: it is the condition that makes it possible to create inclusive ecologies and build non-extractive relationships with living environments, subverting business-as-usual policies. In this sense, care constitutes the political infrastructure of biodiversity.